

**Exploring The Relationship Between Social
Media And Consumer Purchase Intentions
In The Financial Services Industry**

By

Ali Usman

**A Thesis in Completion of
Doctor of Business Administration**

**Supervised By
Professor Wilson Ozuem**

University of the West of Scotland

Table of Contents

1. Chapter 1. Introduction	07
1.1. Problem Statement.....	09
1.2. Research Question.....	11
1.3. Aims and Objectives.....	11
1.4. Rationale of the Study.....	12
1.5. Background and Significance.....	20
2. Chapter 2. Critical Review of Literature	26
2.1. Introduction.....	26
2.2. Conceptual Clarification.....	26
2.3. Development of Social Media.....	32
2.3.1. Social Media and Social Capital.....	33
2.3.2. Web 2.0 and Web 3.0.....	35
2.3.3. User-Generated Content (UGC).....	40
2.3.4. Development of Social networking Sites (SNS).....	45
2.3.5. SNS and Brand Communities.....	46
2.4. Social Media in Theoretical Context	50
2.4.1. Social Influence Theory.....	56
2.4.2. Development of Social Influence Theory.....	60
2.4.3. Social Media in Perspective of Social Influence Theory.....	66
2.4.4. Social Media Value Perception and Social Influence.....	70
2.5. Social Media and Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM).....	72
2.5.1. Online Social Influence and eWOM.....	75
2.6. Consumers Purchase Intentions.....	77

2.6.1. Theoretical context of Consumers Purchase Intentions.....	79
2.6.2. Social media and consumers' purchase intentions.....	80
2.6.3. Social media and consumers' purchase intentions in perspective of Social Influence Theory.....	83
3. Chapter 3. Research Design.....	94
3.1. Research Paradigm	94
3.2. Social Constructionism Paradigm.....	95
3.3. Research Methodology.....	114
3.3.1. Qualitative Research Methodology.....	114
3.3.2. Social media and Consumers Purchase Intentions in Qualitative Research.....	116
3.4. Research Strategy.....	119
3.4.1. Case study Research.....	119
3.4.2. Social Media and Consumers Purchase Intentions in a Case Study.....	120
3.5. Sample Selection.....	122
3.5.1. Pilot Study.....	123
3.5.2. Data Collection and Sample Size.....	124
3.5.2.1. Sample Size.....	125
3.5.3. Semi-Structured Interviews.....	126
3.5.4. Focus groups.....	126
3.6. Limitations of the Methodology Applied.....	127
3.6. Research Ethics.....	127
Chapter 4. Analysis of Factual Evidence.....	129
4.1. Introduction.....	129
4.2. Rational of Thematic Analysis.....	129

4.3. Major Themes Reflecting Antecedents of Social Media Use.....	139
4.3.1. Consumers Media Fulfilment.....	139
4.4. Major Themes Reflecting Social Influence.....	148
4.4.1. Social Complaisance.....	148
4.4.2. Value-Incorporation.....	151
4.4.3. Self-Fulfilment.....	155
4.5. Major Themes Reflecting Purchase Intentions.....	158
4.5.1. Online Verbal Evidence.....	158
4.5.2 Buying Intentions.....	162
4.6. Summery of the Key Findings amd Managerial Implications.....	165
4.6.1. Managerial Implications.....	172
5. Conceptual Framework.....	173
5.1. Introduction.....	173
5.2. Existing Literature and Research.....	174
5.3. Conceptual Framework.....	182
6. Conclusions.....	189
6.1. Introduction.....	189
6.2. Conclusion.....	189
6.3. Contribution to Literature and Theory.....	191
6.4. Managerial Implications.....	194
6.5. Limitations of the Research and Future Guidelines.....	197
7. References.....	199

Acknowledgement

First and foremost, I would like to acknowledge and thank my supervisor Professor Wilson Ozuem for his excellent supervision and guidance throughout the entire research process. Your dedicated supervision, constructive criticism towards this research and your patience played an extremely important role in my thesis completion.

Secondly, I would like to acknowledge my parents for providing me this opportunity to study a doctoral degree and for giving me emotional and mental support whenever I needed it.

Abstract

Within the context of social media, purchase intentions depend on heterogenic online social exchanges, as well as the informational accomplishments, culture, online reference group interactions and relational experiences of consumers. Heterogenic social media interactions (which are informational, social, hedonic and utilitarian in nature) on social media platforms such as SNSs enable consumers to communicate, interact and exchange content about products and services in the financial services industry based on UGC. Such content can transform attitudes and intentions. Therefore the current study investigates the role of social media in consumer purchase intentions in the context of social influence theory. The study adopts a social constructionist paradigm based on qualitative inquiry to understand the role of social media in developing consumer purchase intentions in the financial services industry. The findings identify that heterogeneous social media interactions amongst online members result in three distinct levels of social influence which are compliance, internalisation and identity. These significantly determine consumer purchase intentions. Furthermore, they influence the subjective rationale of the decision-making process. The study also provides a conceptual framework to describe the application of new knowledge to practice. The managerial implications and future guidelines of the study have also been provided.

Chapter 1: Introduction

A key motive behind the development of social media is to use a computer-mediated environment and digital network to create value for financial services firms through promotional activities in business to consumer (B2C) settings in a utilitarian economy (Michaelidou et al., 2011). With the rise of Web 2.0 and web 3.0 based online communication platforms, financial services organisations have begun to identify and investigate the opportunities and possibilities to leverage information with convenience and efficiency (Dootson et al., 2016; Mitic and Kapoulas, 2012). Interactive UGC on social media platforms such as SNSs have been adopted to not only share information and promotions about financial services, but also to enable online users to offer feedback or make specific inquiries about products and services. This allows them to engage in online discussions. Social media is defined by (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010) as “a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and that allow the creation and exchange of User Generated Content.” Likewise social networking sites SNSs are social media platforms developed on Web 2.0 based internet technologies which enable binary communication and the flow of information between online users through digital content exchange (Kim et al., 2018). Such digital content is called User-Generated Content (UGC) as it enables two-way communication between companies and consumers on social media. UGC not only enables marketers to communicate personalised promotional messages to online users, but it also enhances their ability to reach out and provide real time care to potential customers using multiple social media platforms (Usman and Okafor, 2018).

The adoption of social media platforms for online marketing enables marketers to collect vast amounts of customer data by introducing a social element to their heterogeneous social exchanges. This is crucial for transforming consumer attitudes and intentions about financial services products and services (Karaduman, 2013). Within B2C environments, the online retail financial services industry which includes banking and the stock exchange market has experienced the highest rates of usage and has the greatest potential for further growth when

compared to IT, telecommunications, consumer goods and the automobile industry (Bukovina, 2016; Siikanen et al., 2018).

The explicit role of social media comes into play as a mode of value creation for business. It provides a credible platform for online users to communicate, and to enhance their social interactions. In this way they can strengthen their relationships with brands or firms as part of a wider socialisation process in B2C environments (Christodoulides, 2009). This enables a process of online user interactivity across social media based on sharing content and knowledge about financial services (Shi et al., 2014; Kupp and Anderson, 2007). Kohli et al. (2014) argue that social media is explicitly important in terms of influencing customer-brand relationships and satisfaction levels. It also facilitates word of mouth recommendations leading to increased levels of customer purchase intentions when it comes to consumer goods (Raacke and Bonds-Raacke, 2008; Erkan and Evans, 2016; Muhammad et al., 2017). It supports technology based marketing, customer engagement and service recovery in the banking and financial services sector (Pry, 2010; Vemuri, 2010; Stone, 2009; Mitic and Kapoulas, 2012).

Social media has shown tremendous growth due to its very wide reach. Social media connects many potential customers across the globe within the financial services industry (Bonson and Flores, 2011). Social media is expected to achieve similar rates of growth in future years (Zhou, 2017). The online presence of financial services companies accommodates the comprehensive and personalised informational inquiries of online users. It enables real-time communication between potential customers and clients in order to establish the grounds for consumer-brand relationships (Murray et al., 2014). Today, the most active social media platforms in online environments are Facebook, Youtube, Twitter, Google+, Instagram, LinkedIn, Pinterest and Quora. Of these platforms, Facebook, Youtube, Twitter and Instagram have seen the most successful growth rates. Facebook in particular is ranked as the most active social media platform with more than 2.5 billion online members. (Muntiga et al., 2011; Shi et al., 2014)

1.1. Problem Statement

There is some scepticism surrounding the use of social media in the financial services industry. This is linked to concerns about information privacy, the limited control companies have over data, and most importantly, the reliability and effectiveness of social media as a means to communicate and promote financial services information designed to transform online users into potential customers (Dootson et al., 2016). Therefore, the need for research to explore how and why Web 2.0 based social media marketing should be an integral part of marketing strategies to influence the attitudes and intentions of the online users is very clear.

Previous research has highlighted the role of social media in transforming consumer behaviors in the financial services industry (Dootson et al., 2016; Murray et al., 2014; Rajaobelina et al., 2013) However, a detailed conceptualization of social media marketing communication as part of wider corporate marketing strategies has yet to be widely investigated in the context of financial services (Hoffman et al., 2013; Pine and Gilmore, 2011). It is necessary to conceptualize online social media to not only better understand the implications for marketing frameworks, but also to determine the extent to which social media plays a significant role in developing consumer purchase intentions by changing the intentions, attitudes, beliefs, opinions and feelings of consumers (Cheung et al., 2011; Barreda et al., 2015). The present study is an opportunity to reduce this empirical gap by conceptualising social media within a discussion of social influence theory to illuminate the practical use of social media as a means to transform purchase related attitudes and behaviours in the financial services industry. The specific area of focus is consumer purchase intentions in B2C retail financial services. The current investigation provides a much needed empirically tested psychological framework to understand the psychological impact of the social influence model and its capacity to shape brand sales by transforming online users into potential customers.

Social media provides an explicit advantage over traditional media since it enables two-way communications between businesses and empowers consumers and end users to become active

participants rather than passive consumers (Tsai and Men, 2013). In this way, social media marketing varies from the traditional marketing communications paradigm (Dillenbourg, 2008). The consumer-centric, online social media concept, which facilitates two-way communications, fulfils the utilitarian and hedonic needs of online consumers. These needs include information acquisition, speedy exchanges, social networking and social information sharing in SNS brand communities. Such interactive and relational experiences impact both directly and indirectly on consumer attitudes. This can create rational changes to the opinions of consumers. It can shape product selection and service evaluations as well as brand-purchase intensity and subsequent post purchase behaviours amongst consumers (Godey et al., 2016; Spillecke and Perrey, 2012). The impartial influence of social media and its capacity to shape and modify consumer behaviour is one notable outcome which allows marketers to respond to the online behaviours of consumers. It also allows them to develop a consumer centric marketing strategy. However, the existing literature provides little evidence of, and few guidelines for using social media to promote products and services through online behavioural modelling. There is therefore work to do in order to fully understand the complex behavioural and attitudinal changes that are notable amongst customers (Cheung et al., 2011). The absence of a widely accepted conceptualization of social media, and the limited empirical modelling to expose how social media can significantly influence purchase related behaviours leaves a gap in the academic literature in terms of social media research. As such, the current research represents an effort to make a rational contribution towards the literature by exploring the extent to which social media can transform consumer behaviours and convert online users into potential customers. Further, the transition to the digital communications paradigm from traditional modes of communication has increased the involvement of consumers in brand- related online activities and has stimulated their behavioral engagement with SNS brand groups and communities themed around financial services (Jin and Phua, 2014; Menon and O'Connor, 2007).

Social media is important to customers since it facilitates interactions and connects them to brand related information and content. However, more work is needed to understand the role of social media in shaping perceptions and transforming purchase intentions into sales (Hajli et al., 2017). Only a handful of studies have investigated the role of social media in shaping purchase intentions. Very few studies have explored the ability of social influence frameworks to

determine purchase intentions (Hutter et al., 2013). Much work lies ahead to develop an understanding of social influence modelling in relation to consumer purchase behaviours. The present study represents an opportunity to close this empirical gap by developing an understanding of social media marketing techniques based on a social influence model. Such a development could shed light on the practical use of social media in transforming purchase related attitudes and behaviours. The current investigation provides the necessary empirical basis to test a relevant psychological framework to better understand social influence and the power of influence to create leads in the context of financial services. It will also provide guidance for managers in relation to how social consumer influence can transform purchase behaviours in order to achieve real time results using social media networking sites to efficiently engage with online consumers.

1.2. Research Questions

Q1. What are the different purposes of consumer social media interactions, and how do these heterogeneous social media interactions develop multiple levels of social influence?

Q2. How do the multiple levels of social influence that are developed through heterogeneous social media interactions change consumer purchase intentions in the financial services industry?

Q3. In what ways does knowledge of the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions in online marketing strategies have implications for the financial services industry?

1.3. Aims and Objectives

The study provides insight into how external communication sources such as marketing promotions and communication can influence value perceptions, gratification, and online group behaviours such as purchase intentions. As with SNSs, there is a need to understand how complex social interactions based on UGC can act as tools for developing social influence. The research also provides an empirical based model of social influence which can be used to develop an appropriate marketing strategy to identify the specific needs of consumers in order to

promote relevant products. The research also sheds light on the use of SNSs as key tools to promote individual and group level interactions. It provides guidance for financial services marketers to engage with customers using targeted promotional content in order to increase two-way communications and raise satisfaction levels.

The objectives of the study are

- To highlight how heterogeneous social media interactions on social media develop the multiple forms of social influence which transform consumer opinions, attitudes and intentions in the context of the financial services industry.
- To highlight how the multiple forms of social influence (compliance, internalisation and identity) developed through heterogenic social interactions shape consumer purchase intentions.
- To highlight the benefits of conceptualising social media to understand consumer purchase intentions, and to use social influence theory to revolutionise the marketing strategies of financial services companies in order to tailor the behaviour of online users and promote products to meet specific needs.

1.4. Rationale of the Study

The transition from traditional modes of marketing to consumer centric marketing approaches in B2C environments has had an explicit impact on socio-cognitive consumer behaviors, and this has captured the attention of marketers and academic researchers (Michaelidou et al., 2017). The utilitarian and hedonic experiential values of social media have expanded perceptions of relationship marketing and have revolutionised integrated marketing communications, especially in the retail banking industry (Shih et al., 2014; Huang and Benyoucef, 2013). This study therefore represents a unique effort to modify the empirical work of (Zhou, 2017), since it sheds light on changes to the beliefs, opinions, attitudes and intentions of individuals as the outcome of

the heterogenic nature of social media and complex online social interactions between online users on SNSs brand communities. This is discussed from the perspective of social influence theory. According to (Zhou, 2017), social influence significantly influences social media behaviours and knowledge adoption. Zhou (2017) examined the determinants of individual social interactions on social media (i.e. informational and emotional support) that lead to the development of social influence on SNSs. The author found that changes to the behaviours of individuals, such as the continuous use of SNSs is subject to their acceptance of one of three dimensions of social influence. These dimensions are compliance, internalisation and identity, and they have developed as a result of heterogeneous social media interactions. Zhou's (2017) work is limited to the context of understanding the impact of social influence on the opinions, attitudes and behaviours of individuals on social media within socio-psychological disciplines. Such knowledge could have an impact on our understanding of changes to the behaviours of individuals in a business context, and especially in the context of online marketing and electronic commerce. This provides evidence that heterogeneous social media interactions develop multiple forms of social influence which could change consumer perceptions, attitudes and opinions about products and services. The current study is an opportunity to explore how heterogeneous social media interactions develop distinctive forms of social influence in the context of online marketing and communication. The study illuminates how group based social interactions in brand communities on SNSs develop multiple levels of social influence. It reveals how behavioural uniformity is developed amongst members of online social groups, and how this ultimately impacts on consumer purchase intentions.

The leap from internet based digital media and computer mediated marketing applications towards more sophisticated Web 2.0 based social media has rigorously transformed the purchase behaviours of online users by enhancing communication speeds and informational interactions on SNSs. This activity incurs little cost and takes place across narrower time periods (Tsai and Men, 2013). Social media has become one of the primary tools of online marketing, and it has captured the attention of many since it has closed the communication gap between businesses and consumers, as well as between consumers and other consumers (Tsai and Bagozzi, 2014). However, little is known about social media and its generic acceptability as a real time online marketing tool to transform online users into potential customers. There is little empirical

understanding around this phenomenon, and further research is therefore needed. Indeed, research is required to understand more about the role of online social interactions and informational exchange in SNSs from the perspective of social influence theory. Such theory can explain how media gratifications can develop into distinctive levels of social influence. Furthermore it can help explain how the distinctive levels of social influence can influence purchase intentions and decision making behaviours (Zhu and Chen, 2015).

Online behavioural tailoring has become an integral part of online marketing strategies. The environment of social media in which online users are supported with informative resources to organize and engage in social interactions has led to the development of group based intentional social actions. These occur at multiple levels of social influence and involve compliance, internalization and identity (Shen et al., 2011). The functional impact of such social influence enables companies to learn about the gratification and experiential (utilitarian and hedonic) needs of online users. This not only supports the development of new products and services, but it also maximizes opportunities to enhance levels of existing customer loyalty towards brands (Ozuem et al., 2016; Hsiao and Chiou, 2015; Yamoah et al., 2014). It further helps to cater for the informational needs of online consumers through the development of appropriate marketing and communications strategies. These enable businesses to establish a direct connection with end-user consumers at relatively low cost, and in an efficient and timely manner. This can create a positive change in purchase behaviours (Bhatli and Mejri, 2015). In this way, businesses could create significant leads by taking advantage of interactions between online members when they join communities to satisfy their need for information and a sense of belonging by associating themselves with certain brand communities or groups where they feel social connected and recognized after interacting with similar like-minded online users (Bamberg et al., 2007; Zhang et al., 2015). Such an increased sense of belonging enhances the desire of online shoppers to be part of an online brand community, and it significantly increases the trust of online users in financial services. Indeed, the level of interaction and information sharing in the group dictates the extent to which consumers will trust the brands they are interacting with. Online users feel more valued by associating with certain brands. This speaks to the idea of online engagement and it significantly triggers purchase intentions (Tsai and Men, 2013; Gutiérrez-Cillán et al., 2017).

Social media enables active participation and empowers users to communicate and respond to promotional content (Nelson-Field et al., 2012). The principle of UGC has changed the layout of social media and has provided a cutting-edge technological benefit, positioning social media as a prevalent information source that can tailor the behaviour of customers (Zhou, 2017). UGC media has transformed communication tools and strategies in such a way that organisations have greater control over informational flows, and the speedy exchange of information. Organisations can also understand consumers in more detail, and specifically their behaviours in relation to search and social interaction patterns (Gallaughar and Ransbotham, 2010). This two-way phenomenon supports communication between consumers and businesses and transforms online users into active participants in promotional communication processes (Ozuem et al., 2016). For example, on SNSs, online users can actively express views at an individual or group level, and can circulate messages and evaluate information on the basis of knowledge sharing. SNSs such as Facebook increase the validity of social media as an informational platform to promote products and services, and to transform consumer behaviour through informal and compliance-based socialization (Hajli et al., 2017).

The explicit role of social media as a vehicle to influence the socio-cognitive mindsets of online users and transform them into potential customers adds economic value to the marketing communications that take place between consumers and companies (Hutter et al., 2013). In addition to the socialization perspective of SNSs, social media also helps promote brands and empowers companies to create online brand identities and brand communities (Hajli and Sims, 2015). The most recognizable and ubiquitous forms of UGC exchange include micro blogs, weblogs, podcasts, social blogs and ratings. An example of the latter format is Facebook, which hosts brand related group discussions. Based on the exchanging of UGC, companies endorse their brands on SNSs in their perspective brand communities and groups with an embedded message of brand value to improve customer lifestyles, or to meet specific needs (Zaglia, 2013). This has a considerable advantage for managers in terms of developing new forums of online interaction to gain more knowledge about the problems and choices consumers encounter. However, there is also a slight risk associated with such communities connected to the possibility

of losing control while promoting the brand group and community-based social interaction. For example, retail financial service companies such as banks have harnessed social media brand communities to play a vital role in communicating promotional information about financial services such as credit cards, leases, car finance, mortgages and insurance. This also empowers online members to interact with each other to gain knowledge about products and services through group based social interactions (Liang and Chen, 2009). Such group based social interactions on SNSs take the form of group discussions, blogs, poll participation and tagging. These features facilitate information exchange between members which increases value perceptions and the level of gratification associated with the use of retail financial services. Examples of success in this regard are products such as credit cards, leases, mortgages and life insurance. The aesthetic value, in terms of consumer engagement with promotional content and the individual or group based social exchange of information explicitly helps to develop a rational mind-set and positive buying behaviour (Kozinets et al., 2010). Hutter et al. (2013) argued that such online social interactions and group based mutual social actions across social media develop social influence, which significantly affects decision-making behaviors amongst online members. The phenomenon of consumer engagement has a subsequent impact on purchase intentions since it elicits a sense of loyalty and affiliation between the consumer and the brand, giving more recognition to the brand (Hollebeek et al., 2014).

Social networking in brand groups and communities are important constituents of the social environment as they empower individuals to interact and engage on a scale much larger than in the case of small, individual dyadic interactions (Lu, 2018). The impetus of online social networking groups increases individual tendencies to join in with these groups to benefit from psychological affiliation, mutual agreement, the internalization of values, local proximity and the establishment of self-defined relationships which shape social identity (Aiello et al., 2012). Within the context of online marketing and communication, social networking helps organisations to investigate the social aggregations of online actors along with the social and topical dimensions of social interactions. This is achieved by actively participating in group discussions and sharing content via blogs and micro blogs on online SNSs (Manthiou et al., 2013). Smaller groups are less heterogeneous, whereas larger groups are more heterogeneous, and this promotes diversity amongst SNSs (Zhou, 2017).

SNSs play a significant role in shaping the purchase related behaviours of online users, since the online environment has removed many barriers such as geographical location and time. Social networking facilitates prompt access and interaction mechanisms. Such heterogenic social interactions in the form of discussions, blogs and reviews increases engagement with promotional content and develops the potential of Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) which, in turn significantly influences purchase intentions (Okazaki, 2009; Tsai and Men, 2013). eWOM is the outcome of group-based social interactions and yields tremendous benefits for companies when it comes to the practical use of the social media. This is because social media promotes informational interactions between members and increases brand awareness and identity by means of increasing credibility and trust in brands (Kelly et al., 2010). This makes eWOM a vital tool to enhance returns on investment and enhance economic value and exchange between companies and customers. Indeed, eWOM communication, within online brand groups and communities is a critical factor in the online branding activities of firms (Huang et al., 2011; Kozinets et al., 2010). However, in terms of social media research, one question that remains unanswered in the literature is the extent to which group-based informational social interactions and knowledge sharing directly influence consumer engagement to create eWOM. eWOM positions social media as a front-runner in boosting the sales revenue of companies by influencing consumer purchase intentions

The current study draws upon the work of Zhou (2017), who studied changes in the participative behavior of individuals on SNSs. The research explained how informational and emotional support on social media develops multiple levels of social influence which changes the behavior of individuals towards participation in SNSs communities. Their study provided a subjective understanding of the direct connection between social media and changes in individual attitudes and behaviors. It was created from the perspective of social influence theory on SNSs. However, the current research has sought to conceptualize social media in a different context to establish a connection between social media and the purchase intentions of consumers in terms of social influence theory as applied to marketing (Kelman, 1958). Social influence theory (Kelman, 1958) implies an explicit notion of the implicit psychological impacts on the attitudes and behaviors of online consumers (Kang and Schuett, 2013). However, not much is empirically

known about how social interactions on SNSs influence consumers psychologically, and how it motivates consumers to develop purchase intentions in brand groups and communities. Our understanding of social influence in SNSs brand communities is at an early stage of development (Haffaker, 2010). The limitations of the previous research have been noted and it is clear that no significant research has been developed using social influence theory to suggest that social media shapes consumer purchase intentions. Furthermore the limitations of previous research also note that social influence theory has been empirically investigated in the context of social media to measure changes in the attitudes, beliefs and intentions of individuals from a social psychological context only (Zhou, 2017; Cheung et al., 2011; Zhou, 2011; Zhou, 2017; Hwang, 2014). No significant research has been carried out to conceptualize social media from the perspective of social influence theory to measure changes to the intentions of individuals in online marketing and communication contexts. The retail financial services industry has never before been explored from this perspective. This leaves an extensive gap in the literature and it creates an opportunity to apply social influence theory to study its impact on consumer purchase intentions. This study provides a detailed discussion of social influence theory to understand how heterogeneous social interactions shape social interactions on SNSs, which in turn shape consumer purchase intentions

Kelman (1958) explained that social influence develops at various levels (compliance, internalization and identity) in society, each creating a unique outcome. Social influence develops based on mutual agreement to adopt an attitude and behavior amongst the group, where an individual either conforms to the new behavior to win approval from significant others, or finds a match between his personal value system, norms, attitudes and behaviors with the group's norms, values and attitudes (Wang and Sun, 2016). Likewise, identity-based influence determines the self-defined relationship and acceptance of group behavior by individuals. Such individuals are subsequently recognized by other members in the same group (Cheung et al., 2011). Within online Web 2.0 based media, social influence is a product of individual network-based online social interactions which are determined by attitudes towards social behaviour and value systems. Changes in the behaviours and intentions of individuals are the explicit outcome of the acceptance of one of three levels of social influence.

Initially (Dholakia et al., 2004) studied social influence theory and measured social influence to determine the participative behaviour of individuals in network-based online virtual communities. Dholakia et al. (2004) measured “we intentions” and the intentional social action of participants as the outcome of their social influence model which contains three components. These components are consumer value perceptions, social influence predictors and decision-making variables. Intentional social actions determine changes to the behaviour of participants in the group as we-intentions on social media (Zhou, 2011; Cheung et al., 2011) The antecedents of their model include a five factor framework, and the gratification factors framework which includes purposive values (informational value), self-discovery values, the maintenance of interpersonal connectivity as well as social enhancement and entertainment values which gratify the use of online medium for social interaction (Shen et al., 2011). The informational value in the context of social media is considered a major antecedent to the main predictors of social influence, such as group norms (internalisation) and social identity (Tsai and Bagozzi, 2014).

Dholakia et al. (2004) mentioned that the outcome of such social influence phenomenon could vary when studied in large, heterogenic and geographically wide social networks. Within the social psychological disciplines several researchers have contributed in this regard. (Ngai et al., 2015) studied changes to individual attitudes, beliefs and intentions on social media using the perspective of social influence theory. Cheung et al. (2011) studied social influence theory to measure changes to the behavior (we-intentions) of students and their use of Web 2.0 based SNSs such as Facebook. Likewise, Zhou (2011) investigated how the group norm (internalization) factors of social influence theory change the intentions and motivations of online users of Web 2.0 user generated media. (Kang and Schuett, 2013) examined social influence on SNSs communities and drew out specific implications for travel planning. Hwang (2014) studied the role of social influence in social media in terms of e-learning and personal goal achievement. However, the epistemological stance of this study results in a modification to Zhou’s (2017) work in relation to the development of consumer purchase intentions as an outcome of online social interactions within SNSs brand communities in a marketing and communication context. The value perceptions of consumers are a psychological trigger of consumer engagement with online social media groups in order to learn new ideas and obtain new information to improve everyday living.

Dellarocas et al. (2007) suggests individuals accept this influence, either by becoming active members of online groups and sharing opinions, ideas and thoughts in group based online interactions, or by becoming passive members who receive information and knowledge and accept a level of social influence. Social consumer influence implies the real time development of a unique mind-set amongst online social media members (Tsai and Bagozzi, 2014). These modifications were carried out to enhance the vitality and credibility of the social influence model in order to better understand purchase intentions in the financial services industry. Such modifications are new and are carried out to make the model relevant to the specific context of consumer purchase intentions. This enhances the novelty of the research. To develop upon previous research, the framework in this study will investigate the phenomenon of social influence in online social media networking sites such as Facebook. The model is used to analyse the unique context of the retail financial services sector. Indeed, the research model in this study facilitates the dynamic functioning of an integrated marketing communication process to promote financial services online. Such cumulative social influence, supported by the subjective norms of social identity, group association and the value perceptions of consumers could develop the potential of eWOM. This in turn could enhance consumer trust in digital informational content with implications for the purchase intentions of consumers.

1.5. Background and Significance

The internet has enabled the creation of computer-mediated marketing and communications strategies and tools. This movement has triggered rational changes in the canvas of integrated marketing communications (Siikanen et al., 2018). The most significant change in the business models of companies, and in the marketing landscape is the dynamic nature of the internet (Christodoulides, 2009). Social media, which is one of the digital platforms enabled by the internet provides countless opportunities to create brand awareness and increase the number of potential customers by developing brand loyalty in the financial services industry (Filip et al., 2017). User-generated media not only enables marketers to communicate personalised promotional messages to online users, but it also enhances their ability to reach out and provide real time care to potential customers using multiple social media platforms. The front runners of

online medium based applications and tools are social media and SNSs that have revolutionised marketing dynamics, and which have captured the attention of marketing experts that seek to promote their finance brands through online groups or communities (KPMG, 2012). For example, by using SNSs as digital media, financial services companies are able to encourage online socialisation and interact with customers who are willing to converse and articulate queries, complaints and informational requests about financial services such as credit, finance, mortgages, loans, leases and insurance. Marketing and customer support representatives respond to queries and complaints in a timely fashion once they have been posted in the online communities of the financial services brand. Furthermore, customers can be contacted over a secured channel if the informational request involves sensitive information (KPMG, 2012).

Shih et al. (2010) argued that social media holds particularly high value for the banking industry, since it can facilitate the creation of loyal relationships with consumers since social media can create relevant knowledge and content. Further, they suggest that informational content creation and communication depends on a robust mechanism and the banking company's ability to create interactive content that can capture the attention of consumers, and engage online members with imaginative content. In this sense, users become the co-developers of UGC (Bonson and Flores, 2011). As an outcome of Web 2.0 based UGC media, banking companies can create maximum brand awareness. They can improve their image and obtain feedback from customers whilst resolving queries and developing new products and services. Such feedback also enables banking companies to improve their management efforts based on increasing transparency and the development of a customer-focussed attitude (Shih et al., 2014)

The scale of the consumption of social media in the form of SNSs is increasing. For example, people spend more than one third of their time on social media (Cheung and Lee, 2010). Social media has many dynamic uses in addition to socialisation. It has a role in influencing information acquisition. It can change the behaviour of consumers and grow sales whilst creating a subsequent impact on post purchase behaviour such as satisfaction levels (Sohn, 2014). Tang et al. (2012) argue that social media is egalitarian in nature, as the integration of social media and a social communication system creates a level of interactivity between social influencers and their audiences. Behavioural tailoring in social media has become a major focus in order to target the

behaviour of customers in the context of social commerce. This is because understanding the nature of consumer social influence and harnessing social ties brings substantial benefits to businesses.

Consumer social influence on social media is the outcome of social and behavioural interactions and informational exchanges (Kang and Schuett, 2013). These exchanges develop a mutual behavioural tendency to accept the values, norms and behaviours of other individuals or groups of individuals. (Kim et al., 2017). Social influence on social media has a psychological effect which can colour the attitudinal stimuli of online users. This triggers either short or longer-term changes to behaviours as a result of social interactions and learning in social media settings (Wang and Sun, 2016). Such interactions on online user-generated social sites enable users to create identities and seek rich information about products and services by consuming, sharing and discussing such content in social groups and peer circles. This enhances the potential of eWOM (Kozinets, 2010).

Online social interactions and social exchanges depend on multiple levels of social influence which shape the socio-psychological mind set of consumers (Hutter et al., 2013). There are clear implications for consumer decision-making. Empirical research in such social-cognitive disciplines has identified the role of social media in developing customer purchase intentions. However, social media within the context of social influence has not yet been fully understood (Zhou, 2011). Dholakia et al. (2009) argued that although discussions about social media have provided a variety of perspectives in research, there is still a lack of theory relating to the core issue of social media as a means of escalating the sale of products and services by influencing decision making. (Kang and Schuett, 2013) argue that social media helps marketers to understand the behaviour of online consumers and to appreciate the importance of the implementation of key marketing concepts such as service quality, pricing and positioning in discussion of consumer Social Influence Theory. They explain that consumer social influence theory provides a subjective framework based on online social interactions. It measures social influence at multiple levels in online groups in SNSs. According to (Chiu et al., 2006) social influence theory provides a fundamental strategic framework for marketers to target the online behaviour of customers as it analyses individual and group variables to provide deep insight into

the participation levels of individuals in online communities and in group discussions. Empirical research conducted on the role of social media in fostering individual and group interactions has found that online members experience social learning and behavioural and attitudinal changes as they become increasingly persuaded (Hutter et al., 2013; Hollebeek et al., 2014; Kozinets et al., 2010; Kang and Schuett, 2013; Zhou, 2017; Wang, 2014). Zhou (2017) asserts that, as well as predicting the relationship between such mediators and personal attributes in social media marketing research, an important factor that influences the outcome of research is the choice of network size. For example, measuring social influence based on heterogenic social interactions on a geographically wide scale on social networks such as SNSs could lead to different results (Kang and Schuett, 2013). This provides a starting point for marketers to use such a model to understand the impact of social influence on consumer purchase intentions in the context of online social networks. The current research is an empirical effort to address a research gap in relation to the functional use of a consumer social-influence model in heterogenic social interactions based on large social networks in the retail financial services industry. Since the social influence model represents a new behavioural development in addition to a revision to existing behaviours and intentions, the current study will investigate changes to the development of consumer purchase intentions in online social media settings.

Consumer social influence has implications for the development of purchase behaviours on social media (Youn and Jin, 2017). The idea reaches back to the origins of social influence theory developed by (Kelman, 1958) who found that changes to behaviour and psychological orientations are the outcome of individual social interactions amongst social actors and others in society. These are often attributed to the mutual adoption of a common attitude. In the context of social media, the implications of such social influence framework can enhance desires to make rational purchase decisions through individual or group based social interactions and engagement with the online promotional content of financial services companies. Social influence occurs at different levels and integrates into the value system of online users. It creates a lasting impact on the attitudes and actions of consumers (Friedkin, 1998). The implementation of such social influence strengthens the perceived fit between online users, SNSs groups and individual needs. Such users engage with promotional content in relation to services in online brand social groups themed around financial services. The adoption of such beliefs, and agreement amongst

individuals to adopt new values, norms and attitudes is the result of multiple levels of social influence. (Kelman, 1958) explains that individual social influences occur on three levels which are compliance, internalization and identification. These factors impact on individual behaviours through social influence. Compliance refers to a modification or change in the behaviour of online users in order to comply with the values and behaviours of significant others to achieve satisfaction and gratification, and to meet expectations or gain rewards. Similarly, identification refers to the idea of accepting the influence of a group or a community whereby an individual reaches a state of satisfaction by developing relationships on a self-defining basis (Zhou, 2011). Finally, internalization explains the overlapping of group or community values with the personal value matrix. This occurs due to congruence in the psychological processes between individuals and other members of the groups. These three factors of social influence drive online users' induced responses and values. They involve qualitative variations in interactions and communication across social media. Such interactions have a subsequent impact on the creation of social influence. As a by-product of social media, the users of new information tools such as SNSs based on Web 2.0 technologies achieve a greater level of internalization of their modified behaviours by altering and sharing informative content.

Many academic researchers argue that social influence is a vital construct that can help managers to understand consumer behaviour. The rational outcomes of social influence can be integrated into a marketing communication strategy (Xu et al., 2017; Bagozzi and Dholakia, 2002). A number of previous researches have used the social influence framework in relation to subjective changes in consumer behaviours (Bagozzi and Dholakia, 2002; Postmes et al., 2001; Wellman et al., 2001). However, the model developed in the current study is a modification of the empirical work of Zhou (2017) who used the foundations of the social influence framework developed by (Kelman,1958). The social influence framework has proven to be an appropriate tool for understanding the online behaviours of consumers in terms of their value perceptions, gratification levels, group behaviour and social identity. The model creates value to investigate changes in the behaviour of online users. It fits well in situations where the cumulative impact of social influence variables initiate behavioural change as a result of communication and interaction with the information and knowledge embedded in digital content on SNSs (Kang and Schuett, 2013). Further, such a behavioural modification can enhance loyalty and engagement

with brands by increasing levels of trust in brand promotional information (Algesheimer et al., 2005). In today's computer mediated marketing environment, the role of social interaction-based consumer social influence is inclusive and explicit.

Previous studies (Cheung et al., 2011; Zhou, 2011; Shen et. al 2011; Okazaki, 2009; Kang and Schuett, 2013; Hwang, 2014) evidence that the implementation of social influence theory (Kelman, 1958) not only explains how social media modifies the behaviour of online users resulting in changes to attitude and intentions, but also provides clues in terms of how to increase the growth of SNSs, social groups and communities. This phenomenon also adds value to the scope of the current study, making it more relevant to the integrated marketing communication process by providing insight into consumer purchase behaviour matrix (Trusov et al., 2009). The current study explains the impact of consumer social influence on the purchase intentions of online consumers on social media. It focuses keenly on brand group and community based heterogenic SNS interactions, and so the unique implications of the social influence phenomenon relate to changing the behaviours of online users of SNSs. The findings enhance the significance of the social influence phenomenon as a whole to better understand online behaviour and complex interactions on SNSs. The work also sheds light on how these elements act together to enable the user to develop rational purchase decisions. Secondly, the conceptual model of this study could be used to implement online marketing strategies in the financial services.

Chapter 2: Critical Review of Literature

2.1 Introduction

The previous chapter explained the research objectives, problem statement, research question and rationale of the study to explain the significance and value of the current research in the literature. This chapter presents a literature review on social media and its role in developing consumer purchase intentions. Furthermore the chapter also explains how social media shapes purchase intentions in multiple ways in light of social influence theory.

2.2. Conceptual Clarification

Previous researchers have defined social media as a vital tool for online marketing communications (Holsapple et al., 2018; Ozuem et al., 2016). The term social media is defined as the collection of internet-based applications purposely built for the exchange and creation of digital content within the technological foundations of Web 2.0 (Lu, 2018). Web 2.0 technologies are designed with the intention of helping companies engage in two-way communications with customers, such as listening to customers and responding appropriately (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010; Helal and Ozuem, 2017).

Furthermore, (Safko et al., 2009, p.6) defined social media as the:

“Activities, practices and behaviour among communities of people who gather online to share information, knowledge, and opinions using conversational media. Conversational media are Web-based applications that make it possible to create and easily transmit content in the form of words, pictures, videos, and audios.”

Constantinides and Fountain (2008) defined social media as a synonym for Web 2.0, and suggest both terms can be used interchangeably. Kang (2016) suggests social media refers to “UGC

websites” that promote digital content produced by users in the form of podcasts and blogs. (Ansarin and Ozuem, 2014) define social media as social software that enables online users to undertake social networking, including photo sharing, blogging and instant messaging. Social media facilitates instant communication, providing an easy interface for the sharing of digital information to empower online users to achieve quick access by removing the barriers and inherent time constraints associated with traditional media. Social media is a hub, and can be simply described as the starting point for acquiring intelligence on consumer buying behaviour as part of a wider social media marketing strategy (Stokinger and Ozuem, 2014). There has been a variety of explanations and definitions propounded by various scholars, but a formal, standardised and accepted definition of social media remains unestablished in the academic world. The matter of how these various scholars have contributed to social media marketing knowledge and have explained the phenomenon and its implications for social media marketing has been investigated by various key authors in the field of digital marketing (Helal and Ozuem, 2017; Hlebec et al., 2015; Carr et al., 2016).

Developments in technology have enabled individuals to interact online and exchange communication through computer mediated social media. Web 2.0 technologies offer online users the opportunity to communicate and instantly exchange information through a multitude of social media formats such as social bookmarking and blogs (Holsapple et al., 2018). Online social media has facilitated joint learning which has enabled millions of users to communicate within their social circles and to access and share promotional and marketing messages (Muniz and Schau, 2007). Compared to traditional media and integrated marketing communications, new computer mediated online social media have allowed consumers to communicate, not just with each other but with companies as well (Dolan and Goodman, 2017). (Li and Bernhoff, 2008) suggest that social media, from a business perspective differs from the traditional communications paradigm which sees marketers exert full control over promotional content. This high degree of contrast brings explicit benefits to businesses in multiple ways. First, it allows the marketers to quickly communicate promotional content to a wide audience. Second, it facilitates the success of integrated marketing communications strategies through cost reduction based on inexpensive and direct engagement with clients on the basis of two way

communication. This occurs with greater efficiency and a sharper focus than with any other integrated marketing communications tool (VanMeter et al., 2015; Felix et al., 2017).

Online social communications and the speedy exchange of information between members of online groups strengthens participation by connecting entire populations. This significantly impacts on their behaviour and mind set when it comes to making a purchase decision (Sinha et al., 2012). Online social media enables the creation, alteration and modification of UGC that is publicly available to online consumers and end users (Jiang et al., 2010, Herget and Mader, 2009; Litvin et al., 2008). Technological developments and communication platforms based on Web 2.0 technologies have enabled the publication of UGC on social media, and have also dramatically improved the aesthetics of websites (Brengharth and Mujic, 2016). Depending on the nature of usage and influence, Web 2.0 can be a unique technological solution to enhance the use of online applications developed based on Web 2.0 technologies. For example, it can enhance social networking and facilitate collaborative learning (Zhou, 2017). It can also support the speedy exchange of information to support two-way communications. This not only enables online users to receive UGC messages, but also enables them to respond to and interact with the sender at the same time (Hearn et al., 2009). This further enables online consumers to potentially engage in information sharing which facilitates further information exchange between companies and consumers, and this drives consumer purchase intentions (Sinha et al., 2012; Zhu et al., 2016).

Social media marketing has been defined as a type of online, inbound consumer-centric marketing strategy that uses social media networking sites as tools to facilitate online interactions and the consumption of UGC in the form of blogs, micro-blogs, product ratings, product reviews, group discussions and social book-marking. It essentially creates a two-way communication process between marketers and online consumers (Dang et al., 2014; Bojārs et al., 2008). Social media marketing has been widely used in the context of integrated marketing communications through social networking. This type of marketing is discrete from its long-standing existence in the field of sociology (Qi et al., 2018). The term 'social network' is a subset of online communities, platforms, or group pages where users interact and share ideas (Jansen et al., 2009). It is important to note that the terms 'social media' and 'SNSs' cannot be

used interchangeably as the former is a broader term compared with the latter, which is a component part of the idea of SNS.

Chan and Guillet (2011) defined Social Media Marketing (SMM) as

“A set of Internet-based applications that enable interaction, communication, collaboration of UGC and hence, sharing of information such as ideas, thoughts, content, and relationships”

They suggest that social media marketing is a platform for the promotion and communication of products and services on SNSs through UGC using Web 2.0. Social media provides a fundamental platform to establish a two-way conversation between companies and customers (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). UGC is the material generated by online members on social media websites, comprising of information in the form of blogs, product reviews, videos, micro blogs and informational content based on experiences of products. Examples include Facebook and YouTube. (Cox et al., 2008) stated that online users interact with online social media in three ways as follows: i) consuming social media, ii) participating in social media and iii) producing social media. Consuming social media involves simply using social media to access information and to view interactive content. These users do not participate in conversations on social media. Participation concerns user-to-user and user-to-content interactions in which users share personal experiences in relation to content use. They also share and evaluate content on the basis of its value proposition to the public (Jia et al., 2018). Finally, producing UGC entails the creation, modification and publication of content generated by a user on social media. Examples include pictures, videos or podcasts. Such UGC social media sites have captured the imaginations of almost every kind of customer, and they play a significant role in modifying perceptions of, and awareness about the products and services offered (Füller, 2006).

Malthouse et al. (2013) state that since the social medium is all about users sharing UGC for information and knowledge-sharing purposes, the creation of such content cannot limit the extent to which organisations can control promotional and advertisement messages that are made accessible to the general public. Such UGC and information exchange activities cannot be isolated and are limited to certain groups of people on social media, as promotional content is

viewed in multiple contexts on such platforms (Lee, 2018). Thus, whenever a company designs a promotional campaign to target certain users with specific needs, this phenomenon necessarily signifies that the campaign will reach users on social media who are not specifically targeted (Arrigo, 2014). In practice, it is almost impossible for organisations to target audiences of marketing promotional campaigns based on specific needs and requirements (Hajli, 2015). In almost every case, whenever a company launches a promotional campaign directed at certain groups of specific users on social media, such promotions must include the very high probability of users sharing advertising information with others, irrespective of whether they share the same specific needs and/or requirements. This phenomenon has had an impact on viral marketing as part of social media marketing strategies. Under such explicit conditions, a considerable audience can be reached with promotional advertisements, encouraging information sharing among social media members (Miller and Lammas, 2010).

Social media explicitly emphasises user-generated communication between consumers and between consumers and companies. The importance of web-based technologies, such as Web 2.0 are based on the principle of UGC, and facilitate the instant creation and sharing of content among communities and groups (Harrysson et al., 2012). The transition of marketing strategies from a company-centric matrix has influenced the target audiences of marketing strategies through the mechanism of online value creation (Lee, 2018). The phenomenon of two-way communications between users, and between users and marketers as a function of UGC has increased the scope of marketing online due to the extensive influence and wide targeting of audiences within a short time span (Hajli, 2015). The creation of such digital content on social media, and the consumption of UGC at the same time has created the phenomenon of “prosumers”, a term used to describe the simultaneous creation and consumption of digital content by social media users (Laestadius and Wahl, 2017). (Fuchs, 2010) explains that “prosumers” are consistent creators and consumers of content on social media.

Broadly explained, users participate in value creation by carrying out innovative activities on social media. The idea of creating innovative online content by adding value stems from online engagement with such content and the active participation in value addition to the online content of promotional campaigns. Such users show interest in developing co-creation promotions

through online value addition (Weinberg and Pehlivan, 2011). Such a value addition process can include value creation to influence the content of a promotional campaign, and this occurs when consumers share their personal experiences and remain loyal to certain brands by helping other online users engage to generate new ideas or share information about specific problems (Scott, 2012). Furthermore, the content modification undertaken by users on behalf of organisations helps organisations to reach increasing numbers of potential customers online. These organisations harness contributions made by online users and incorporate value additions into their promotional campaigns to influence online behaviour (Qualman, 2009). Technological developments in social media can modify and challenge traditional consumer behaviour.

Marketers use this phenomenon as a cushion for their online marketing strategies by purposely engaging online users in promotional content in marketing, and by empowering them to share information and knowledge with fellow users in order to influence an optimal population of online users exposed to promotional campaigns (Hajili, 2015). However, the limitations of social media marketing are well documented in the literature. Predominantly, there are two major perspectives that clearly outline the limitations of social media. The first factor defines the limitations of social media as platforms that support information exchanges and knowledge-sharing that completely neglect the characteristics of self-expression amongst users. The second factor indicates the limitations of social media in relation to information exchange, knowledge-sharing and online interactions with content. Such information is exchanged in a marketing environment that is explicitly concerned with consumption-related activities (Iankova et al., 2018).

Online social interactions offer many benefits to users due to significant changes in consumer behaviour enabled by social media marketing strategies. Social media strategies are very valuable in the current business environment (Qualman, 2009). The interactive motives of online users on social media are categorised into two major groups based on the nature of the interaction. The first explains that online social interactions are based on rational motivation, for example knowledge-sharing and/or advocacy. Similarly, the second view suggests that online interactions have an emotional motivational basis: for example, developing social networking by interacting with more social media members and expressing personal views, thereby gaining

confidence and identity (Li et al., 2017). Further the integration of online users' interactions combined with complex internet tools and technologies creates eWOM (Balaji et al., 2016). However, this phenomenon is limited in the sense that online users face difficulty in the face of information 'overload' when it comes to choosing which promotional campaign they would like to participate in.

2.3. Development of Social Media

Current academic research has focused keenly on consumer responses to social media marketing, although significant research into this topic is still pending, and there is little written on the optimisation of social media which can significantly explain how firms attain greater numbers of customers using SNSs as trade platforms (Chong et al., 2018). Hoffman and Novak (1997) first used the concept 'digital medium' as a platform for online marketing to sell goods and services. They used the term "hyper-mediated computer environments" to explain the behavioural targeting of consumers by firms and suggested that trends are shifting towards digital-based marketing when it comes to products and services (Hoffman et al., 2003). They affirmed that the traditional communication paradigm, fundamentally based on the traditional promotional mix in relation to integrated marketing communications strategies must be replaced with a new communications paradigm which explicitly relies on computer-mediated environments and platforms. Such a format could include all forms of social media and potential tools for creating an IMC strategy in online B2C marketing settings (Ozuem et al., 2016). For example, in a computer-mediated environment and a technological setup, web pages contain key information, banners and other forms of advertising through which marketers reach out to customers by analysing clicks. This information is then stored and passed on to marketers to design appropriate online marketing strategies (Chang and Wang, 2008). Hoffman et al. (2013) indicate that the development of such computer-mediated environments is an evolution of electronic commerce that highlights the impact of social media and social networking in online marketing. These developments have created a new dimension of online social media marketing called 'social commerce'. Social commerce is a notable platform for providing online shopping with information across social media and SNSs by engaging an optimal number of customers with social network ties, and enabling them to develop their social identity by sharing, recommending,

and discovering online financial services information (Vemuri, 2010; Sciglipaglia and Ely, 2006). Such an adaptive process creates the building capabilities of financial services firms in computer mediated environments to generate value for customers with the help of digital technologies (Walsh et al., 2004).

2.3.1. Social Media and Social Capital

Chan and Ngai (2011) suggest that the nature of the motivations and interactions of users in relation to online promotional messages depends on their perceptions of online advertising and their participation in online SNSs. This also includes the self-disclosure of behaviours and attitudes in online brand communities amongst participants in a social group (El-Ouiridi et al., 2015; Chen and Li, 2017). Self-disclosure and intentional involvement in social media, as well as engagement with communications can motivate consumers to buy (Lin and Utz, 2017). This kind of consumer self-disclosure on social media takes place through various forms of online media, whereby users create and share content in accordance with their engagement and level of interactivity (Chen and Li, 2017). This creates social capital based on personal or mutual interactions on social media, and it has implications for consumer-to-consumer information sharing, discussions and personal experiences of promotions. The term ‘social capital’ is the aggregate of the resources developed through individual social interactions, social information sharing and valuable social value exchange between individuals in society (Aldrich and Meyer, 2015). The term ‘social capital’ has been sourced out from Social Capital Theory which explains the aggregated sum of actual and potential social interactions connected to a reliable social network of social exchanges, mutual acquaintances and institutionalised social relationships (Bourdieu, 1983). The structure of such social exchange and valuable social interactions amongst individuals holds potential value for user engagement with interactive digital content on Web 2.0 based social media. It clarifies the development of the aggregated resource in the form of social capital which holds unique value in terms of enhancing individual interactivity and engagement on social media platforms such as SNSs.

Ghahtarani et al. (2020) stated that Social Capital Theory explicitly focuses on three important factors that lead to the development of social capital on social media. These factors are social

interactions, trust and perceived benefit. Firstly, social interactions are introduced as the sum of activities and interactions of online users as a result of binary communication. Individual social interactions and engagement with online content, and the valuable social exchanges that occur with other individuals on SNSs channels are key to the flow of such information and resources (Kim et al., 2018). The higher the volume of engagement and interactions between individuals on social media, the higher the intensity and sequence of the flow of information. Secondly, the level of trust explains the willingness, cooperation, generosity and ability of individuals to share information with other individuals on social media. Interpersonal trust in information sharing media leads to a shared vision and network credibility. It increases the credibility and transparency of the information that leads to purchase decision-making. Finally, perceived benefit explains the value that individuals perceive while sharing valuable information on social media; for example, personal satisfaction and brand loyalty. Razak et al. (2016) argued that individual brand loyalty is one of the intrinsic benefits that individuals seek by sharing personal experiences, product reviews and opinions about specific products and services on social media.

Such social capital helps marketers to communicate with online clients using a B2C approach (Iankova et al., 2018). Chang and Zhu (2011) found that personal, individual interactions on any social medium defines the personality, influences and so-called self- presentation of subjects. These consumers also share their thoughts, feelings and ideas and seek to develop relationships with others to create social capital and an identity in social circles on social media.

2.3.2. Web 2.0

To comprehensively understand the concept of social media, it is first essential to understand the background to the development of Web 2.0, since these Web 2.0 two concepts are often used in the same context (Berthon et al., 2012). The term Web 2.0, which is used to describe a subset of the internet, comprises of websites which operate on the principle of UGC. These empower users to actively participate in altering and editing web content (Kang, 2016). The development of Web 2.0 is explained as the composition of the images, graphics and texts on the internet operating on the basis of UGC (Ho and Chang, 2010). Jansen et al. (2009) argue that Web 2.0 has revolutionised the world of the internet with the active participation of users in creating digital content online, rather than remaining passive recipients of such content, as was the case in the era of Web 1.0. They further argue that the development of Web 2.0 has had a considerable impact on the world of the internet. For example, the internet has undergone certain modifications which have led to the development of new internet-based applications and new categorisations of internet-based applications. The most notable change that the internet has undergone with the development of Web 2.0 is the facilitation of UGC which has led to the development of social media and other interactive communicational platforms as contributions to the electronic economy (Cox et al., 2008). Further, Web 2.0 categorises internet-based applications into UGC applications which run on Web 2.0 platforms such as social media, digital content communities, online forums, blogs and micro blogs.

Web 2.0 differs from first-generation Web 1.0 in many ways. In the era of Web 1.0, online users were passive recipients of web content and were unable to alter or create content due to limited functionality (Constantinides and Fountain, 2008). The term “Web 2.0” brought about social networking developments in 2004 when online network developers integrated Web 2.0 platforms with UGC (Newman et al., 2016; Cox et al., 2008). UGC has made the World Wide Web into a platform harnessed by end-users to alter and modify online content and share it on the internet. This contrasts with first-generation Web 1.0, where users had limited access as passive viewers of content on a website (Rodriguez-Ardura et al., 2010). Further, Web 2.0 is an open foundation platform, supporting the sustainable development of innovative technological applications

through the generic features of royalty-free technologies (De Valck et al., 2009). This has brought about the establishment of unlimited web-based links to web pages, and has created unrestricted, instant access to webpages. McQuail (2005) argues that for many prominent search engines which run on Web 2.0, the smallest unit is a webpage. In the case of social media (also termed Web 2.0) the smallest entity is considered content or ‘bits’ altered or created by active online social media users. These are commonly known as a “UGC units”. Web 2.0 and social media therefore differ in certain ways, as each webpage has several content entries created or altered by users or companies, and these are greater than the smallest entity on a social medium (Newman et al., 2016).

The development of Web 2.0 is also linked with the evolution of the internet, serving as a medium to facilitate sharing and the altering of UGC online. Jansen et al. (2009) suggests that the internet and subsequent development of Web 2.0 has been primarily concerned with enabling online access for the general public to more actively engage with others to share perspectives. This heralds a new era of development towards online democracy (Rainie and Wellman, 2012). As a step further from the development of the internet, Web 2.0 was seen as friendlier, and easier to use, particularly with reference to UGC. Web 2.0 has empowered users, and has revolutionised marketing. It has allowed companies to interact and share information with each other (Newman et al., 2018). This second-generation web service has also led to the transformation of the web through multiple channels, for example through one-to-many, and many-to-many. It has been embraced wholeheartedly by online users all over the world.

Focussing on the basics of the multidimensional functionality of Web 2.0, marketers consider it a prime medium for the development of internet-based applications created using digital content. Web 2.0 has become a mass medium, since it encompasses a much wider role than traditional Web 1.0 because it has modernised the structure of online communications, giving a clearer focus to the transfer of promotional messages. It has polarised social and digital content-based interactions (Murugesan, 2007). This modernisation of mass media in the form of Web 2.0 has out-performed traditional marketing and communications methods thanks to instant two-way communication. Users can reach a far wider audience with quicker customer response times (Fuchs et al., 2010). In addition, it has enabled a power shift on the internet from sender to

receiver, with more emphasis on information acquisition. This has led to a transition of the landscape of the marketing mix and a reorientation of marketing strategies from push to pull (Faci et al., 2017). This seismic change in the paradigm of marketing communications has meant that interaction processes online can enhance the credibility and vitality of web promotions. These are based on the exchange of information initiated by organisations in quicker and more convenient ways (Newman et al., 2018). Behavioural changes in consumers are an explicit functionality of the interactive features of Web 2.0-based applications which are more user-friendly on account of consumer interactions-based applications such as social media. In using social media, consumers interact as individuals, or in a community to seek information and gain wide acceptance from peers (Brenghar and Mujkic, 2016; Walther et al., 2012).

New advancements in internet technologies have transformed Web 2.0 into more of a “semantic web” which is now referred to as web 3.0; an intelligent agent which has enabled firms to communicate and interact with customers by automatically manipulating (reading, writing and executing) customer data on multiple platforms such as SNSs (Fuchs et al., 2010). Integrated Web 3.0 technology has given rise to large scale applications by enabling firms to react quickly to change. Their ability to construct and infer relationships between data within different networks based on social media applications has been enhanced. For example, Web 3.0 semantically links data and creates connections between web applications on the basis of user information search, taste, feelings and content consumption. This goes beyond simply collecting information from webpages. It provides semantically linked data access to the internet which helps users search for information quickly (Hendler, 2009). For example, if a certain user searches for information on financial services, Web 3.0 not only provides personalised information, but also provides information about the best financial services institutions offering specific financial services. The integrated technology of Web 3.0 facilitates reading, understanding, interrelating and manipulating data through data mining, data warehousing and, most importantly through customer relationship management. As a further action to support customer relationship management, web 3.0 semantics provide essential information about customer needs, preferences and choices and information searches. This enhances the firm’s ability to tailor their products to the needs of customers by communicating and promoting very personalised information (Garrigos et al., 2011).

Both Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 have facilitated social interactions through the technologically innovative development of online social communities, connecting online users all over the globe. This forms a sophisticated platform of human interaction in a virtual online environment (Al-ghamdi and Al-ghamdi, 2015). Predominantly, Web 2.0 has proven to be a key medium for the development of online communications, linking users around the world and supporting interaction-based applications development such as SNSs. Such platforms have made it easier for online users to develop a greater understanding about making a rational choice when it comes to products and services.

An explicit feature of Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 is that both offer a friendly interface which has enabled online users to participate in, and control online interactions, social information sharing, and the promotion of products and services on SNSs. (Dang et al., 2014). With such a user-friendly interface, the development of online brand communities where consumers become members that share a common interest and similar characteristics of membership has been made possible. Such online communities facilitate content consumption amongst online users who achieve satisfaction by reading and sharing valuable content which enables them to shape their buying behaviour. This, in turn has had a subsequent impact on their online purchase decisions (Berthon et al., 2012). Berthon et al. (2008) note that with the development of SNSs running explicitly on UGC, the internalisation of content information shared on social media can be used for both commercial and non-commercial purposes. Within this scenario, consumers use digital content which originated, not from a commercial source, but from a reference group on a social networking site. Such content takes the form of product reviews, experiences and testimonials and recommendations that are made available on Web 2.0 (Michopoulou and Moisa, 2018). The advancement and development of technology such as the development of online search engines together with sophisticated mobile communication devices, online social networks and websites for peer-to-peer communication and online group discussions has helped marketers to extend their understanding of online communities. There is now a greater understanding of social trends and user preferences regarding preferences for brand products and services advertised online (Habibi et al., 2014).

Developments on social media networking sites gained popularity when the practices of different forms of UGC became available on websites created by end-users. However, in order to qualify as social networking websites there were some basic features and regulations imposed on such sites to compel them to meet various criteria and requirements. For example, the website must contain online users' profiles, personal content and information in order to enable users to develop a unique identity to be able to participate in community discussions and establish a connection with others. This enables users to post online in online communities and gain information through reading online blogs and expert testimonials on social media (Alarcón, et al., 2018). According to the (OECD, 2007), for a user graphic interface to be considered suitable for online availability and sharing it should fulfil certain requirements. First of all, such UGC needs to be available online as published content available to a group of online users to access and alter. Secondly, it needs to demonstrate innovation in containing vital information for online users. These characteristics support the development of social media, which is explained by many researchers collectively as internet-based applications developed on Web 2.0 which help online users to exchange UGC (Dang et al., 2014, Faci et al., 2017).

Kietzmann et al. (2011) explained that such interactions reveal the human behavioural matrix on online social platforms. For example, online social networking and group discussions on a Web 2.0-based application increase human exposure to the desired content and information related to consumption. This initiates a transition process from ordinary user to potential online consumer (Fu et al., 2018). Such a behavioural matrix supported by online interactions and active membership has dominated Web 2.0 with extensive online traffic enlarging the overall function of UGC applications (Stokinger and Ozuem, 2014). Online user traffic on Web 2.0-based applications is based on participation by online users and the heterogeneous nature of interactions. For example, on SNSs, online users create digital content and interact at the same time to receive information and knowledge. They actively participate in group discussions or become members of a group associated with specific content related to information concerning a product or services. Examples include product reviews, personal experiences, or post-purchase behaviours (Kim and Kim, 2018). Azemi and Ozuem (2014) explain that today, the exchange of

UGC on Web 2.0 has enabled the development of many potential social networking websites that provide extensive benefits to online users, such as Facebook, Wikipedia, or LinkedIn.

2.3.3. User-Generated Content (UGC)

The transition in the marketing paradigm from a traditional company-centric approach to a more consumer-centric one has significantly impacted on the multiple dimensions of contemporary marketing techniques (Alalwan, 2018). This paradigm shift from traditional marketing to more consumer-centric inbound marketing has held the attention of consumers through online marketing. Such marketing is encountered on Web 2.0-based marketing applications developed using UGC. These enable marketers to achieve two-way communications with consumers to a greater degree than is possible using traditional marketing tools (Huang et al., 2017; Chang et al., 2014). Although UGC facilitates online user interactions and consumer participation in UGC, there remains a gap in the literature regarding the use of such online interactions for online media marketing (Chang et al., 2014). The term ‘UGC’ is often interchangeably used with ‘social media’ due to its self-sustaining nature and the fundamental influence of UGC on multiple functions of social media sites. Examples include communication and online entertainment. These influence the value perceptions of online users (Choi and Lee, 2017). However, the major impact of UGC on social media remains unclear to academics and online marketing researchers because UGC is a little-understood phenomenon that enables social interactions amongst social media members.

The term ‘UGC’ is defined as available content on a social media platform containing multiple forms of informative and interactive material that is publicly available to online social media members. Such content is created and circulated by online users on online social media sites (Luca, 2015 ; Jia et al., 2018). UGC is made of bits of core data and ‘meta data’ (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). UGC in the context of Web 2.0-based applications consists of users creating altered or modified content as core data. The relative information providing the descriptive explanation of UGC on the social medium is termed “metadata”, and this contains content information in relation to its status on online media. Data, such as the date of creation, the rate of

access to the content, and the number of shares on the online social medium are relevant here (Wyrwoll, 2014).

Daugherty et al. (2008) suggested that UGC on social media sites is the sum of interactions and engagement of online users. It is based on a variety of informational and entertainment-enriched content generated in the form of product reviews, comments in group discussions, interactive videos and podcasts. They further explain that the creation of such content on social media is an affective investment in online economic progress as users engage in creating such content online. An important question that arises here is how UGC is created and used, and how it aids and enhances the engagement of online members on social media. The answer to this question lies in the elusive mechanism of the active participation of online users who add content for informational purposes, for entertainment or even, in more subjective cases, to share personal experiences when interacting in an online brand community (Kim and Johnson, 2016; Crowston and Fagnot, 2018).

Yoo and Gretzel (2011) state that Web 2.0 applications are built on UGC principles, as is the case with user-generated media. This suggests that online users who consume UGC online and who develop purchase intentions to come up with a buying decision encompass the user-generated medium (Fu et al., 2018). On a practical note, the phenomenon of using consumer-generated media instead of user-generated media illustrates the fact that an online social medium is explicitly used for online users to consume content related to making a purchase decision as an end result (Choi and lee, 2017). This means that user-generated media includes websites and online social media specifically built to provide digital content relative to product reviews, testimonials and post-purchase reviews (Park and Lee, 2009). However, some researchers suggest that this mechanism cannot be interchangeably used as an alternative term for UGC. Social media using UGC plays a more significant role compared to the limited function of consumer-generated media (Wang and Li, 2016; See-To and Ho, 2014; Choi and lee, 2017). The functionality of a user-generated social medium is not limited to online social trade, but has multiple dimensions whose purpose may be to create a brand community or to share content and knowledge in order to increase understanding about brand reputation by engaging consumers in

online social group discussions and follow-up opinion-sharing on social media (Goh et al., 2013).

In terms of social media, UGC is generated by members of a social online community in the form of product reviews, group discussions, informative and entertaining videos or evaluations of products and services. UGC can therefore be summarised as content emanating from online users which is publicly available on social media sites or created out of professional routines and practices. Such content is purposely created to be shared and consumed on social media (OECD, 2007). For example, in accessing UGC, online members go to user-generated sites on the internet (like YouTube, Facebook and Twitter) where UGC has been made available to online users in much the same way as paid media content.

User interactions and social exchanges on social media are two perspectives that have dual significance. The first perspective is significantly associated with active participation in the creation and co-creation of content online. Users keep themselves engaged in on-going discussions in closed groups, or contribute to a public page on social media. Such active participation cultivates social profiles, commitment to an online community and the creation of valuable content for wider consumption by fellow online users (Karahasanović et al., 2009). The second perspective is significantly supported by the first. Wide encouragement from the social media audience is required to consume content created by a particular online user. This defines the social identity of the user in the social group as a pro participant of a social media platform (Flanagin et al., 2013). Further, it develops the status of the online user and his/her relative positioning on social media in terms of the level of trust earned from fellow users, and the importance attributed to the information issued by the user (Gebauer et al., 2013). An online social medium develops from the prerequisites of UGC, nourishing the diverse relationship of online users within the social community (Flanagin et al., 2013). This facility of user empowerment to post and develop personal content in online media enhances the accomplishment of positive outcomes such as informational enhancement, entertainment value and continuous social interactions compared with traditional types of media developed based on Web 1.0 technologies. In the latter case, online users had no choice but to be passive recipients of promotional adverts and messages sent by companies. As with traditional media, most online

advertising campaigns involve the passive consumption of content created by companies to promote products and services in computer-mediated environments (Yankova and Ozuem, 2014). However, the development of content on web-based technologies and networking sites offers consumers the choice to avoid unwanted exposure to content and provides the flexibility to choose the most coveted content to view, according to specific needs and choices.

Fig. 1. Mechanism of Social Media Interaction

Web 2.0 technologies have enabled online users to publish digital content online. This is particularly the case with web-based applications which run on UGC. Publishing UGC is about making content available for online users on social media. In the context of creation and the publication of online content on social media, the publisher has, at their disposal multiple forms of user-generated digital content to suit many online users. In particular, on social media sites, users have the option to make digital content available to online users on the basis of levels of

privacy (Li et al., 2017). More precisely, the privacy of UGC published online is categorised into five major forms of accessibility of content by online users which are: general accessibility, limited public, known-limited public, unknown-limited public and private (Wyrwoll, 2014). General accessibility is a form of UGC in which the content creator aims to maximise the accessibility of the digital content to as many online users as possible, or to an unlimited online audience so that more online users can access content and benefit from it. Similarly, in limited public online content publications, accessibility and exposure to digital content is greatly limited by content contributors, and is made available to specific online users who meet specific criteria or specific conditions that qualify them to view content. For example, the content contributor publishes content online and makes it available to an online audience upon registration and disclosure of personal details due to the sensitivity of the content. Perhaps the content contains information or materials which require users to identify their age to access content. Wyrwoll (2014) further stated that, in some situations, those who access such content may also be required to pay. Limited public content on online social media can be further categorised into three types: known, and unknown, and public limited access. In the case of known public limited access, the online content contributor limits access to digital content to an online social community which includes members who are well known to the content contributor. Examples include friends, family members and peers. Likewise, unknown public limited access is user-generated digital content made available to online users with accessibility restricted to unlimited online users in the social community of the content contributor. At the same time, these users need permission from other members outside the social community or group to access such content. Unknown public limited content published by the content contributor can interchangeably be used with private access granted to known and unknown online members within the specific group of the content creator. These individuals can have access to the data, and accessibility is restricted to online users outside the social community.

One important reason for the creation of UGC on social media which explains the motivation to create content and restrict access to it on the online medium is the gratification of online users on social media. User gratification refers to the extent to which they perceive that their needs are satisfied while accessing UGC online. In this way, marketers can understand the motivations of online members to access media (Leiner et al., 2018). Furthermore, this also explains what form

of gratification users expect, which subsequently influences their specific needs and the consumption patterns of online consumers. Yoo et al. (2009) explain that user gratification has greatly increased online traffic, especially on social media websites such as YouTube, Facebook and Daily Motion. The most important of these online user gratifications includes informational value, entertainment value or participation in, or association with a group on social media of significant value to the online users' life-styles. The key perspective of user gratification upon accessing UGC is the type of gratification value that the online consumers deliberately seek upon consuming UGC. Akehurst (2009) concluded that, in the majority of situations, the online consumption of UGC on social media yields two prominent forms of gratification to users: informational accomplishment and entertainment value. They further stated that, in most cases, online users gratify their specific consumption needs by consuming UGC in the form of informative and entertaining videos as well as product review blogs, or active group discussions on social, political or business issues on sites such as Facebook and YouTube. This, on the other hand, yields valuable information about online consumer behaviour on the basis of gratification search patterns like Googling information, uploading or watching a video on YouTube, commenting in an active group discussion on Facebook or following a trend on twitter. Online marketers use such information to target online audience behaviour by developing a relevant strategy to reach out to the maximum number of customers online (Gao and Feng, 2016).

2.3.4. Development of SNSs

The very first step in the development of social networking websites was taken almost 25 years ago by Tom Truscott and Jim Ellis in 1979 (Kaplan and Haenli, 2011). They created a worldwide online discussion system for online users called "Usenet" where users could post public messages. Later on, Bruce and Susan Abelson created an online social networking site and named it "Opendiary". They then created an electronic diary writer's community by bringing these two services together on one platform. (Weber et al., 2016) note that the features of SNSs closely resemble previous online network-based communities in terms of the nature of communication and social interaction they support. These environments are interactive and rich in graphics. Many online communication scholars argue that the implementation of digital networks in social networking websites provides a public interface between firms, and online

users, and this defining characteristic of SNSs enhances the focus of marketers to understand online behaviour in the context of promotional content (Berkelaar, 2014; Steinfeld et al., 2008). Further implementation of digital networks into integrated marketing communications led to the development of social media for companies that produced digital products and services. They were able to produce network directories to reach a very wide audience with quick customer response times.

Kaplan and Haenlin (2010) define SNSs as

“A group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of UGC”

Kaplan and Haenlein's (2009) study suggests that the development of social media websites and online networking sites are related to the philosophy of self-generated, authentic communications and information exchanges between online users in relation to a specific subject of interest. Key here are the opinions, thoughts and personal experiences of online participants. Therefore, the purpose of social media and online networking sites was to share and offer more appropriate and well-informed choices to online users (Windels et al., 2018). The role of social media was consistent with traditional integrated marketing communications. Social media companies communicate advertising and promotional messages to online customers, and these are sponsored either by companies or individuals. Another promotional objective of social media is that customers share online content, thus promoting corporate messages to many potential online customers through word-of-mouth (Park et al., 2017; Chun and Lee, 2016). Can and Kaya (2016) state that traditional marketing strategies with conventional promotional activities have led to customer dissatisfaction, and one dissatisfied customer tells ten more potential customers, substantially damaging the reputation and brand value of the company.

2.3.5. SNSs and Brand Communities

The user-generated interfaces typical of SNS cultivate brand loyalty amongst online social media members by enhancing content consumption to create personalised experiences, informational

enhancement and value perceptions (Kujur and Singh, 2017). The SNSs have created a holistic social platform across which members of the SNSs can connect and share their 'likings' and motivations about favourite brands with their peers, family, friends and other acquaintances (Cheung and Lee, 2012). This paradigm shift has made it imperative for marketers to better understand the reasons for digital behaviour amongst net-savvy consumers on SNSs. They are particularly keen to understand why individuals interact and engage with brand related content in order to cultivate a relationship (Kelly et al., 2010). Social media platforms such as SNSs have offered unprecedented opportunities for marketers to communicate their brand image to online members in SNS brand groups and communities to better understand the needs of their consumer by building relationships at a personal level (Lu 2018). Such B2C relationships personify the fact that consumers consider such relationships as a guide while interacting with brands and evaluating informational and promotional content. Such a relational view contrasts with the transactional view of online brand-consumer interactions (Li et al., 2006). (Ngai et al., 2015) state that social media can be referred to using several other keywords such as social computing, virtual communities, online communities, Web 2.0 and social networking sites.

Muniz and O'Guinn (2001) argue that an online brand community is defined as:

“A specialized, non-geographically bound community, based upon social relationships among admirers of a brand in cyberspace”.

Members of SNSs can easily and freely join such brand communities and engage with brand content through user-generated communication processes on SNSs, such as leaving positive comments on informational videos, content and pictures of brands. They can also co-create informative content such as reviews, and they can respond to brand promotions (Dessart et al., 2015). The brand communities provide intrinsic motivation for consumer engagement with informational content, and they facilitate the exchange of information about the history and culture of the community. Muniz and O'Guinn (2001) argue that a brand community's recognizable characteristics include an intrinsic connection between the members of the community showing respect and support for each other and enjoying social collaboration. The community shares social values and rituals such as sharing information, expertise and

experiences with other members to strengthen the culture and history of community. Finally, members share a sense of responsibility and duty to the community.

The social, participative features of SNS brand communities are to develop an environment which helps marketers not just to advertise the brand, but to communicate it and engage online members in it with greater intimacy and interactivity. Such SNS brand communities further allow marketers to monitor consumers activities within brand communities, and actively respond to group conversations and consumer inquiries to help them find solutions to their needs. Dessart et al. (2015) stated that there is congruence between consumer participation and engagement with brand content, and that central to this is the idea of value co-creation, informational exchange and interactive activity within SNS brand communities. Additionally, social media not only allows online members to communicate with brand representatives and existing customers, but also allows the users to communicate their opinions to companies about improvements to the community products and services or corporate policies.

Muntinga et al. (2011) offer an explanation of consumer typologies in the context of online brand interactions. They categorise brand related activities and engagement in SNSs brand communities into three levels: The minimal or passive level, the moderate level and the ultimate level. The minimal level explains that the digital behaviour of the brand community member is limited to the consumption of interactive and informational content such as watching informational videos, reading blogs and reviews or downloading brand widgets. A moderate level of engagement means users participate in group discussions and polls and respond to content provided by the brand community. Examples include posting opinions in discussions and liking and sharing interactive brand content in brand communities. Finally, the 'ultimate' level explains the higher levels of activity and engagement with brand related activities in SNSs brand communities, such as using personal expertise to create informational and interactive content about brand products and services such as blogs and reviews which provide help and support to other members. This might involve answering questions in group discussions using pictures and videos and statistical illustrations.

Many researchers acknowledge the fact that companies have adopted B2C communication channels, and are using resources to harness SNSs to create and develop brand groups and communities in order to strengthen their relationship with potential customers (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2010; Libai et al., 2010; Xie and Lee, 2015; Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010; Laroche et al., 2012; Zheng et al., 2015; Tsai and Men, 2013; Lu, 2018). The brand communities developed on SNSs offer multiple advantages to companies, such as fostering a consumer base, and maximising brand engagement in communities to increase purchase intentions (Goh et al., 2013; (Xie and Lee, 2015). Furthermore, marketers are intrigued by the benefits of SNS brand communities such as the ability to examine consumer value perceptions about the brands products and services for the purpose of anticipated future developments, promoting social collaboration and information sharing to attract new customers and retain existing ones, and co-creating value and content for brand groups or community development (Zaglia, 2013; Schau et al., 2009). Such managerial interventions in SNSs brand group development influences consumer trust and develops electronic word of mouth (Porter and Donthu, 2008).

Tsai and Men (2013) argue that, with the development of SNS brand communities and groups corporate social media marketing and consumer relationship development tactics such as brand related informational and promotional communication create the psychological bond that motivates consumers to interact, and strengthen relationships with companies via user-generated media. Such user generated media has transformed the way consumers obtain information, share their experiences and expertise and develop purchase intentions (Zheng et al., 2015). The social and communal nature of the SNS brand communities has proven to be an effective platform for online marketers to implement their online marketing strategies.

2.4. Theoretical Context of Social Media

Previously, social media has been studied as a predictor of the socio-behavioural outcomes of social media stakeholders such as social media users and customers (Kang and Schuett, 2013). These theories explain that social media impacts both on behaviour at individual and social levels. Social media has been studied using personal behaviour theories, social behaviour theories and mass communication theories (Ngai et al., 2015). In the context of personal behaviour theories, social media has mainly been understood at a human behavioural, individual level. There have been more than fifteen such personal behavioral theories used to study the role of social media on individual behaviours. On a large scale, the impact of social media on individual behaviours from the perspective of various personal behaviour theories has been mainly studied in the context of the Big Five personality trait theory (Labrecque et al., 2010; Liu and Campbell, 2017; Kircaburun et al., 2018; Zhong et al., 2011). It has also been studied using the Theory of Reasoned Action (Hsu and Lin, 2008; Karnowski et al., 2017; Kim et al., 2015; Sheldon, 2016), the TPB (Casaló et al., 2010; Chang and Zhu, 2011; Cheung and To, 2016; Kim et al., 2016; Nazar, 2013), and Social Cognitive Theory (Lin and Chang, 2018; Chiu et al., 2006; Lin et al., 2009; Stefanone et al., 2018; Yen, 2016). As with personal behaviour theories, studies on social media in the context of social behavior theories explain individual social media behaviours at a social level. For example, individual social behaviours on social media have been studied from the perspective of Social Influence Theory (Zhou, 2017; Cheung et al., 2011; Hwang, 2014; Kang and Schuett, 2013; Zhou, 2011; Okazaki, 2009), Social Capital Theory (Chai and Kim, 2010; Carmichael et al., 2015; Lee, 2017; Hau and Kim, 2011; Yang et al., 2016), Social Interaction Theory (Fischer and Reuber, 2011), Social Identity Theory (Casaló et al., 2010; Cheung and Lee, 2010; Mudrick et al., 2016; Chan, 2014;) and Social Exchange Theory (Blanchard, 2008; Harrigan et al., 2018; Li et al., 2016). Additionally, the influence of social media on the behaviour of individuals in society has been studied using Mass communication theories including Media Richness theory (Koo et al., 2011; Mandal, 2012; Lodhia and Stone, 2017; Shiue et al., 2010) Parasocial Interaction Theory (Colliander and Dahlén, 2011; Yuksel and Labrecque, 2016; Labrecque, 2014) and Uses and Gratification Theory (Cheung et al., 2011; Dholakia et al., 2004; Whiting and Williams, 2013; Quinn, 2016; Kim et al., 2016).

Of all the socio-behavioural theories, Social Influence Theory (Kelman, 1958) has been considered as the most holistic framework for measuring and transforming the social behaviours of individuals interacting and communicating on user-generated media (Zhou, 2017; Dholakia et al., 2009; Kang and Schuett, 2013; Zhou, 2011; Hwang, 2014). Social influence theory provides a theoretical explanation of the multiple levels of change in individuals' social behaviours as a result of heterogeneous social interactions on social media (Zhou, 2017). In taking orientation from this theory, the current study explains the role of social media in developing consumer purchase intentions from the perspective of Social Influence Theory.

Theories, Frameworks and Models	Empirical Evidence
Big Five Personality Traits	Zhong et al. (2011), Correa et al. (2010), Liu and Campbell (2017), Gosling et al. (2011), Quintelier and Theocharis (2012)
Social Cognitive Theory	Yoon and Tourassi (2014), Lin and Chang (2018), Stefanone et al. (2018), Lin et al. (2009)
Theory of Reasoned Action	Gunawan and Hurang (2015), Bigne et al. (2016), Andrews and Bianchi (2013), McCormick and Livett (2012), Kim et al. (2015), Karnowski et al. (2018), Branley and Covey (2018)
TPB	Pelling and White (2009), Kim et al. (2016), Baker and White (2010), Ahlabash et al. (2015), Sparks et al. (2013), Pujadas-Hostench et al. (2019), Chaudhary and Bisai (2018)
Goal Directed Behavior Model	Chiu et al. (2018)
Social Influence Theory	Youn and Jin (2017) , Zhou (2017), Varnali and Gorgulu (2015) Hwang (2014), Kang and Schuett (2013), Cheung et al. (2011), Cheung and Lee (2010), Li (2011)
Social Capital Theory	Carmichael et al. (2015), Lee (2017), Krishen et al. (2018), King and Lee (2016), Zhao (2016)
Attribution Theory	Porter and Donthu (2008)
Technology Acceptance Model	Hwang et al. (2016), Hajli et al. (2014), Sharma et al. (2015), Liu and Guo (2016), Cheng et al. (2012), Bakar and Bidin (2014),

	Ayeh et al. (2013)
Social Exchange Theory	Shiau and Luo (2012), Surma (2016), Cheung et al. (2015), Proudfoot et al. (2018)
Social Interaction Theory	Fischer and Reuber (2011)
Social Identity Theory	Prentice et al. (2019), Wang (2017), Okazaki (2009), Chan (2014), Bathish et al. (2017), Arenas-Gaitan et al. (2013)
Uses and Gratification Theory	Aluri et al. (2015), Alnawas and Aburub (2016), Huang et al. (2017), Ho and See-To (2018), Phua et al. (2017)
Media Richness Theory	Koo et al. (2011), Mandal (2012), Lodhia and Stone (2017), Shiue et al. (2010)
Para-social Interaction Theory	Chung and Cho (2017), Yuksel and Labrecque, (2016), Labrecque, (2014), Colliander and Dahlén (2011)
Theory of Social Network Analysis	Predendergast et al. (2015), Phang et al. (2013), Park et al. (2014)
Social Ties	Ostertag and Ortiz (2017)
Hofstede's theory of culture difference	Xu-Prior et al. (2014), Lo et al. (2017), Zhu et al. (2017), Benson and Filippaios (2019)
Dialogic Theory	Waters et al. (2011), Lee (2014)
Social Learning Theory	(Deaton, 2015) (Othman et al., 2012)
Signalling Theory	Ahn (2011), Donath (2007)
Warrenting Theory	(Ahn, 2011), Lin and Spence (2018), DeAndrea et al. (2018)
Self-Determination Theory	(Ferguson et al., 2015), Casale and Fioravanti (2015); Wakefield and Wakefield, 2016), Paulin et al. (2014).
	Ramadan et al. (2018), Azizah et al. (2017)

Theory of Social Information Processing	
Social Media Engagement Theory	Gangi and Wasko (2016)
Social Penetration Theory	(Rains, et al., 2014; Tang and Wang, 2012; Panos, 2014)
Social Comparison theory	(Vogel et al., 2014; Lee, 2014; Islam et al., 2018; Li, 2019)
Elaboration Likelihood Model	(Teng et al., 2014; Shi et al., 2018; Schieb and Preuss, 2018)
Social Support Theory	Yusuf (2018), Farzin and Fattahi (2018)
Consumer socialisation Theory	Wang et al. (2012)
Information Adoption Model	(Erkan and Evans 2016; Gunawan and Hurang 2015)
Source Credibility Theory	Dejafarova and Rushworth (2017)
Attitude and Hierarchy Response Model	Duffet (2015)
Stimulus-organism-response model	Huang (2012), Kim and Lennon (2013)
Social Presence Theory	(Hajli et al., 2017)
Flow Theory	Kang et al. (2018), Chen et al. (2018)
Value Theory	Hsiao (2011)
Social Impact Theory	Perez-vega et al. (2016), Seltzer et al. (2013), Bedard and Tolmie (2018)
Motivation Theory	Chen et al. (2018)

Hyper-symbolic Interactionism Theory	Nolcheska (2017)
Hierarchy of effects (HOE) Model	Lakasmana (2018), Hutter et al. (2013)
Halo Effect Theory	Dejafarova and Rushworth (2017)
the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)	Liu and Guo (2016), Martin and Herrero (2011)
VAM Model	Chung and Koo (2015), Chen et al. (2018)

2.4.1. Social Influence Theory

Research into changes to individual behaviours and feelings as a result of social interactions has been salient in social psychological disciplines for decades. Individual social relationships are developed within the domain of social anthropology in such a way that they adjust beliefs and attitudes in accordance with other social actors that they can relate to. This creates social influence, which is the outcome of the subsequent actions of individual social interactions with others in society to influence individual feelings, opinions, thoughts attitudes and behaviour (Luo et al., 2016). Changes in the behaviours and attitudes of individuals can occur through independent interactions with other members in society who are considered desirable, and who have similar feelings or possess social expertise (Rashotte, 2007). Such adjustments to individual behaviours with respect to others are developed on the basis of the psychological principle of balance (Lee et al., 2011). Furthermore, the adoption of behaviour is also developed when an individual's behaviour is influenced by a large social group in such a way that the individual is likely to perform similar behaviour to the group members in society (Kwon et al., (2014). The social influence phenomenon is distinct from the individual behavioural dimensions of conformity and power in such a way that individuals in society are independent of the change in their perspective attitudes and beliefs. They are not forced or required to seek a balance with groups of individuals in society by complying with their beliefs, attitudes and behaviours in order to fit in (Sridhar and Srinivasan, 2012).

Subjective changes in individual behavioural outcomes are influenced by the outside social world. This is explained within the realm of the social network paradigm (Dholakia et al., 2004). The social network paradigm introduces the social influence phenomenon as a process of psychologically focussing individual social relationships with other social members. The prospective development of social connections is formed in social networks (Pattinson, 1981). Such behavioural development and attitude changes have been the explicit focus of investigation using the social network paradigm in the social anthropological disciplines for some time. The social network paradigm, instead of explaining the existence of a social structure, investigates and analyses the development of individual social relationships in the form of social networks.

Bagozzi and Dholakia (2002) define the social network as the interlink between the nodes and connections in which individuals in society are nodes, and individual social interactions and communications in society formulate the social network.

Norman and Wolfe (1974) note that the social network paradigm explains the phenomenon of social influence by underlining the three most important principles concerned with individual social interactions within the social network. Changes in individual behaviours and beliefs are a consequence of social influence, and the social network explains social influence over individuals, groups of individuals or societies. Finally, individual social interactions within communal social networks are dynamic and not static in nature (Watts, 2004). Empirical research into social networks explains that social influence leads to group-based interactions and changes in individual group behaviours in organizational management (Kjos et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2006; Bagozzi and Dholakia, 2002; Dholakia et al., 2004). Achrol (1997) suggests that the social network paradigm explains changes in individual social behaviours within organizational groups and teams in social networks. They further conclude that individual behaviours and attitudes are based on interactions and the diffusion of group members' behavioural characteristics in organisational management scenarios. Despite such changes in individual attitudes, beliefs and behaviours, the social influence phenomenon is explained in the light of various renowned socio behavioural theories developed by scientists who have contributed significantly towards the development of a social influence framework. In early contributions to the development of the social influence phenomenon French and Raven (1959) stated that social influence is the outcome of social power. They further stated that changes in individual behaviours, attitudes and beliefs are not only the result of individual and group based social interactions in the society, but the values and norms also play an important role in developing and modifying these behaviours. They further explained that individual social actions and change in behaviours and attitudes are the controlled outcome of social agents or groups, rather than being independent in nature. Their concept of social influence was more of an outcome of behavioural formalization in which individual social influence is the result of individual behaviours, attitudes and beliefs that comply with other social actors or group (Hinkin and Schriesheim, 1989). For example, changes in the attitudes and behaviours of a subordinate at work through attitudinal and behavioural conformity may occur and present in behaviours

towards management. The researchers further explained that the development of individual social influence is sourced from multiple dimensions of social powers such as reward power, coercive power, legitimate power, expert power and referent power (Raven, 2008). On the basis of their research they categorised changes in individual behaviours and attitudes as the compliance-based behavioural conformity of individuals who adopt behavioural change and adjust themselves into situations regardless of the fact that such behavioural modification represents true change (Wood, 2000). However, this perspective of social influence has not been well accepted in the academic community as individual social interactions are dynamic in nature and possess a variety of traits depending upon the persuasiveness of other social actors in society (Li et al., 2018). Examples include social interactions between customers as regards a product or service, or employees within a group approaching a task or goal influenced by the views of attitude conformity-based social influence.

Another significant development towards understanding social influence was achieved by Bibb Latané (1981). He developed social impact theory and explained social influence as change that occurs in individual behavioural and psychological systems as a result of the behavioural influence of others in society (Harton and Bullock, 2007). Individual social interaction-based social influence is a complex set of behavioural and psychological change that impacts on individual cognition, emotions, behaviours and psychological mind sets. Latane (1981) further explained that social influence can develop on the basis of social informational interactions between individuals and social groups. This idea contains three important factors: first, the group of individuals acts as a source. Second, they are subject to mutual exchange, and third the consistency and immediacy of interactions is key. (Latané and Liu, 1996). The theory further holds that the higher the involvement and balance between these three factors and individuals, the higher the strength of the resulting social influence.

In a broader sense, social influence is understood as a pervasive force in individual social interactions with others. In most social interactions, the individual modifies and adopts to changes in the opinions, behaviours and attitudes of those they interact with (Luo et al., 2016). Social influence develops when individuals engage in communicational interactions and are persuaded by convincing arguments, information sharing or knowledge exchange. This explains the variety in social influence, as it could either be the case that a similar behavior is adopted

upon understanding the potential benefits associated with it, or it could be adopted to confirm with the social group (Bikhchandani et al., 1992; Wood, 2000)

The diffusion of beliefs in social systems is the result of individual dynamic and iterative social interactions and influences that occur in society (Latané et al., 1995). The customized beliefs and cultural values developed in social networks influences the likelihood of individuals being influenced by others in a social structure, confirming the centrality of the element of immediacy (Teven, 2007). Social influence from this perspective develops based on mutual and strong norms as well as the values, beliefs and attitudes that are adopted by individuals in society. These are consolidated into widely accepted cultural norms that are developed through dynamic social interactions. Weak beliefs get clustered into minority sub cultures (McDonald and Crandall, 2015). Empirical research supports this phenomenon and categorizes social influences as complex socio-psychological phenomena in society. The influence of individuals over other beliefs, attitudes and values are key. These principles of social impact theory were developed by (Latane, 1996). He stated that social impact theory explains social influence as a self-organizing, complex socio-psychological system which impacts on the beliefs of individuals in society. These create a uniformity of beliefs, values and attitudes. Latane (1996) explained that social influence develops on a larger scale in the form of a social network within society. He explained that, in a network, society influences individual conformity and the nature of the adoption of new behavioural attitudes and values. These reflect the specific referent groups than individuals or groups of individuals in society value (Leenders, 2002). Such network-based influence can be categorized into two distinctive forms: interpersonal influence and social influence. Interpersonal social influence is a smaller unit of social influence and is the outcome of individual dynamic social interactions and exchanges with individuals based on their socialization and identity in a specific social structure (Xiao and Lo, 2016). On the other hand, social influence is the process by which group members understand, weigh up and integrate the opinions and beliefs of others in a referent group within the limits of social network structures (Kim et al., 2017). Further, such social structures determine the fit between the individuals' values, and the beliefs of individuals within a social network.

Within the social influence research online, social network-based influence is explicitly important in social psychological disciplines (Kim et al., 2017). Network based social influence has explicit importance in discussions of social influence on a much larger and broader scale. The development of electronic media such as the internet and Web 2.0 has played a significant role in enhancing the wider implications of network based social influence (Newman et al., 2016). Online network based social influence has led to a transition from traditional to electronic interfaces, where individuals interact with social members from different geographic territories, exchanging values and creating uniformity in attitudes and beliefs on a geographically large scale (Leenders, 2002). Friedkin (1998) defined a significant mechanism that explains how social influence is developed on an electronic network based on social interactions. In their social network influence theory, they defined a two-stage mechanism of averaging influential individual opinions on social networks. Social influence develops in such a way that actors in the social network share their personal opinions or exhibit specific behaviours during interactions (Friedkin et al., 2016). According to his view, network based social interactions relating to shared norms or beliefs are developed on the basis of mutual agreement amongst actors as a central value of all attitudes and beliefs (Proskurnikov et al., 2017). Finally, actors respond to central beliefs by modifying their personal beliefs and attitudes to ensure uniformity and agreement according to central beliefs and norms which are created as a result of social interactions and exchange. Friedkin's (1998) theory takes more of a mathematical approach to explaining social influence on social networks using a mathematical model. This contrasts with attempting to understand the phenomenon from a behavioural point of view using social sciences (Friedkin and Johnsen, 2011). However, their mechanism provides the basis for online social influence, and it has been used in later research to investigate the development of social influence on Web 2.0 based virtual social network communities and SNSs.

2.4.2 Development of Social Influence Theory

Despite extensive research, the phenomenon of social influence remains one of the most puzzling in social anthropology. Existing research contributes to an understanding of social influence in multiple areas, such as creating uniformity of behaviours and attitudes by reducing differences through complying with the conformity based social influence (Asch, 1956). This does not

however significantly explain individuals' independent adoption of behaviours through mutual agreement, internalization and persuasiveness. Importantly, it does explain how online social interactions and information diffusion in terms of social influence developed on online social networks (Myers, 1982 ; Bond et al., 2012). There is not enough evidence to empirically model interpersonal social influence which has developed through the composite dynamics of individual social interactions. Richerson and Boyd (2005) explained the principle mechanism of social influence and stated that it has its roots in the cognitions and nervous systems of individuals in which they unconsciously imitate the behaviours, feelings and gestures of significant others in society. The fundamental basis of modelling social influence lies in the assumption that when individuals socially interact, they exert influence on each other and adopt a mutual behaviour upon reducing their attitudinal and behavioural differences (Lee et al., 2011). The principle assumption in social influence modelling explains that the growth of social influence relationships between social actors increases if individuals in society are connected socially through the influence of relationships compared to when they are exposed to multiple influences from different sources in a social network. There is a certain probability that such social influences could be ineffective, but when individuals are exposed to multiple social influences on the same social network, they cancel the effect of each other. The research supports the idea that individuals connected to a reference group on a social network might develop the propensity to make better decisions upon complying with group values, norms and pressure (Richerson and Boyd, 2005).

Earlier developments to model social influence emphasize the inclusion of factors in the development of social influence such as social learning and conformity with group norms to form uniformity in behaviour (Homans, 1950; Myers, 1982). In later research, the inter- group behavior of social actors was considered based on the resolution of behavioural and attitude disagreement where individuals in social networks persuaded and helped other social actors to adopt similar values. This creates uniformity in attitudes and behaviours (Groeber et al., 2009). Empirical research offered by earlier social scientists has yielded a model of social influence to describe social networks in society. Various researches (DeGroot, 1974; Harary, 1959; Lehrer, 1975) contributed towards modelling social influence in the context of a large social network. Such research introduced the concept of nodes and network links in social networks as key

components of the development of social influence. In this context, the nodes are social actors that are connected to each other in a network. They develop social influence through frequent interactions, mutual exchange, agreement and persuasiveness. They ultimately adopt shared behaviors and attitudes.

Deutsch and Gerard (1955) argued that individual social interaction leads to two types of social influence: informational social influence and normative social influence. Both informational and normative social influences lead to changes in the attitudes and intentions of individuals through behavioral conformity (Burnkrant and Cousineau, 1975). Informational social influence is defined as a process of change in attitudes through accepting information as evidence of reality obtained through social interaction. Informational social influence is indicative of conformity in attitude based on informational updating about factual and true aspects of reality (Kelley, 1967). On the other hand, normative social influence is a change in attitude in individuals as a result of compliance behavior for the purposes of reward, punishment or satisfaction. This is based on the influence of significant others. In terms of normative social influence, individuals conform to the beliefs of group members, and social interactions lead to behavioral conformity regardless of whether or not evidence about factual or true aspects of the environment are sought (Burnkrant and Cousineau, 1975). Both informational and normative social influences result in behavioral conformity which supports individual decision making. In this sense, individuals who accept informational social influence commit to decisions based on informational exchange and evidence of facts and reality. Decision making is based upon accepting normative social influence as explicitly dependent on conforming to the expectations of others to gain satisfaction or reward, or to avoid punishment mediated by the others (Cialdini and Goldstein, 2004).

Deutsch and Gerard (1955) provided a multi-faceted framework of social influence to examine individual behaviors. The crucial issue in terms of social influence research and framework development is to understand and measure the nature of change brought about in the form of particular social interactions at different levels (Cheung et al., 2011). Earlier developments on social influence support the observation that it incorporates changes in individual behaviour and attitudes, which impact on decision-making. However, this idea alone it is not sufficient to appreciate that there has been a measurable change in attitude. What is important is to understand what type of change has occurred (Bagozzi and Lee, 2002). Change could be a superficial or

verbal exchange that disappears within a short period of time, or it can be a long lasting change as a result of adopting new attitudes and beliefs which manifest into individual behaviors within multiple social situations (Bagozzi, 2007). To answer this question Kelman (1958) explained that there is a strong relationship between individual psychological motivational processes with cognitive links to form an induced behaviour in a way that embed particular attitude-structures within new attitudes. This determines the consequences and manifestations of new attitudes (Cheung et al., 2011). To understand the extent of changes in attitude and beliefs it is important to appreciate how the motivational and cognitive systems of individuals have been linked. In their framework for measuring the outcome of social influence, Kelman (1974) states that changes in individual attitudes and social actions are the result of social influence, and these may occur at different levels. Varied changes in attitude and intentions occur in accordance with differences in the psychological setups of individuals. They further explained that new attitudes are induced behaviours and are the resultant outcome of three levels of changes which are compliance, internalization and identity.

The components of Kelman's (1958) framework of compliance, internalization and identity explain that new attitude development conforms to influence at one of three levels of attitudinal change where compliance is the acceptance of influence rather than basis of independent choice. However, conforming to beliefs for the sake of achieving favourable rewards, reaction and approval from others represents conformity to the social effects of influence (Zhou, 2011). Secondly identification is explained as a self-defining interaction and relationship of an individual with other individuals or groups (Bagozzi and Lee, 2002). It may be based on reciprocity whereby the individual seeks to meet the expectations related to his/her own role. Unlike in the case of compliance, an individual believes and accepts changes in behaviour and attitudes and embraces the development of new attitudes as a result of identification and confirming a desired relationship with the individual or group (Kelman, 1961). Finally, internalization is the process whereby new attitudes are developed as a result of satisfaction with behaviours that individuals accept on the basis of cognitive consistency upon finding a match or congruence between their attitudes, beliefs and value systems with the values and beliefs of other individuals or groups (Kochanska, 1994). The value congruence further takes the form of induced behavior on the basis of affective appropriateness for the maximization of individual

personal values and beliefs. Zhou (2011) argued that normative social influence leads to compliance based social influence on the basis of satisfaction, reward or the avoidance of punishment. This is also influenced by levels of motivation in relation to positive self-defining relationships, taking into account the behaviors and opinions of referents that support the self-concept. Kelman's (1974) framework of social influence provides the fundamental basis for the development of a social influence model. Compared to traditional media, this framework has been significantly used to model social influence in online media settings. Some researchers have used a three-factor social influence framework to measure social influence in relation to changes in attitudes and actions in the context of online platform environments (Cheung et al., 2011; Okazaki, 2009; Shen et al., 2011; Zhou, 2011). Kelman's (1974) social influence framework has been used to measure the intentional social actions of individuals based on their online social interactions and the extent of informational exchange they engage with in the form of UGC.

Fig 2. Kelman's (1958) Social Influence Framework

2.4.3. Social Media from the Perspective of Social Influence Theory

Pervasive digital environments where digital networks are used for social activities such as online social interactions and informational exchange can potentially influence and connect like-minded people (Postmes et al., 1998; Zhou, 2017). Further, the growing realization of the use of such online social influence at different levels enables marketers to change opinions and influence knowledge and the decision-making behaviours of customers (Williams and Cothrell, 2000). Online social influence is an outcome of perceptions of the hedonic and utilitarian benefits of online social interactions and mutual agreement between individuals adopting unified behaviours and attitudes on Web 2.0 based networks (Cheung et al., 2011; Gutiérrez-Cillán et al., 2017). Such digital networks facilitate online social interactions in the form of formal or casual interpersonal and group-based interactions (Sutcliffe et al., 2018). The participation and interactions of actors in online digital networks creates an intentional social action as an outcome of distinctive levels of social influence compliance, identification and internalization (Zhou, 2011). Further, such social actions where individuals implicitly and explicitly interact with reference groups are a way to adopt mutually shared behaviours and engage in joint actions.

Previous studies have investigated (Kelman, 1958) social influence theory in the online medium. For example Tsai and Bagozzi (2014) studied the role of social influence in virtual community participation in digital environments. Cheung et al. (2011) investigated the role of social influence theory towards the development of we-intentions amongst students regarding the use of SNSs such as Facebook Hwang (2014) investigated how social influence impacts on personal goals achievement in Web 2.0 based social media. Kang and Schuett (2013) studied the role of social influence in SNS communities in travel planning and decision making and Zhou (2017) studied role of social influence in developing a continuous commitment to use SNSs.

Zhou (2017) states that individual heterogenic social interactions on social media platforms such as SNSs have a distinctive outcome in terms of one of three different types of social influences. These influences impact on changes of attitudes, beliefs and behaviors. Changes in individual attitudes that occur through accepting social influence are the product of individual attitudes towards adopting behaviours based on normative social beliefs (Compliance) and pressure from

social actors or groups of actors in the network (Scott et al., 2007). Subjective norms develop normative social influence as compliant behaviour leads to conformity amongst individuals in the social network (Bird et al., 2018; Darker et al., 2010). Changes in behavior as a result of social interaction on SNSs occur through an association with the group or community, rather than by rationally adopting an induced behavior and performing specific behaviors in the same way as significant others. Compliance in this regard is the outcome of rewards anticipation being associated with the group or community. For example subjective norms influence the perceived enjoyment of participation in SNS groups and communities to share travel experiences and information about travel planning (Kang and Schuett, 2013). In terms of SNS brand groups and communities, normative social interactions and engagement with brand related activities are influenced by rewards and benefits, such as economic incentives, coupons and discount promotions (Nov, 2007). However, subjective norm-based social influence neglects the descriptive norms which explain how individuals behave when influenced by significant others (Lee, 2011). The construct of subjective norms emphasizes the acceptance of social influence by narrowing down individual perceptions to focus on the adoption of behaviours in lieu of rewards and hedonic or utilitarian experiences rather than in accordance with how significant others ought to see them in online community. Such normative social interactions on SNSs lead to conformity, which is a product of individual levels of trust. This can further lead to planning and decision making (Luo et al., 2016; Kang and Schuett, 2013.). More specifically, compliance could possibly lead to the development of purchase related behaviours in individuals on social media through the development of eWOM as an intentional social action (Okazaki, 2009; Hennig-Thurau et al., 2015).

In addition, internalization is explained as the incorporation of online social group norms, values and beliefs which develop a rational and long-term change in individual beliefs (Zhang, 2010). Internalization is the outcome of informational and knowledge based social interactions on SNSs which induce enjoyable commitment in individuals' behavior (Zhou, 2017). This is defined as the rational adoption of the norms and values of a group in a social network to increase the commitment of individuals in the group on the basis of incorporating mutual beliefs and attitudes into subjective value systems, and intrinsic motivations or 'personal norms. Personal norms form part of the idea of group norms, and are fundamentally associated with

individuals actively seeking group norms and values upon joining the group (Tsai and Bagozzi, 2014). In this regard, individuals who use social media as a source of information to inform a buying decision are also likely to actively participate in brand communities to share their experiences of making a purchase. This caters to the exchange of social norms and values amongst members through social interactions and further plays a role when individual value systems overlap with group values and norms before joining the group (Bauer, 2008). The values of information sharing and receiving on SNSs tend to integrate with the individual's own value system norms matrix as intrinsically rewarding. Internalisation derives satisfaction through the adoption of behavioural content into personal values. Web 2.0 based user-generated media technology is seen as intrinsically rewarding. Such group norms have predictive power in determining desire, which formulates decision making behaviours as individuals in the group consider themselves as important members of the group (Zhou, 2017; Smith and Louis, 2009). For example, group norms within online brand communities on SNSs enable the members to internalise the values of social information and experience sharing (eWOM opinion giving, seeking and passing) whilst actively participating in group discussions and publishing informational content in the group in the form of comments, opinions, reviews and personal experiences. Such gestures increase their understanding about the utility of the products and services (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2015). Some internalise socially shared informational content about travel experiences within SNS communities and make rational travel decisions thereafter (Kang and Schuett, 2013). Furthermore, Group norms are associated with members accommodating the personal commitments of individuals as well as their limitations and preferences. This is done in order to foster group based social interactions which cumulatively form group based joint social actions (Cheung and Lee, 2010).

Behavioural developments and changes explain how individuals affiliate and respond to specific socially constructed groups in society (Brewer, 1979). This supports the view that, within socially rich digital environments, social identity subsequently influences mutual interaction and status in online social networks (Okazaki, 2009; Zaglia, 2013). Individual social identity in online networks has emotional and evaluative significance for social relationships (Bergami and Bagozzi, 2000). (Cheung et al., 2011) explain that individual self-awareness, as well as cognitive and affective identity has an explicit role in determining social influence and changes in social

behaviour. In their research, which models online social influence, they identify a three-factor social identity framework of affective, cognitive and evaluative identity (Ellemers et al., 1999, p. 372). They further state that social identity explains the extent to which individuals possess inclinations within certain groups in terms of their membership. They also argue that such inclinations form the basis of how individuals identify their affiliation within a specific group. Malhotra and Galletta (2005, p. 123) explain identity in online social networks as “behavior adopted through identification is performed only under conditions of salience of the individuals’ relationship to the influencing agent”. Underpinning this statement, individuals affiliated with the online group or community develop a sense of belonging or fit with the brand community or group on SNSs (Okazaki, 2009). After all, individuals find pertinent information about the brand’s products and services they are looking for within the brand group. Such a formation of identity with the brand group or community on SNSs is the result of deep-rooted affiliations with a “shared consciousness” within the community and its members (Zaglia, 2013). Furthermore, affiliation with the online group or community on social media shapes social cohesion which consequently enhances the perception of reward, positive relationship with the community and intrinsic happiness (Zheng et al., 2015).

In terms of cognitive identity, individuals self-categorise themselves into social brand groups on SNS on basis of their self-defined and cognitive choices (Christodoulides et al., 2012; Kim et al., 2014). This can also result in affective identity whereby individual emotional affiliation with the online social group is salient, or can lead to evaluative identity which refers to the group-based self-esteem of individuals linked to positive or negative feelings about their prospective group membership (Brodie et al., 2013). Within online brand groups and communities, the emotional affiliation between individuals and the brand group is referred to as kinship between members because it encourages affiliation and loyalty between the brand and its consumers (Tsai and Bagozzi, 2014). This identification process is a form of referent power that triggers the development of social influence since intrinsic associations make users reluctant to switch to an alternative. Such influences can impact on group-based attitudes and behaviour and formulates group-based social actions by strengthening bonds between individuals and SNS brand communities on social media (Lu, 2018).

2.4.4. Social Media Value perception and Social Influence

While conceptualising social media and user behaviour from the perspective of social influence theory in a consumer-centric marketing context, the importance of its antecedents and predictors cannot be neglected (Quan-Haase and Young, 2010; Phua et al., 2017). (Kwon et al., 2014, and Muntinga et al., 2011) state that heterogenic online social interactions on SNSs are embedded with perceptions of informational and entertainment value, and social connectivity value. These fulfil the media gratification needs of consumers. Such media gratifications not only lead to the fulfilment of utilitarian and hedonic needs on SNSs, but also have different impacts on brand community-related outcomes such as identification, consumer engagement, community membership and intentions (Quan-Haase and Young, 2010). Such gratifications also develop intrinsic motivations for the selection of social media platforms such as SNSs for social interaction, where the magnitude of such interactions transform individual behaviours and attitudes upon becoming a distinctive form of social influence. For example, the perception of value in the form of knowledge and information sharing through community based social interactions on SNSs leads to the development of social influence at an internalisation level (Zhou, 2011; Kang and Schuett, 2013). Similarly the entertainment and connectivity values lead to social interactions on the basis of reward-anticipation, happiness and affiliation within SNSs brand communities that may develop compliance and identification on the basis of utilitarian and hedonic value, reward anticipation, happiness and affiliation with in SNSs brand communities (Xie and Lee, 2015; Goh et al., 2013). Dholakia et al. (2004) note that, without including the antecedents of these predictors, (Kelman, 1958) the social influence framework is more of an exogenous construct. Their view tallies with the views of Kelman (1958), who stated that each predictor component of social influence has a unique set of antecedents that corresponds to qualitative variations in the psychological processes of individuals. These determine their prospective induced behaviour in social networks. Similarly, each set of antecedents corresponds with a distinctive set of consequent behavioural conditioning amongst individuals, as subsequent variations in induced behaviours (Kelman, 1974). The antecedents also serve as the reason to choose social media for social interactions (Flanagin and Metzger, 2006). While investigating social media from the perspective of social influence theory, the uses

and gratification framework developed by Katz et al. (1974) has been widely used. It is effective where the aim is to study the motivations to use online media (Okazaki, 2009; Phua et al., 2017; Cheung et al., 2011; Dholakia et al., 2004). Cheung et al. (2011) studied the role of the uses and gratification framework (the value perception matrix) as an antecedent to measure changes in the intentions of students using SNSs such as Facebook. (Phua et al., 2017) applied the framework to study participation and social interactions in SNSs brand communities and (Quan-Haase and Young, 2010) studied the role of UGT in solving problems, sociability and collaborative learning for knowledge improvement in SNS brand communities. Katz et al. (1974) explained that the theory of Uses and Gratification is based on three tenets 1) consumer behaviour is well guided by a perspective goal or purpose 2) consumers are considered as active media users and, finally, consumers hold significant knowledge as regards how media can gratify their needs. The five factors of the value perceptions of social networks are purposive value, self, discovery, maintaining interpersonal connectivity, social enhancement and entertainment value. The integrated value perception factors extracted from the uses and gratification paradigm of (Katz et al., 1974) have been employed in communications research in order to understand various motivations to use SNSs and interact in brand groups and communities (Quan-Haase and Young, 2010; Phua et al., 2017; Okazaki, 2009; Flanagin and Metzger, 2006). Further, the uses and gratification model supports the concepts of self-actualisation and self-fulfilment where media are sources of information (Dholakia et al., 2004).

Informational value, entertainment and social connectivity value are considered to be the prime variables of value perception that create the motivation to choose Web 2.0 base social media as a method of interaction (Muntinga et al., 2011; Taylor et al., 2012). Informational value explains the creation and consumption of informational and interactive promotional content on SNSs brand groups and communities in the form of comments, informational support opinions, blogs and testimonials shared on social media profiles. Zhou (2017) used informational support and emotional support as predictors of the social influence in SNSs to measure continuous commitment. From a marketing perspective, such informational value mitigates the perceived risk and uncertainty associated with brand products and services, and sellers by building trust with online users (Bai et al., 2015).

Furthermore, for (Okazaki, 2009) informational value measures eWOM on SNSs when studied as an antecedent to the relationship between individuals' ubiquitous social interactions and their intrinsic association with brand informational value. Although entertainment value and social connectivity provide significant reasons for interacting on SNSs, more or less both of these have been studied in the context of informational value, such as informational entertainment and social information sharing (connectivity).

Empirical developments on social influence theory on Web 2.0 based social media platforms have enhanced the marketing scope of social influence and provide a real time platform for marketers to understand and make use of the outcomes of individual social interactions in SNSs brand communities in online B2C environments (Lu, 2018). Such arguments provide a fundamental basis to empirically conceptualise social media from the perspective of social influence theory in the retail financial services industry. The conceptual model in this study will explain the applied form of online social influence in the retail financial services sector. The study will ultimately explain the multiple impacts of social influence that significantly change and modify consumer purchase intentions.

2.5. Social Media and Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM)

The rapid proliferation of the internet in the 1990s enabled consumers to use the online medium for the speedy exchange of their product post-purchase experiences using websites, bulletins, user-net news groups, chat and blogs (Okazaki, 2009). Internet-based Web 2.0 technologies developed unique applications which maximized the social interactions of online users through socialisation, communication and information-sharing with consumers. This enabled academic researchers to identify new research perspectives based on online users' multiple collaborations (Holsapple et al., 2018). As with social media, online users not only communicate, but interact with each other on social platforms by means of multiple forms of digital content such as pictures, texts, personal information and expertise relating to different brands' products and services. Such information and knowledge-sharing through mutual interactions amongst consumers on SNSs, and the process of joining or affiliating with specific brand groups on social media are the key contributors to eWOM (Jin and Phua, 2014, Lee and Youn, 2009).

eWOM comprises of both positive and negative comments, or statements made by consumers about products and services on digital platforms and communities in the form of discussions, reviews, opinions and comments (Cheung and Thadani, 2012). These digital platforms include review websites, discussion forums, bulletin boards and SNSs. Among these digital platforms, SNSs have paramount importance in the creation of eWOM as UGC. UGC principles enable consumers to not only share their experiences and opinions but also rapidly exchange valuable information and opinions about brands, products and services across the social network at individual and community levels (Raacke and Bonds-Raacke, 2008). This is a focal point for marketers, as significant efforts and resources are invested in setting up and promoting brand profile groups and communities on SNSs, encouraging eWOM through maximizing interactive experience such as interactions and the co-creation of content. Further strategies include consumer engagement with brand posts and social exchanges with other members (Paschen et al., 2017; Chu and Choi, 2011). This engagement subsequently develops online word-of-mouth communication about products and services advertised by companies on online social media, leading to consumer loyalty towards certain brands or services (Baek et al., 2017). Indeed, since the brand group and community-based interactions mostly refer to brand awareness through the promotion of products and services and relational experiences with brands, they naturally influence consumer purchase intentions (Wang et al., 2012).

According to (Alboqami et al., 2015) social media develops eWOM in multiple ways. For example, it can occur via online users posting comments or information about certain brands, products and services in a social group. Another example is when users unintentionally associated with certain brands display their brand association to the social network and comment and participate in comments, liking and sharing brand information without the intention of promoting the brand. Lastly, interactive promotional content and posts published by marketers and their social media teams to establish maximum credibility and the value of a brand in the consumers' society is another example eWOM. In essence, eWOM is a communications outcome which necessarily flows as information. It is facilitated by the consumption of digital content. It contains embedded information relative to product benefits, usage, and utility (Standing et al., 2016). Glazer (2011) studied the banking industry, stated that such eWOM resulting from online users' extensive participation in online communication and interaction with

online content subsequently leads to economic value creation for the company through the development of consumers' purchase intentions (Tang et al., 2015). Since interpersonal online social interactions are more complex and hold more significant value for the promotional activities of a business, more emphasis in academia as well as in business pedagogy has been given to grasping the opportunity to engage online consumers with online promotional content for products and services. This creates strong brand relationships with online users, thereby creating eWOM (Cheema and Kaikati, 2010).

Traditional media have fragmented while targeting specific segments of the markets, whereas electronic media, due to its flexibility with censorship, the reduced cost of promotion and its powerful distribution and global reach, has increased in popularity (Lu, 2018). Previously, eWOM research has investigated the role of consumer opinions and information-sharing platforms as well as the role of emails and blogs in the development of eWOM on SNSs (Chu and Kim, 2011; Park and Kim, 2014; Chang et al., 2013; Jun et al., 2017; Jin and Phua, 2014, Lee and Youn, 2009; Chu and Choi, 2011). eWOM has an advantage over traditional WOM communication because the variety of forms of internet-based applications like blogs, reviews and emails enable consumers to exchange essential information about brands, products and services publicly and privately (Cheung and Thadani, 2012). User-generated media functioning on digital platforms allows users across geographical boundaries to have control over their eWOM behaviour, enabling them to choose when, why and where they want to consume digital content. Within SNSs, brand communities and groups play a tremendous role in developing eWOM (Jin and Phua, 2014). Brand profile groups and communities encourage greater interaction between members to learn new information and share their opinions to geographically wide audiences. This UGC in the form of comments, posts, likes and product ratings in these brand groups enhances the credibility of the brand and contributes to positive eWOM (Paschen et al., 2017).

Hennig-Thurau and Walsh (2004) identified the key motivators behind consumers which motivate them to read opinions and digital content in online media. These factors include interactive experiences and experiential values (informational, social utilitarian, economic and hedonic) through searching, accessing and reading post-purchase information. Other factors

include informal social orientation, affiliation with social groups or communities and information related to product consumption. They further explain that these factors are the determinants of changes in consumer perceptions, enhancing trust and increasing verbal evidence in the form of word-of-mouth about products and services in the online medium. (Phua et al., 2017) argue that SNS blogs, information sharing, products reviews and informational and promotional content impact on consumer know-how, perceptions of value, brand awareness and brand trust.

Previous researchers established a relationship between eWOM and purchase intentions on social media and found that informational quality and credibility have a significant influence (Lee and Shin, 2014; Park et al., 2007; Prendergast et al., 2010). Similarly the eWOM developed on UGC exchanges on Web 2.0-based digital platforms such as social media have a significant impact on consumer purchase intentions (Erkan and Evans, 2016). Social media brand groups or community-based social interactions on SNSs enable specific informational and knowledge exchange amongst members to not only create informational value but also to support marketing activities and to directly engage with customers through interactive promotional content (Park and Kim, 2014). (Cheung and Thadani, 2012) state that eWOM is the outcome of the quality, credibility and interactivity of digital content in terms of the products and services which are positioned to develop purchase intentions.

2.5.1. Online Social Influence and eWOM

Bearden et al. (1989) studied the role of interpersonal social influence on the development of word-of-mouth and explained that individuals in social networks are more susceptible to such influences in terms of their purchase behaviours. Briley et al. (2000) argued that individuals in society who have an interdependent self and who value to the importance of the social context are more favourably influenced by word-of-mouth. Brown and Reingen (1987) explained the role of social interactions and their influence on the diffusion of products and services as an antecedent to word-of-mouth. Such social ties in online networks predict eWOM in group-based social interactions on SNSs (Toder-Alon and Brunel, 2018). Bearden et al. (1989) argue that such interpersonal influence varies amongst individuals, leading to the development of word-of-

mouth that can be categorised into two dimensions: normative (compliance) and informational influence (internalisation). Furthermore, social identity is also a major level of social influence that develops eWOM in electronic media particularly on SNSs (Okazaki, 2009). Normative influence explains the tendency of the individual in society to accept and conform to the attitudes, beliefs and values of others, whereas informational influence explains the tendency of an individual to accept, interpret and validate information from credible informational sources which supports consumers' information and guidelines regarding brand products and services. These two dimensions of interpersonal influence share a similarity with Kelman's (1974) social influence dimensions of compliance and internalisation. Compliance, within the digital social network explains the change in an individual's attitudes, beliefs and intentions upon accepting the group members' attitudes, values and behaviours for the sake of rewards and happiness or functions to avoid punishment and internalisation. It is the rational choice of group members to accept the group attitudes and behaviours based on the individual's conformity with information, interpretation and the evaluation of the available information and content (Dholakia et al., 2004). Such group-based social interaction and informational exchange on SNSs in brand groups or communities develops social influence, where members internalise and confirm the credibility and reality of information about products and services and develop a group-based social intention in the form of eWOM (Farzin and Fattahi, 2018). Furthermore, Tsai et al. (2015) argue that the influence of compliance and internalisation develops eWOM through consumers' conformity to utilitarian and hedonic value as well as persuasion, social interaction, informational exchange and the consumption of informational digital content in the form of reviews and blogs. Likewise (Okazaki, 2009) identified the role of social identity in the development of eWOM on online social networks and argued that information sources and information seekers are connected in online social groups in a way that members share group-based motivation and positive self-esteem to participate in group-based social action as eWOM.

eWOM has developed through social interactions on SNSs, where individuals search for product-related advice and engagement with brand posts to maintain robust relationships online. Within brand communities on SNSs consumer-generated product content in the form of reviews, comments and blogs not only develop social influence but also enhance the credibility of the information and value perceptions of the brand's products and services (Jin and Phua,

2014). Such eWOM developed on online SNSs is used for two different purposes: market-level analysis and individual level analysis (Lee and Lee, 2009). In marketing it is used to measure marketing parameters such as product sales, while on an individual level such eWOM transforms purchase intentions in the individuals (Chevalier and Mayzlin, 2006; Duan et al., 2008; Cheung et al., 2009). eWOM on SNSs occurs when consumers provide or search for informal product-related advice through the unique applications of SNSs. Through extensive social interactions on SNSs, eWOM communicated via these sites may be especially effective given that these sites provide an easy way for consumers to not only build and maintain robust social relationships online, but to develop their purchase intentions at the same time.

2.6. Consumers Purchase Intentions

The term 'purchase intention' has been defined by many scholars as the psychological process that helps consumers to use, dispose of, or experience a rational purchase decision in relation to certain products and services based on the satisfaction of their specific needs (Erkan and Evans, 2016). Every individual is a direct or indirect consumer. Within the contextual paradigm of social psychology, consumer buying behaviour is an explicit function of the foreground of consumer attitudes, behaviour, motivation and intentions (Luo et al., 2016). Consumer psychology explains the behaviour of the consumer as a part of consumer needs. It is the psychological process involved in creating a motivation to buy and consume a specific product or service to satisfy a need. Buying behaviour is a subjective process of human cognitive and biological influence which stems from the instinctive force or motivation that develops into a rational purchase intention (Gendel-Guterman and Levy, 2013). According to (Simonson et al., 2001) consumer buying behaviour is a complex matrix of attitudes, motivations and thought processes that enable a consumer to satisfy his/her needs upon making a rational buying decision. This complex process encompasses purchase intentions as consumer perceptions of products and services, and their perspective attitudes (McNeill and Wyeth, 2011). Consumer purchase behaviour has been widely considered as a psychological process that rationally helps consumers to search for and evaluate products and services to satisfy their needs (Konuk, 2018). The drive to purchase, in the form of purchase intentions, is a key phenomenon determining the purchase behaviour of customers. Furthermore, the socio-economic characteristics of consumers

are also considered as valuable contributors towards purchase intentions (Kim and Ham, 2016). Although consumer purchase intentions are significantly impacted by the information and knowledge background of individuals, a more important mechanism is the development of reasoning and rational thinking, based on the integration of the aforementioned knowledge and cognitive abilities (de-Gregorio and Sung, 2010).

Purchase intentions come into play when a consumer evaluates a product and decides whether to purchase the product or not (Erkan and Evans, 2016). They make up their mind based upon the information they receive and based on an assessment of the usefulness of the product or service (Lueg and Finney, 2007). Compared with traditional media, the consumer decision-making process involves the same psychological process of attitudes, behaviour and motivations to develop a purchase intention in the context of online media (Irmak et al., 2010). Unlike consumer decision-making in traditional media, which involves the recognition of needs and informational search, followed by the evaluation of the alternatives and rational purchase behaviour, the online medium offers more experiential benefits which are utilitarian and hedonic, and attracts consumers with promotional adverts containing interactive content and information about products and services. These take the form of videos, podcasts, blogs, interactive information content, brand widgets or promotional messages and engage consumers with products and services more quickly in online brand communities (Alalwan, 2018; Lu, 2018). The online communications process within such communities and brand groups focuses more on creating an interest in products and services by ascertaining how online behaviour orientation and content type in such communal groups creates utilitarian and hedonic value for individuals (Zaglia, 2013; Gutiérrez-Cillán et al., 2017). This enables two-way communication between the company and the customer on the basis of consumers' relational experiences, such as involvement in brand related online activities such as interaction and the co-creation of content. Furthermore, the consumer seeks additional information from brand communities on online media about products and services before developing his/her psychological motivations and purchase intentions (Jin and Phua, 2014).

2.6.1. Theoretical Perspective of Purchase Intentions

Consumer purchase intentions are based on the premise of the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) which predicts individual intentions as an outcome of one's ability to make systematic use of information systems (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980). The TRA explains that individual beliefs and attitudes determine intentions, and those intentions in turn develop into behaviours. Attitude is the amount of effect in favour or against a specific object. According to (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1977, p.288) intentions determine individuals' behaviours and confer to the strength of ones' intention to perform a specific behaviour. The theory explains that the individual's intentions to perform a particular behaviour are based on two motivations i.e. attitude towards intentions and perceived social pressure (subjective norms) to perform or to not perform a certain behaviour in social settings. (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980) Stated that TRA predicts the individuals' purchase intentions leading to purchase behaviours, and is under the volitional control of individuals. They further indicate external factors such as demographics and individual personality traits might have certain impacts on behavioural intentions which provide a better understanding of the purchase behaviour in question. Nonetheless, past behaviours, experiences and individual involvement could also possibly predict prospective intentions and behaviors (Bagozzi et al., 2000).

Individual purchase intentions have been explained using the TPB (TPB) which is a modification of the TRA (Ajzen, 1991). In the context of social media, the TRA and TPB have been used routinely to study consumer purchase intentions (Amaro and Durate, 2015; Benson et al., 2018; Bigne et al., 2016 ; Dutta and Bhat, 2016; Sparks et al., 2013. TPB explains that beliefs determine attitudes, and subjective norms are determined by the motivation to comply and confer to normative pressures and beliefs. Perceived behavioural control is informed by the individuals' possession of the resources and opportunities to perform that specific behaviour. Based on these theoretical assumptions, individual purchase intentions on social media are influenced by individual motivations to align with the opinions and values of a social group or community members which hold importance to individuals. Secondly, individual beliefs about possessing the necessary resources to engage in behaviours constitute purchase intentions.

In the context on SNS brand communities, heterogenic consumer social interactions (informational, social hedonic and economic) determine their attitude, which in turn develops into purchase intentions. Consumer purchase intentions are informed by adopting and complying with socially accepted beliefs and attitudes about brands and their products and services. Additionally TBP explains the influence of subjective norms on purchase intentions by means of accepting the social media platform as a credible information source (Wang et al., 2012). Perceived behavioural control has a role in developing purchase intentions since it motivates individuals to seek opportunities and resources in the form of promotions, discounts and benefits associated with making purchase decisions.

2.6.2. Social Media and Consumers Purchase Intentions

Dynamic changes to consumer behaviour occur due to the mediating role of the online medium. This has motivated marketers and experts to research the key factors involved in shaping the online decision-making motivations of consumers (Abdullah et al., 2016). This shift towards an expanded view of on relationship marketing has changed the relationship between online users and businesses, developing online social media as extensive opportunities for online commerce and trade by considering online social media as a competitive advantage (Ozuem et al., 2016). Within the context of integrated marketing communications, market superiority has become a primary concern for many businesses, and online social media are considered major tools for communicating with customers, targeting their utilitarian or hedonic motivations and stimulating online behaviour and in order to develop a consumer-centric online marketing strategy (Alalwan et al., 2017). Marketers are aware of the online role of consumers in the development of product recognition and brand recognition, so they need to understand the key factors affecting purchase intentions on an online medium. It is also important to understand how to utilise such information to tailor the online behaviour of consumers (Alalwan et al., 2017).

Leeraphong and Mardjo (2013) argue that the online behaviour of consumers varies and depends on their heterogenic online social exchanges, as well as their informational accomplishment, culture, online reference group interactions and relational experiences with brand groups and

communities. This explains the mechanism of online consumer decision-making to satisfy their needs. The authors further affirm that the personality and cognitive makeup of consumers also influences their buying patterns. Cognitive factors include self-confidence, social interactions, value perceptions and personal gratification (Erkan and Evans, 2016). Value perception and gratification is a product of dyadic social interactions and group based exchanges of annotated information content through multiple levels of social aggregations (Muntinga et al., 2011). Further, such value perception facilitates decision-making amongst online actors through group based social interactions which create uniformity in behaviours and attitudes in online contexts (Cheung et al., 2011). On the basis of the theoretical knowledge available in related literature, there is clear evidence that actors' dyadic or group based online social media interactions play a vital role in triggering purchase intentions through interactions with social media (Alalwan et al., 2017; Wang, 2014 Chang et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2010).

Increased traffic and the wide usage of social media has won the attention of online users who are searching for valuable information and digital content which can assist with decision-making (Curty and Zhang, 2013; Hajli, 2015). Such interactions amongst online consumers, with the help of information search tools have increased the utilitarian and hedonic value of social media, thereby making it a platform of trade to encourage communication and interactions amongst online members. (Mersey et al., 2010) note that a new marketing reality has evolved due to the integration of such communication and internet-based technologies which enable consumers to receive key information quickly to meet their specific needs and to make subsequent purchase decisions as follow-up actions.

Hajli (2014, p. 388) explained this phenomenon as

“The networking of individuals through social media provides shared values, leading to a positive impact on trust (Wu et al., 2010). Today, with the expansion of social media and SNSs, a study of consumer behaviour on these platforms is a research agenda (Liang and Turban, 2011) because social media are likely to develop marketing strategies in firms through trust-building mechanisms and affecting customers' intention to buy online products”

Social media is of significant value for engaging consumers in online digital content, facilitating interactions and intimacy amongst consumers. It has expanded the view of relationship marketing and imposed a transition from conventional relationship marketing into new “transcending view of relationship marketing” through increasing the involvement of consumers in firms’ brand related activities such as interactions and the co-creation of content (Gutiérrez-Cillán, 2017). This helps them to develop a greater understanding in order to develop a significant purchase intention (Hajli et al., 2014). The social interaction and content consumption patterns of online users on multiple social media platforms has increased substantially, thereby enhancing the dependence companies place on the use of social media marketing to target consumers to increase sales leads (Hajli, 2015). Furthermore, communication between companies and online consumers relating either to the brand or the company name creates a greater impact on the positioning and consumption patterns of online social users (Cheung et al., 2014). This new perspective has commercial implications for consumer engagement with online content which includes interactivity in the form of videos, graphics or other interesting components ascertaining the interactive experiences of consumers with brands. These are used to understand online behaviour and buying decision processes (Hajli et al., 2014). As a part of continual development in the communication between online consumers and companies, businesses capitalise on user interactions and pay attention to the online content of their promotional campaigns by introducing online stores, which have transformed online users into potential consumers (Hajli and Lin, 2014).

Social media networking sites such as Facebook, YouTube, LinkedIn and Twitter are profitable media to invest in for marketing products and services. Each of these SNSs represents a unique opportunity to interact with a specific type of audience, and reveals the heterogeneity of users’ online social behaviour in terms of social media marketing. The uniqueness of consumer behaviour in brand groups and communities on each of these social networking platforms in the form of social interactions, socio-emotional support, group discussions and information and idea exchanges helps companies to target specific consumer needs in accordance with online search patterns and social exchange (Wang and Yu, 2017; Lu, 2018). With such interactive tools in brand communities on SNSs, companies create brand recognition and an identity for their products and services by enhancing interactive experiences to endure consumers’ engagement

with their promotional campaign content (Chu and Choi, 2011). With marketer-generated and brand fan-generated communities and groups on SNSs marketers can continually monitor changes in the online behavioural patterns of online consumers for information and to retain loyal customers. In this way, they can collaboratively create value with group members (Schau et al., 2009; Zaglia, 2013; Baird and Parasnis, 2011; Barreda et al., 2015; Naylor et al., 2012).

2.6.3. Social Media and Consumers' Purchase Intentions in Perspective of Social Influence Theory

Consumer purchase intentions are a complex dimension of online purchase behaviour. Purchase intentions have been widely studied in the context of online marketing as a subsequent corollary to online marketing strategies (Chen et al., 2016). Purchase intentions are of critical value in conceptualising purchase behaviour which influences the subjective rationality of the consumer decision-making process (Yamoah et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2018). Consumer social influence embedded in behavioural intentions is an integral part of the consumer decision-making process and illustrates how online consumers regard the adoption of certain well-formulated purchase behaviour (Kang and Schuett, 2013). Social influence could either develop into positive or negative purchase intentions, impacting on the consequences of overall purchase behaviour (Wang, 2014). The contextual value of social consumer influence in determining purchase behaviour is powerful, as ubiquitous SNSs social interactions are a strong contributory factor directly affecting purchase decisions (Kim et al., 2011). Beukeboom et al. (2015) suggests that consumer purchase intentions on online social media are the cumulative impact of experiential value (utilitarian and hedonic), and behavioural and attitudinal changes in online media settings.

Individual social interactions on online media are of critical value in conceptualising consumer purchase behaviour, which influences the subjective rationality of the decision-making process (Bagozzi, 2000; Hajli et al., 2017). Such online social group-based interactions in terms of the degree of online members activities result in one of three distinct levels of social influence i.e. compliance, internalisation and identity. Kang and Schuett (2013) and Zhou (2017) state that individual online social interactions influence decision making through the internalisation of

social influence (informational) or normative social influence (compliance), and this depends upon the involvement, membership social pressure and distinct interests of individuals in the group or network. Informational social influence is also understood from the perspective of internalisation, where individuals seek and provide information and knowledge in SNSs communities and internalise these values into their value system. Informational social exchange within SNS brand communities not only influences individual beliefs which are easy to change, but also shape beliefs which are more resistant because such beliefs are deep rooted and have higher levels of individual involvement (Lu, 2018). Such deep-rooted beliefs are highly valued and are associated with the individuals' personal experiences, providing them direction and guidance to understand reality (Pérez and Carrasco, 1998). In reality, the significant impact of online persuasive communication and social interaction depends on the internalised association of individuals with a source of information (Kang and Schuett, 2013; Zaglia, 2013).

The resultant influence on individual beliefs and attitudes mainly depends on socio-cognitive links between the credibility of the informational source and the individuals' perception of self-competence (Cheung et al., 2011). Taking the informational source into consideration enhances the motivation of actors to elaborate upon their knowledge. Such informational source on SNS brand communities encourages individuals to accept informational influence and to acknowledge the superiority of useful information about products and services. In particular, in the decision making process, this phenomenon holds significant value as the dynamics of the pragmatic informational social interaction and communication lead to the development of new and more accurate information as a contribution to the objectivity of truth (Zhou, 2017)

Kaplan and Miller (1987) explained that normative social influence differs from informational social influence in the sense that individual decision making is based on compliance to elicit positive evaluations of significant others and to comply to group decisions. Zhou and Li (2014) explain that normative influence predominately impacts on individual decision making in groups even when conditions favour normative social influence and informative social influence. Normative social influence or compliance comes into play when the social interactions are motivated by normative social pressure, rewards or benefit. The subjective importance of subjective norms have been identified by (Hansen et al., 2011 ; Ham et al., 2015) who measured

perceived behavioural control and subjective norms in relation to buying behaviour. Subjective norms explain the perceived social influence of individuals in social circles that influence behaviour (Cialdini and Goldstein, 2004). Subjective norms develop compliance based social influence, where individuals confirm and accept changes in attitude and behaviour for happiness and satisfaction to fit in with significant others. Park and Kim (2014) argue that individual social interactions in SNS brand communities are intrigued by the perception of the benefits of group interaction such as informational, hedonic and economic benefits. These benefits are based on an exchange of beliefs which are categorised as functional, hedonic and experiential benefits. Such perceived benefits could also lead to changes in purchase behaviour (Casaló et al., 2013). Likewise, Dholakia et al. (2009) argued that perceived social networking benefits such as peer to peer problem solving, collaborative learning and technological support changes in individual behaviours upon accepting social influence. Such informational offerings and monetary incentives on SNS brand communities encourage consumer engagement with brand content and transform behaviour by creating a psychological bond to connect with brands to strengthen relationships with the company.

These research findings resonate with the TPB, which explains the systematic process of possible consumer behaviours in the market. The TPB is an interdisciplinary framework, determining the possibility of behaviour in online media. The purchase aspects of the TPB explain that consumer purchase intentions are the resultant impact of perceived behavioural control, subjective norms and relative attitudes that contribute towards consumer decision-making (Azjan, 1991; Gruen et al., 2006; Kuster et al., 2016). Fu et al. (2018) further state that the most important factors on social media which predominantly mediate its role in consumer purchase intentions are consumer value perceptions, perceived behavioural control and subjective norms (Tarkiainen and Sundqvist, 2005). These factors explicitly contribute towards the development of consumer purchase intentions as they enable active information-seeking by individuals online when an online user evaluates a product or service and is not sure about the outcomes of the purchase decisions regarding a product (Mahon et al., 2006). Value perceptions and subjective norms increase the online buyer's ability to discriminate between the choices available on the basis of quality and specific personal needs (Okazaki et al., 2014). This three-factor construct influences consumer purchase intentions and has been widely used in multi-

dimensional social media research where perceived behaviour control and subjective norms have been found to be the most significant contributors towards positive purchase intentions (Young et al., 2013). Compared to the normative social influence of subjective norms, information-based social influence has developed through conformance to the beliefs of social actors as well as their values and intentions. Internalisation social influence is significant when it comes to making decisions related to product evaluation and online purchase decisions (Burnkrant and Cousineau, 1975; Currás-Pérez et al., 2013; Hajli et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2011). Social interactions based on informational exchange are shaped in the sense that individuals conform to behavioural change and accept social influence by accepting the opinions of others and by engaging in the mutual exchange of information through social interactions. This behaviour has been linked to travel purchase decision making (Kang and Schuett, 2013). Internalisation social influence also leads to behavioural conformity which further develops buying behaviour (Wood and Hayes, 2012). However such conformity of behaviour does not depend on the satisfaction of significant others, but rather individuals have independence and a choice to make in reaching a decision by accepting a change in their attitude and intentions. To arrive at this they look at other members' judgements and behaviours as an information source and assume that such information can be better than individual judgement (Çelen and Kariv, 2004). The underlying assumption of informational social influence is based on individual perceptions that other members in the online network or group have arguably more accurate and better information and so can be considered informational reference points (Kuan et al., 2014). Informational social influence develops conformity in the sense that individuals in the social network are influenced by the way other social actors have made a purchase decision (Herding, 2010). In online social media settings, information exchange is entered into by a number of people who make a buying decision and exert informational social influence on hesitant buyers to make a rational purchase decision (Kuan et al., 2014). Furthermore, sharing such information about a purchase decision also exerts influence and encourages online members to make unplanned purchase decisions.

Bagozzi (1992; 2000) stated that online influence is the shared intention and resultant outcome of group-based intentional social action. Further, the desire to act as the impetus for such social action creates eWOM in online media that influences changes in group-based intentions and decision making behavior (Okazaki, 2009). eWOM is the product of group based social action

that functions on the basis of social connection, communication and identity between the information sharing social actors and the individuals seeking information (Lee and Koo, 2015).

Muntinga et al. (2011) state that eWOM is the outcome of the consumer's interaction with other consumers in the brand community, and with the content uploaded by other consumers. Group based online word of mouth subsequently leads to individual purchase intentions (Okazaki, 2009; Lu, 2018; Kim et al., 2011 Kim et al., 2018). Elwalda et al. (2016) explain that eWOM is an alternative source to two way interactions on digital platforms compared to traditional word of mouth. Such eWOM leads specifically to the development of buying behaviour in multiple ways (Erkan and Evans, 2016). Firstly this occurs through online interactions and the exchange of information about the cost, price and features of financial services. Secondly, it supports the buyer's value system and rational analysis to evaluate alternatives. Finally it provides online members with organized and well-structured information (Augusto and Torres, 2018). More specifically such eWOM leads to purchase intentions online in financial services. Since users consider detailed and direct comparisons between financial services, they evaluate information about the value of a financial service purchase.

Walsh et al. (2004) argued that there is a distinctive set of psychological and motivational factors that drive the acceptance of changes in attitude and the intentions of individuals on online platforms. These are value perceptions, identity, motivation and gratification. Consumer articulations of social influence on SNSs are subject to online social interactions in relation to purchase related information, social orientation behaviour and attitudinal change. Also relevant here are active memberships of brands online SNSs groups and communities, and perspective exchanges of knowledge and learning about the consumption of products or services.

It holds a rational implication for the subjective value of online economics where the perceived value perception and usefulness of the product and services attract the attention of consumers. Such subjective value perceptions and the motivations of consumers are factors that have a tremendous impact on purchase intentions (Kim et al., 2011; Zhou, 2017). Walsh et al. (2004) argue that there is a distinctive set of psychological and motivational factors that drive the acceptance of changes in attitude and the intentions of the online platforms. Muntinga et

al.(2011) argue that the uses and gratification (U and G) factors identified by Katz et al. (1974) explicitly explain consumer value perceptions towards the use of SNS.

The U & G examines media fulfilment from the consumers' point of view as a contrast to the traditional effect-oriented approach that explains consumer media fulfilment from a communicator's point of view (Aitken et al., 2008). Boyd, (2008) and Muntinga et al. (2011) examined the tentative reasons behind individual uses of social media and explained that U and G factors motivate consumer social interactions on an experiential and utilitarian basis. They further influence consumer behaviours and attitudes towards brand advertisements and purchase behaviors. The motivation of users to interact on social media is the principal element in the integration of online consumers' perceived usefulness and perceived value in the social media (Konuk, 2018). Consumer value perceptions explain the true value an online consumer perceives of during multi-dimensional interactions with online digital product-related content in the form of videos, product reviews and follow-up of active social group discussions (Tsai and Men, 2013). It also explains why consumers choose social media to interact and this serves as an antecedent to engagement with social media brand related activities (Phua and Kim, 2017). Such motivational factors trigger the individual's need to interact and engage with brand related content on SNSs, and to search for products and services which satisfy his/her need(s). This also concerns active memberships of brands on SNSs groups and communities. Consumers engagement with UGC in such spaces to satisfy their utilitarian and hedonic needs and to learn about the consumption of products or services (Muntinga et al., 2011).

Previous research (Chi, 2011; Kelly et al., 2010; Rodgers et al., 2007) suggests that consumer value perceptions facilitate SNS brand group based social interactions and motivations to engage with online content, making their involvement more proactive and co-creative in the firm's activities. Consumer engagement can attain maximum user exposure on online social media through multi-dimensional social interactions which mediates the relationship between social influence and consumer purchase intentions (Kang and Schuett, 2013). Consumer engagement is "a psychological state of consumers developed as a result of the impact of interaction, co-creation of consumers with the online digital content" (Brodie et al., 2011a). Further in their research suggest that online social networks help consumers to engage with

online content and interact on the basis of their perceptions, in order to gain wide acceptance and knowledge. The pragmatic relevance of consumer engagement is that it also allows online consumers to review products and services and to evaluate their current purchase behaviour in relation to future purchases by posting their purchase experiences on SNSs communities (Lu, 2018). Tsai and Men, (2013) explain that consumer engagement has a direct influence on consumer purchase intentions on social media as it enables interactions between UGC online (blogs, product reviews, group discussions and personal opinions) and consumers. Such engagement also develops trust between the online medium and consumers, establishing the online social network as a place that offers factual information and practical know-how about products and services embedded within online promotional content (Zaglia, 2013).

In all the major studies that seek to determine consumer purchase intentions, consumer value perceptions and motivations have been considered as the key determinants of the motivation of social media use and positive purchase intentions (Kim and James, 2016; Azjan, 2015; Kim and Ko, 2012; Chen et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2011). Kang and Schuett, (2013) state that, in order to closely analyse the conditions underlying the acceptance of social influence, the role of the flow of information could explicitly determine the subsequent engagement of individuals in the SNS brand group to formulate purchase intentions. Consumer brand related behaviours constructed on social media such as COBRA support similar finding by explaining that the multiple levels of user generated content engagement result in consumer to consumer, and consumer to brand behaviour on SNSs (Muntinga et al., 2011). Such conceptualisation which considers the actions of other social actors in shaping individual behaviours could lead to the acceptance of group based social influence due to engagement and interaction with the online information about the products and services (Zhang et al., 2017). The cumulative impact of the continuous growth of SNSs brand groups and communities has played a major role in brand value by justifying social media as one of the most significant marketing tools that companies use (Hajli et al., 2017).

Within the context of consumer online social influence on social media, online reference groups and communities encompass three forms of interaction and socialisation by the

online user with members of social media. First, social media facilitates communication and knowledge-building amongst online users through online blogs, micro-blogs and interactive promotional content (Gutiérrez-Cillán et al., 2017). Secondly SNSs enable extensive interactions between online users and reference groups and communities to help them make a purchase decision. Finally, they strengthen the ties between social entities and online users, to enhance the socialisation of information through information exchange (Zaglia, 2013). Further, such information exchange within online SNS brand groups and communities can be either positive or negative with the potential engagement of consumers in the social group mediating consumer purchase intentions (Liao and Chu, 2012).

From a qualitative perspective, the degree of involvement and active participation of online members in group based social interactions explicitly depends on the size of group on the SNS (Kang and Schuett, 2013). Intra-group social interactions can be characterised in terms of the frequency of sharing and exchange practices, the propensity of group members to address and solve an inquiry or problem and the uniformity and consistency of the topics under discussion (Negoescu and Gatica-Perez, 2008). Such in-group social interaction behaviour stems from behavioural conformity through accepting group based informational or normative social influence. Internalisation (informational) social influence has prior importance in this regard as it is more instrumental when the group based social interaction adds value to the existing information about products or services (Dholakia et al., 2009) Such informational influence provides a solution to the problem related to product inquiries. It supports existing information that individuals possess about a product or service. Furthermore, such influence is considered as internalised influence because it is perceived to enhance individual knowledge about the products and services and it develops a significant change in behaviour to allow individuals to develop their own evaluation (Burnkrant and Cousineau, 1975; McGuire, 1969).

The empirical modelling of such in-group interactions has enabled companies to construct effective strategies for the future growth of online brand groups (Wang et al., 2012). Such modelling further helps companies to increase their online group's affiliation by improving informational search facilities and providing online customers with services and products whilst helping with service-related problems (Lee, 2017). This helps the company when it launches a

new product or service and advertises it/these on online SNSs such as Facebook. As the online consumer increasingly depends on Facebook as a trusted informational source, new opportunities for social interactions and consumer-brand relationships in the financial service industry evolve (Mitic and Kapoulas, 2012).

Facebook group based interactions offer members valuable information in relation to brand related products and services and this significantly enhances their value perceptions about brands (Park and Kim, 2014). The mobilisation of such information further leads them to make rational purchase decisions. On such a group based SNS, consumers have the opportunity to raise sufficient enquiries about essential financial services such as property mortgage, credit finance, lease, car finance etc, further leading them to develop a purchase decision. This could either be done through social interactions and engagement of consumers with information or through online recommendations evaluating products and services. It might be fulfilled through recommendations about existing product owners/users. This phenomenon is one of the main advantages of SNSs since they promote online users' ability to strengthen their ties on social platforms to enhance the social network by adding more ties to it (Zhou, 2017).

Facebook groups explicitly provide impetus for group based social interactions where users share common interests, express opinions, download brand widgets and post images and photos, thereby unifying their attitudes and behaviour with group norms and changing their opinion and behavioural intentions (Chu, 2011). Facebook groups are a structured set of social relationships and ties amongst online users sharing a common identity; i.e. they are enduringly engaged with brand related activities and they admire the brand (Zaglia, 2013). In-group behaviour explains group members' personal actions representing his or her identity in the group. Such self-disclosure leads to the subsequent development of social influence at different levels (Zhou, 2017). Individual group based self-disclosure refers to how the individual presents themselves, and their feelings and experiences of being in the group (Chu, 2011). Self-disclosure on SNSs takes the form of user-generated information about an online member in a group. Such self-disclosure plays a significant role in individual and group-based relationship development on SNSs brand communities where individuals

express their needs, or motives to be a member of the group as part of a discussion (Gutiérrez-Cillán et al., 2017). Such self-disclosure is related to online members' use of the SNSs and fundamentally impacts on social and behavioural modifications by creating awareness and purchase intentions (Lee, 2017). Social ties in the brand communities help with essential social information and interactive exchanges between online users and social actors, groups and communities. This occurs via the diffusion of as many contacts as possible into the social networking circle. The amassed online social interaction, social groups and communities then become the reference groups for online users on the social medium, which impact on the consumers' decision-making choice (Munzel et al., 2018). These reference groups can be categorised as primary and secondary reference groups, based on the rate of interaction. The primary reference group usually involves the highest rate of social interaction including with friends, family, and peers, and the secondary online reference group involves a relatively lower rate of interaction and includes fellow professionals, or religious and spiritual groups. Either informative or normative social influences condition the uniformity of the information shared and exchanged by social members. This has a significant impact on the consumers' evaluation and informational mind-set about product and service quality, as well as utility and economies of scale (Lee et al., 2011). Social influence is particularly operative in this type of group-based interaction and exchange where individuals evaluate the product or service and make a rational buying decision based on the uniformity of information, their personal judgement and their interpersonal response orientation (Henningsen et al., 2003).

Maintaining such network-based interpersonal online interactions and connectivity with online members increases social exchange and communication, cultivating the multi-dimensional social influence of such online social interactions in the form of social support, growth in the social network of an online user based on mutual exchange of information, knowledge and intimacy (Park et al., 2007). Kotler et al. (2009) reveal in their study that the development of social networking applications running on UGC principles has transformed the appearance of the online marketing landscape, due to the inherent online purchase behaviour satisfying consumers' specific needs through relevant information exchange and communication within an online social group. Such participative social interactions based

on the active membership of online users not only helps them to make a purchase decision but also gratifies the consumers' hedonic needs at the same time. This is achieved through expressing opinions, and acknowledging and recognising the social community as well as peers, friends and family.

Chapter 3: Research Design

3.1. Research Paradigm

The methodology used in this thesis is based on the social constructionist research paradigm which enables an analysis of the impact of social media interactions on consumer purchase intentions in context of social influence theory. The research paradigm used explains the dissemination of social influence knowledge and its implications in social media communications and marketing promotions. The paradigm also explains the constructivist and epistemological assumptions about heterogeneity and the ubiquity of the informational, social, hedonic and utilitarian social interactions on social media to develop distinctive levels of social influence that change individual attitudes and intentions. This paradigm highlights a shared set of beliefs and agreements underpinning the scientific approach towards understanding and addressing an existing empirical phenomenon (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The term ‘paradigm’ has its roots in the Greek word “paradeigma” which means ‘pattern or outline of a process’. It was first introduced by Kuhn (1970) who defined it as the framework of activities used in investigations by scientists and researchers to enable them to problem-solve and posit a structured solution in the form of an empirical model.

According to Kuhn (1970, p.10):

“The research paradigm in “normal science means research firmly based upon one or more past scientific achievements, achievements that some particular scientific community acknowledges for a time as supplying the foundation for its further practice.”

Masterman (1970) explained that, while establishing an understanding of a particular phenomenon, there are three main categories of research paradigms which encompass presuppositions and the investigation of scientific knowledge about an existing problem. They are: metaphysical, sociological and artefact paradigms. A metaphysical research paradigm describes the hidden and unquestioned presuppositions about an existing problem which are well-known amongst the various members of the scientific community. A social paradigm

describes the constellation of social values, beliefs and interactions among various members of a society, formulating the basis of significant sociological phenomena. An artefact paradigm describes the investigation and understanding of problems related to well-established paradigm models, providing the basis for an ontological understanding of knowledge in the existing field. (Levin and Wagner, 2009). Existing literature has explained the subjective importance of social influence theory as a relationship between social media and consumer purchase intentions. Social influence theory (Kelman, 1958) is a well-known and established socio-psychological framework developed primarily on the basis of ontology and epistemological assumptions. He further explained that social influence develops three distinctive forms such as compliance, social identity and group norms (internalisation). The constructivist paradigm and epistemology explain the reality of social influence as a socially constructed phenomenon subjective to the experiences and interactions of individuals in any society (Mutch, 2005).

3.2. Social Constructionism Paradigm

The term social constructionism originated as a philosophical approach explaining the nature of reality. In essence, it explains the creation of knowledge and the nature of the knowledge created while being less concerned with the ontology of the research (Young and Collin, 2004). Social constructionism does not take reality for granted, but rather seeks to explore how social factors impact on the creation of knowledge on the basis of certain underpinning epistemological assumptions (Hibberd, 2011). The term ‘social constructionism’ originally developed a few decades ago and its roots are embedded in sociology. It has been part of research methodologies in the postmodern era of research carried out on a qualitative basis. The term was introduced into social research methodology by the renowned social scientists Berger and Luckmann (1966) through their work entitled “social construction of reality” in which they applied the philosophy of social constructionism to their investigation of the case of religion. In their research they found that social constructionism is not associated with ontology, as it has an anti-realist and relativistic stance in research. Billig (1987) stated that social constructionism enforces accurate observations of phenomena in real time, thereby providing an accurate reflection of the phenomena investigated. Social constructionism interprets subjective knowledge, emotions and cognitions of individuals on multiple levels and reveals factual evidence about how these aspects

are related to phenomena and are involved in the creation of its effects (Brown, 1989). In the domain of social psychology, social constructionism often refers to the scientific process through which individuals' cognitive structures transform their knowledge about certain social phenomena when interacting with their environment and subjects in society. Social constructionism explains that heterogenic interactions on social media have multiple outcomes. Social influence posits that all individual actors within the social system are interdependent rather than independent. Secondly it explains how the members or social actors interact, link and develop an information and affection-based relationship, and lastly, how the linkages or social interactions evolve into social influence to explain their economic and social choices by means of their behaviours and decisions.

Social constructionism underpins a subjective approach using a qualitative methodology for developing a detailed understanding of heterogeneous social media interactions (Flanigan and Babchuk, 2015). Constructionism explains how individuals in society experience the impact of a shared social phenomenon qualitatively (Creswell, 2013). Social constructionism is especially valuable for critically investigating the application and limitations of complex socio-psychological, ambiguous and emotionally laden constructs (Burr, 2015). The process of drawing on multiple meanings from existential experience using subjective qualitative research design has triggered a seismic paradigm shift from a traditional deductive (positivist) to an inductive (subjective) approach across academic disciplines (Vagle, 2014). For example, while investigating social media and user behavior from the perspective of social influence theory, social constructionism explains how social interactions between social actors leads to a greater understanding of the multiple meanings of social influence. Furthermore, the subjective approach in constructionism enables researchers to draw out qualitative findings based on their epistemological assumptions.

Scientific development based on epistemology and constructivist assumptions that individuals' social relationships and SNSs community interaction influence their behaviours in multiple ways has been the starting point of research for interdisciplinary social scientists for decades (Kjos et al., 2013; Zhou, 2017). Some of the notable contributions in this regard were made by categorising individuals' heterogenic social interactions and the influence of relationships in the

context of social influence theory, inferring that such interactions within the social system define the subject's existence and identity in society (Bagozzi and Dholakia, 2002; Bagozzi and Lee, 2007; Okazaki, 2009; Okazaki et al., 2014). Social constructionism explains the multiple meanings of heterogeneous social interactions and the impact of heterogeneous social interactions on the behaviour, attitude and actions of humans. The constructionist paradigm further explains the development and modification of human behaviour as an outcome of social interaction, and explains this phenomenon in the light of various socio-behavioural theories and frameworks, for example the social influence framework (Kjos et al., 2013). Based on the realm of social connections and interactions and relationships in the social network, the constructionist paradigm provides an inductive insight into how consumer interactions are driven by interactive experiences on social media platforms such as SNS brand communities and groups. In this way, consumer-generated and market-generated digital content can shape the purchasing behaviours of individuals in the retail financial services industry. This helps to develop certain epistemological assumptions, for example that online consumer purchase intentions in the financial services sector are the result of the strong influence of SNS brand group and community based social interactions and rational behavioural modifications. The foundation of constructivist research relies on an inductive methodology and epistemological assumptions. It explains the change in an individual's social behaviour is an outcome of distinctive social influences sourced from ubiquitous and heterogenic social interactions. It has multiple meanings associated with it when studied in the light of socio-behavioural empirical frameworks (Dholakia et al., 2004; Zhou, 2011; Zhou, 2017; Qi et al., 2018). These subjective and epistemological assumptions were first investigated by Kelman (1958) leading to the first social influence framework which explained that there are three basic components of social influence: compliance, identification and internalisation. The research paradigm evaluates the phenomenon of social influence on ontological grounds, and explains subjective changes in ontological knowledge as a result of the subjectivist evidence of epistemological assumptions.

According to Hammersley (1992) social constructionism entails the development of knowledge and explains the creation of knowledge as the outcome of the interactions and experiences of individuals in society. He further stated that while explaining social constructionism there are two major factors that contribute towards the constructionism processes for creating knowledge

philosophy, which are accommodation and assimilation. Assimilation posits that individuals in society incorporate and add new experiences into their previous perceptions and experiences about certain events or phenomena. Assimilation enables individuals in society to modify their perceptions by adding new dimensions of thinking into their mind-sets and to update their knowledge, for example, about brands through realistic interactions with their surroundings in SNSs communities. These ultimately change perceptions of products and services. Likewise, accommodation entails the reframing of new experiences and interaction-based knowledge into an individual's psychological setup and mental capacity. For example, it asserts that every individual has a different vision and perception about the value of financial services in everyday life, and so they have to accommodate the concept in order to reframe their expectations of outcomes, as it would be impossible to develop understanding and knowledge without taking into account the way in which the world works (Denizin and Lincoln, 2002).

Social constructionism explains multiple realities in terms of individual social interactions on the basis of ontology and subjective epistemology (Creswell, 2013). Social constructionism, often referred to as interpretism, is widely known in the post-modern era of qualitative research and analysis (Young and Collin, 2004). Interpretism explains how multiple meanings of a phenomenon are created by individuals, corresponding to their inductive experiences. Individuals' understanding of mutual interactions and the development of multiple meanings and perceptions as a result of such interaction-based social influence are mutually exclusive (Wang and Sun, 2016). These meanings are associated with inductive reasoning and are not innate within each social actor (Creswell and Miller, 2000). Social constructionism explains that the meaning of SNS based social influence and its value in social media settings are associated with the axiological stance of the researchers' association with the research process. The researchers' intervention is a fundamental aspect of constructionism and value creation. Social constructionism evaluates SNS and users' interactions in brand communities developing distinctive social influence in some depth based on qualitative scientific methods. It explains how different individuals accept social influence at different levels, and how social influence changes the attitudes and actions of online users of social media. It has been adopted as a paradigmatic approach while evaluating SNS and social interactions in brand groups and communities. This is because it examines reality in depth and on a wide social scale on the basis

of qualitative methods. This pattern of social interaction dynamics is of specific interest to marketers because individual behaviours and attitude changes are exclusively related to the prediction and targeting of the online behaviour of consumers towards products and services using social media (Hollebeek et al., 2014). This constructionist methodology explains the ontology of social influence and sheds light on social behavioural dynamics in the light of qualitative social interactions among members of social groups. Further, this constructionist paradigm helps to create multiple meanings of the phenomenon, providing a deeper understanding of social influence phenomenon developed as a result of heterogenic social interactions that change the individual behaviours, attitudes and actions in a society.

In this study, the constructionism paradigm applies to research conducted on the basis of three important principles: first, that individual social interactions on social media are significantly associated with social influence, behavioural change and individual beliefs; secondly, that SNSs brand communities, groups and social entities and individuals' heterogenic interactions are mutually exclusive; and lastly that behavioural modification and relationship development within the realm of social interaction are dynamic in nature (Gehlbach, 2010; Schrader, 2015). Zhou (2017) noticed the heterogeneous impact of social media on attitudinal outcomes from the perspective of social influence theory and highlighted the multi-dimensional subjective outcome of social influence on individuals' actions and attitudes. In their study they explained that their objective measurement of social influence was based on the antecedents of each of its factors. Additionally they investigated the ontology of online social influences on SNSs and predicted that the hedonic and utilitarian value of social interactions on social media gauge the users' commitment to engage with SNS communities. They further ascertained that the informational and emotional support were the key motivators towards engagement with SNS communities and these are linked to the development of an intrinsic association with them. These findings were supported by Kang and Schuett (2013) in a later study, in which they evaluated the impact of social media interactions to develop multiple levels of social influence that change the attitudes, opinions and purchase decisions of those purchasing travel.

Existential research has limited application to social influence theory when studied in the context of online social media to examine changes in the attitude and behaviours of online users. Previous studies adopted positivist approaches by using a psychological lens to study the role of heterogenic online social interactions in transforming the opinion, attitudes and beliefs of the individuals within socio-psychological disciplines only. The notable works in this regard come from authors like Dholakia et al. (2004) who studied individual social interactions from the perspective of social influence theory and measured changes in virtual community participation. Cheung et al. (2011) studied the role of social influence theory in determining the impact of individual social interactions towards using SNSs such as Facebook. (Zhou, 2011) studied individual social interactions on social media from a social influence perspective and measured intentional social actions for virtual community participation. (Tsai and Bagozzi, 2014) argued that individual participation in virtual communities occurs in light of multiple social influence levels. Kang and Schuett (2013) studied the role of SNS community based social interactions and interactive experiences and their role in developing travel motivations. Hwang (2014) examined the role of social influence in individual learning outcomes on SNS and Zhou (2017) examined the role of ubiquitous social interactions on continuance commitment to use SNS communities in the context of social influence theory. Youn and Jin (2017) investigated the role of social media in consumer brand purchase intentions and consumer-brand relationship quality in the context of social influence theory. In the above-mentioned studies, the underlying epistemological stance holds three major assumptions. First, the majority of previous research has adopted a positivist, quantitative approach to study the role of social media in developing purchase intentions as shown in the table 2. Previous studies adopted a quantitative methodology to study the role of social media in developing the multiple levels of social influence to transform social behavior and beliefs. They failed to explain how and why social influence changes beliefs and attitudes as a result of heterogenic social interactions. Most of these studies focussed on pre-developed hypotheses. Such limitations in the methodologies of previous research have resulted in a notable gap in the literature and this provides a potential opportunity to apply an interpretist, qualitative methodology to understand the phenomenon. Secondly, the epistemological stances in previous research confirm the positivist belief that the use of social influence theory in online media is only useful to analyse changes in the attitudes and beliefs of individuals within socio-psychological disciplines. For example it develops intentional social actions as we-intentions,

continuance and commitment with SNS, and a motivation to use SNSs as the outcome of group based online social interactions. Finally, the antecedent and motivational factors of online social interactions in social media have also been studied to predict similar outcomes. Positivist methodologies that have been applied in previous research have explained the role of social media in the context of social influence theory as a means to change the attitude and intentions of individuals. This has greatly limited application across different contexts. Such limitations have also reduced the pragmatic scope of the application of the phenomenon within online marketing and communications disciplines. Furthermore the positivist view contradicts the fact that interactive experiences based on utilitarian and hedonic and economic social interactions can socially influence the purchase behaviors of consumers. The epistemological stances in previous research have limited the scope of social influence theory to socio-psychological disciplines only. The use of positivist, quantitative methods of research have left an extensive gap in the literature and have explained that social influence developed as a result of heterogeneous social interactions only. This has implications for socio-psychological outcomes. Such positivist approaches also fail to explain how heterogenic online social interactions on social media can lead to changes in the purchase behaviors of consumers in a marketing and communication context.

Table 2: Matrix of Social media and Consumer Purchase Intentions Research

Author	Dimensions	Industry	Method	Theory/Model/Framework
Chen et al. (2018)	SNSs, social commerce, Purchase Intentions	IT Industry, E-Business	Quantitative	VAM Model; Flow Theory
Kim and Ko (2010)	SNS, customer relationship and Purchase Intentions	Fashion Industry	Quantitative	SMM and purchase intentions conceptual model
Yusuf (2018)	Social Media, Purchase intentions, eWOM	E-Business	Quantitative	Theory of Reasoned Action and Social Support Theory
Prentice et al. (2019)	Social media, purchase intentions	Tourism	Quantitative	Social Identity theory
Farzin and Fattahi (2018)	Social Media, eWOM, Purchase Intentions	Multiple Industries	Quantitative	Social Support Theory
Hutter et al. (2013)	Social media, Branding, Purchase intentions	Automobile Industry	Quantitative	Hierarchy of effect Model (HOE)
(Wang et al. 2012)	Social media, peer Communication, Purchase Intention	Multiple Industry (E-business)	Quantitative	Consumer Socialization Theory
Ko and Kim (2015)	Social Media, Para social relationship, Purchase Intentions	fashion	Quantitative	Para social relationship Theory
Erkan and Evans (2016)	Social Media, eWOM, purchase Intentions	Education Industry	Quantitative	Information Adoption Model, Theory of reasoned Action
Pookulangara and Koesler (2011)	Culture, SNS, purchase Intentions	-	Conceptual Paper	TAM Model
Lakasmana (2018)	Social media, Purchase	Financial Services	Quantitative	Hierarchy of effects (HOE) Model

	Intentions	Industry		
Zahid et al. 2018	Social media, Green products publicity, purchase intentions	Cosmetic Industry	Quantity	Green Purchase Intention Model, theory of Planned Behavior
Bedard and Tolmie (2018)	Social media, Interpersonal influence, green purchase intentions	HR Industry	Quantitative	Social Impact Theory
Youn and Jin (2017)	Social media, social influence, purchase intentions	Textile and Clothing	Quantitative	Social Influence Theory
Reiter et al. (2017)	Social media, online communities, purchase intentions		Quantitative	Technology Acceptance Model
Bigne et al. (2016)	Social Media, Purchase intentions, eWOM	Aviation industry	Quantitative	Theory of Reasoned Action
Lim et al. (2018)	Social Media, Advertisement, Purchase Intentions	Multiple Industry	Quantitative	
Fard et al. (2016)	SNS, Purchase Intentions	Multiple Industry	Quantitative	Unified theory of acceptance and use of technology theory
Duffet (2018)	Social media, attitude, Purchase Intentions	Education	Quantitative	Multiple component Model of Attitude
Hajli et al. 2017)	Social Media, Social Presence, Purchase Intentions	Multiple Industries	Quantitative	Social Presence Theory
Ho and Wang (2015)	Social Media, Brand Communities, Purchase Intentions	Multiple industry	Quantitative	Consumer-Centric Brand Community Model
Leeraphong and Mardjo (2013)	SNS, Trust, Purchase Intentions	Multiple Industry	Qualitative	OSN Model of Purchase Intentions
Nolcheska	Social Media,	Multiple	Quantitative	

(2017)	influence, purchase intentions	Industry		Hyper-symbolic Interactionism Theory, Social Influence Theory
Ali et al. (2018)	Social Media, Social Influence, Purchase Intentions	E-business	Quantitative	SOR, Big five Model
Aluri et al. (2015)	Social Media, gratification, Purchase Intentions	Tourism Industry	Quantitative	Uses and Gratification Theory
Hajli et al. (2014)	Social Media, purchase Intentions, Trust	Multiple Industries	Quantitative	Technology Acceptance Model
Lim et al. (2017)	Social Media, Social Learning, Purchase Intentions	Higher Education Industry	Quantitative	Social Learning Theory
Sharma et al. (2015)	Social Media, Purchase Intentions, WOM	E-Business	Quantitative	Technology Acceptance Model
See-Too and Ho (2014)	Social Media, WOM, Purchase Intentions		Conceptual Paper	Trust Theory, TAM Model
Hajli (2015)	Social Media, trust, Purchase Intentions	Higher Education Industry	Quantitative	Social Commerce Construct
Ng (2013)	Social Media, trust, purchase intentions	Multiple industries	Quantitative	Trust Transference Theory, Hofstede's Cultural Dimensions theory
Hsiao et al. (2013)	Social Media, trust, social shopping	Gaming Industry	Quantitative	Consumer-centric trust model
Gunawan and Hurang (2015)	Social Media, Viral, purchase Intentions	Education Industry	Quantitative	Theory of Reasoned Action and Information adoption Model
Hung et al. (2011)	Social Media , vanity, purchase intentions	Fashion Industry	Quantitative	Consumer Culture Theory, Brand luxury Index.
Predendergast et al. (2015)	Social Media, Online Word of Mouth, purchase intentions	EBusiness	Quantitative	Social comparison Theory, Social Network Theory, Theory of reasoned Action
Mauri and Minazzi	Social Media, eWOM,	Hotel and Tourism	Quantitative	-

(2013)	Purchase Intentions	Industry		
Kamal et al. (2013)	Social Media, Materialism, Purchase Intentions	Fashion Industry	Quantitative	
Sparks and Browning (2011)	Social media, eWOM, Trust, Purchase Intentions	Hotel and Tourism Industry	Quantitative	-
Martin and Herrero (2011)	Social Media, social influence, Purchase Intentions	Tourism Industry	Quantitative	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology – UTAUT
Lim (2014)	Social Media	Multiple	Quantitative	-
Shiau and Luo (2012)	Social Media , social exchange, purchase intentions	Multiple	Quantitative	Social Exchange Theory
Jimenez et al. (2013)	Online Rviews, purchase intentions	Education Industry	Quantitative	-
Liu and Guo (2016)	Social media, social commerce, Purchase Intentions	e-Business	Quantative	Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT), Task Technology Fit (TTF) and the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)
Alnawas and Aburub (2016)	Mobile Social Media, Purchase Intentions	Multiple	Quantitative	Uses and Gratification Theory
Godey et al. (2016)	Social Media , consumer behavior, purchase intentions	Luxury Fashion Industry	Quantitative	-
Cheng et al. (2012)	SNS, Perceived Usefulness, Purchase Intentions	Multiple Industries	Quantitative	Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)
Kim and Lennon (2013)	SNS,perceived Risk, Purchase Intentions	Education Industry	Quantitative	Stimulus-Organism-Response model
Dutta and Bhat (2016)	Social Media Marketing, Trust, Purchase	Education Industry	Quantitative	Theory of Reasoned Action, theory of Planned Behavior

	Intentions			
Andrews and Bianchi (2013)	Social Media, Purchase Intentions, Consumers attitude	Multiple Industries	Quantitative	Theory of Reasoned Action
Sparks et al. (2013)	Social Media, CSR, Trust, Purchase Intentions	Tourism Industry	Quantitative	Theory of Planned Behavior
Bakar and Bidin (2014)	Mobile Social Media, Purchase Intentions	Entertainment Industry	Quantitative	Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)
Ahlabash et al. (2015)	Social Media, Behavioral Intentions	Food and Beverages Industry	Quantitative	Theory of Planned Behavior
Phang et al. (2013)	Social media , consumption intention, user interaction	E-Business	Quantitative	Social Network Analysis
Adjei et al. (2010)	Social Media, brand communities, Purchase Intetions	Manufacturing Industry	Quantitative/Netnography	-
Dejafarova and Rushworth (2017)	Social Media, purchase Decisions, eWOM	Fashion Industry	Qualitative	Source Credibility Theory/Halo effect theory
Hwang et al. (2016)	Social media, attitudes, purchase intentions	Clothing Industry	Quantitative	Technology Acceptance Model
Zhou et al. (2013)	Social Media, Social networking, Social Shopping	-	Conceptual Paper	Four-Component Model
Park et al. (2014)	Social Media, network Involvement, purchase Intentions	Multiple Industries	Quantitative	S-O-R Framework, Social Network Theory
Ayeh et al., (2013)	Social Media, UGC, Purchase Intentions	Travel and Leisure	Quantitative	Technology Acceptance Model, motivation Theory
Xu-Prior et al.	Social media,	Cosmetic	Quantitative	Hofstede's Theory of Cultural

(2014)	Online shopping, Browsing Experience	Industry		Dimensions and theory of Reasoned Action
Amaro and Durate (2015)	Social Media, Perceived Risk, Purchase Intentions	Travel and Tourism Industry	Quantitative	Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), the TPB (TPB) the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and the Innovations Diffusion Theory (IDT)
Agag and El-Masry (2016)	Online Travel communities, Purchase Intentions, WOM	Travel and Tourism	Quantitative	Innovation Diffusion theory, Technology Acceptance Model
McCormick and Livett (2012)	Online Interaction, Consumer Behavior ,e-commerce	Fashion Industry	Qualitative	Theory of Reasoned Action
Jalilvand and Samiei (2012)	SNSs, Purchase Intentions, Brand Image	Automobile Industry	Quantitative	-
Duffet (2015)	Social Media, Purchase Intentions, Behavioral Attitudes	Education Industry	Quantitative	Attitude and Hierarchy Response Model
Huang (2012)	SNSs, Customer Behavior, Flow	Multiple Industry	Quantitative	Stimulus-organism-response model
Hsiao (2011)	SNS, Purchase Intentions, Value Theory	Multiple Industries	Quantitative	Value Theory
Huang et al. (2017)	SNS, Purchase Intentions, Consumer engagement	Gaming Industry	Quantitative	Uses and gratification Theory
Kang et al. (2018)	SNS, Purchase Intentions, Flow Experience	Food Industry	Quantitative	Flow Theory
Pujadas-Hostench et al. (2019)	SNS, purchase Intentions, Self-Image	Clothing Industry	Quantitative	Theory of Planned Behavior
Benson et al. (2018)	SNS, Information Sharing, Purchase Intentions	Multiple Industries	Quantitative	Theory of Planned Behavior, theory of Reasoned Action

Chaudhary and Bisai (2018)	SNS, Green Purchase Intentions	Education Industry	Quantitative	Theory of Planned Behavior
Lin (2018)	Social Media, Purchase Intentions, Experiential Purchases	Multiple Industry	Quantitative	Social Comparison theory

(Wang, 2014) suggested that individual informational social interactions in society develop distinctive levels of social influence which significantly enhance consumer purchase intentions. Similarly, Gutiérrez-Cillán et al. (2017) stated that informational and entertainment interactions, socio-emotional support and consumer-generated content engagement in SNS brand communities distinctively influences purchase behaviors. Their views provide the epistemological basis for the constructivist paradigm, narrating the fact that social influence developed from consumer-generated and marketer generated SNS brand communities and group-based social interactions which have different meanings and outcomes when studied in marketing and communications contexts. These epistemological assumptions suggest that individual social interactions on social media (especially within SNSs brand communities) impact on attitudes and purchase behaviors, but the level and strength of the impact of this influence can vary from one individual to another (Dholakia et al., 2004; Tsai and Men, 2013). The research epistemology explains the contribution made by multiple sources of knowledge, and views reality as subjective rather than positivistic. A research epistemology explains how we create knowledge using a variety of scientific methods without accepting reality as it is, as is the case with positivistic ontology (Denizin and Lincoln, 2002). Epistemology is embedded within a constructivist scientific approach and helps the researcher to explain reality on the basis of interpretive assumptions which assert that there are multiple realities associated with the same phenomenon. (Willis, 1995) describes interpretist researchers as “anti-foundationalists” who believe in multiple truths within the same reality, rejecting the single route to knowledge. For example, different individuals in society perceive the influence of SNS on user behavior in various ways. Constructionists rely on investigations of reality using scientific methodologies in which the researchers create value using scientific methods, while studying the impact of phenomena. Furthermore, existing research and methodologies do not provide sufficient evidence of the impact of social media on purchase intentions in the context of social influence theory. Henceforth, this phenomenon should be investigated and reasoned around using multiple accounts in order to add value to research. The inductive social constructionist methodology suggests that social influence on SNS should be understood based on multiple accounts to understand its impact on individual behaviors. For example, informational, economic, utilitarian and hedonic social interactions on SNS brand communities may develop distinctive levels of

social influence that inform purchase intentions. Gutiérrez-Cillán et al. (2017) studied user behavior on SNSs from a socio-political context (Varnali and Gorgulu, 2014; Knol et al., 2018). A subjective epistemology also explains the limitations of existing knowledge around the social influence literature, and suggests areas where the subjective outcomes of social influence can be used to determine the behavioural choices of customers from a marketing perspective. Using the constructionist approach, these actions collectively help marketers determine the development of the community's social characteristics, with a common social basis for purposive social action. For example the purpose of the interaction, and what happens when members interact online can be examined.

The constructivist paradigm also explains the intrinsic values that drive user motivations and provide a fundamental basis for heterogenic interactions on social media platforms such as brand communities. Such an axiological stance helps explain the subjectivity of social media behaviour, unveiling the key values (antecedents) which drive individuals' motivations to participate in SNS brand communities. Zhou (2017) identify the antecedents and value perceptions of the user behaviors in online communities. In their research they identified informational and emotional support as the strongest predictors of the willingness of users to participate in SNS communities. These subjective epistemological assumptions reveal the role of subjectivity in terms of such antecedents in marketing research, claiming that informational and emotional support hold explicit antecedent value towards predicting users' motivation and SNS behavior in brand communities (Okazaki et al., 2014). Regardless of the level of emotional support, a subjective epistemology ascertains the contextual value of informational support in terms of informational value as one of the strongest media fulfilment factors and antecedents behind the motivation of users to participate in brand groups and communities (Zaglia, 2013; Lu, 2018; Tsai and Men, 2013; Jin and Phua, 2014). Social media gratifications have been measured using the Users and Gratification paradigm (U&G) (Katz et al., 1974) and have been put to work by the majority of researchers to investigate the intentions of users of networking sites (Cheung and Lee, 2010; Okazaki, 2009). Such an epistemological stance about consumers' social media gratification resonates with the pragmatic belief that U&G not only motivates individuals to participate in SNS, but also creates value for them by influencing their purchase behaviours. Based on ontological reasoning, social media gratifications comprise of many

significant factors, which, based on epistemological and constructionist evidence, have the greatest influence on consumer choices and social influence when selecting media.

Social constructionism encompasses ontological properties and explains how user behaviours in SNSs brand communities promotes the subjective internalisation of values through multiple qualitative social experiences. For example individuals in SNS brand groups develop influence by internalising group values such as information sharing, socio emotional support and collaborative learning (Jin and Phua, 2014). Social constructionism, based on the lived experiences of individuals incorporating such values, impacts on changes of attitudes, behaviors, intentions and the formulation of reality (Schrader, 2015). Such ontological duality provides a fundamental basis for constructing a unique form of social influence which varies amongst online communities and supports the epistemological assumption that the construction of reality is subjective

This resonates with the constructivist belief that the symbolic experiences of individuals are certainly mediated on basis of heterogeneity of perspective social exchanges (Low, 1996). In his regard, the constructionism rejects the preconceptions about the social influence theory as a mere socio-psychological agent of behavioural change, stating that individuals' behavioural change is subjective and is exclusively associated with the nature of social interactions and size of the online social network. As explained by Dholakia et al. (2004) using a bigger online network can change the meanings of individuals social interactions would be different and so does outcome of the social influence. For example, (Okazaki, 2009) in their study identified the importance of individual social action as outcome of SNS based social interaction and a common factor in tailoring the behaviour of online users in order to enhance their buying intentions, and explained that individuals' self-concept and identity are dependent on the importance of the group or community they belong to and the relevance of such a group to an individual's life. Zaglia (2013) furthermore the contextual meaning of such concept in which the individuals make rational choices and comparisons on the SNS brand communities as a key driver of positive consumer brand relationship and self-esteem. Such in-group comparisons and rational choices favour a distinctive self-identity of a member within the brand group (Lu, 2018).

The constructionist attitude views knowledge as truth created by the interactions of individuals who create their own structures within society. It proceeds from the perspective of how we experience certain phenomena (Young and Collin, 2004). Such interpretist frameworks of analysis are also extremely helpful in inductive reasoning and analysis using phenomenological research analytics (Flanigan and Babchuk, 2015). The constructivist methodology is applied while accepting that the object of the study, or a particular phenomenon in society might not be the same as they appear. From a constructivist point of view, the social influence phenomenon is an object which is intended and constituted from multiple meaningful subjective perspectives by meaningful subjects (individuals) from a particular orientation in the social setting. This is where the interpretive methodology becomes useful to draw conclusions. Constructionism explicitly theorises that society is directed by widely held belief which subjectively impact on individual opinions and generate multiple beliefs and meanings of the metaphor. The different meanings are added to specific metaphors when meaningful activities about the consumer consumption of products and services. Knowledge about new products and services and the utility of such products and services are shared as knowledge with other individuals of society in the social group (Berger and Luckmann, 1967; Van Maanen, 1979). Such findings support the idea that utilitarian and hedonic interactive experiences, through heterogeneous social interactions on SNS brand groups add multiple meanings to social interactions in a marketing context. For example SNS users in brand communities establish pragmatic beliefs about social influence to develop eWOM as an agent of change in the mind-sets and behaviors of individuals. This means that user behaviour on social media platforms such as SNSs, apart from determining a desire and continued commitment to participate S can be applied within a marketing context to build a customer base by changing their purchase-related attitudes and intentions (Lu, 2018). Individual social interactions add multiple meaning when SNS user behavior is examined from the perspective of social influence theory. Furthermore, applying the inductive interpretist methodology can fill this gap that has been created by an objectivist approach to methodology.

Since social constructionism rejects positivist claims about the impact of social influence on user behaviors and intentions, it relies on scientific investigation to construct multiple facts arising from interpretist inquiries formulated by the researcher (Andrews, 2012). Social constructionism provides access to a radical qualitative scientific description of social

influence, considering it a product of individual actions and mutual interactions where every actor complies with the meaning of his social actions (Cheung and Lee, 2010). The intentional social action of members of an online social media community explains their intentional acts of mutual information sharing and relationship building, categorised as attributes of individuals' volitional control triggered by their goal-directed behaviour (Perugini and Bagozzi, 2001). These epistemological assumptions constitute the formal structure of individuals' social influence based on their intentionality and a notion of vital social action within the heart of interpretive sociology. Many researchers conclude that the construction of the social reality of the SNSs users in brand communities deepens their commitment to the brand leading to loyalty and raised purchase intentions (Bagozzi et al., 2006; Zhou, 2011; Zaglia, 2013; Lu, 2018).

The constructivist paradigm thus provides an appropriate methodological framework for the application of social influence meanings within socio-psychological cognate disciplines (Schrader, 2015). It advocates for a subjective and qualitative methodology which explains how social influence develops through consumers' heterogeneous consumer-brand interactions on social media. It explains how these can develop marketing related outcomes such as consumer purchase intentions. It contrasts with previous studies conducted using positivist, objectivist methodologies in socio-psychological disciplines which only explain the role of social media in the context of social influence theory to stimulate demand to use SNSs. Furthermore it enables marketers to gain a greater insight into how the social influence model could achieve greater content promotion by triggering a greater level of engagement and interactions amongst social media communities.

3.3. Research Methodology

3.3.1. Qualitative Research Methodology

Social constructionism involves an interpretive form of qualitative inquiry that leads the researcher to a scientific conclusion based on inductive field techniques such as interviews (Given, 2008). For example, the researcher interrogates the deeper meaning of a phenomenon, asking the research participants open-ended questions based on the applied interpretive framework of subjective constructionism (Creswell, 2013). Such qualitative inquiries in social constructionism frameworks investigate the development of social influence through heterogenic social interaction on SNS brand communities and draw out the deep meanings associated with the conferred actions of the social actors. Underpinning the research work with interpretist qualitative inquiry, the researcher sets the parameters of research to understand the impact of SNS brand communities on individual attitudes, intentions and behaviours, based on the intentionality of their social interactions. Since the meaning of every individual's acceptance of social influence is based on their conferred social actions and experiences, the researcher can draw multiple meanings of social influence from a variety of perspectives on the ontological grounds of constructionism (Schultheiss and Wallace, 2012). This further provides a radical scientific description of how social influence uniquely impacts on individual purchasing behaviours, based on the intentionality of online social information and knowledge-sharing.

Individual social influence is a result of qualitative, interactive experiences in SNS brand communities. The epistemological assumptions under the umbrella of social constructionism rely on a qualitative methodological construct to provide a deeper and more detailed examination of individuals' lived personal experience of heterogenic social interactions (Schrader, 2015). Social constructionism justifies a qualitative research design, based on a structured theoretical underpinning. To develop on this, the integration of phenomenology and social constructionism articulates a post-modern interpretist methodology which posits that the lived experience of social influence on individuals' behaviour and intentions has multiple meanings, and is subjective in nature compared to pre-existing literary preconceptions. Secondly, such an

approach considers the participants as sense-making organisms. Such an interpretive qualitative methodology allows the researcher to develop a proposition based on participants' individual experiences (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2009) that social influence gives rise to psychological changes in purchase behaviours. Lastly, rather than making a general assumption, a qualitative constructionist methodology underpins a detailed examination and study of the impact of social influence on each individual's purchase intentions, thereby providing a detailed explanation of social influence on the online social medium while studying consumers' purchase intentions.

Social constructions allows for a qualitative application of the applied interpretist framework which is based on asking social media users semi-structured and open-ended questions (McKenna et al., 2017). Such approaches enable a subjective construction of the multiple meanings of the intentions and impact of these intentions on social influence attitudes. This is achieved by allowing participants to describe their personal experiences freely (Creswell, 2013). On the other hand, this demonstrates the ideographic commitment of the researcher to investigate individual personal experiences, and to formulate a detailed conclusion based on the variety of individual experiences (Sengupta and Sahay, 2018). The interpretive nature of qualitative inquiry allows the researcher to derive more insight when interviewing respondents by employing empathy, curiosity and flexibility. This encourages participants to describe their personal experiences of certain phenomena in their lives within their natural settings. This helps the researcher connect the information 'dots' to better understand the behavioural modification impact of social influence on online social media (Creswell, 2013). Such a qualitative research methodology not only enables the researcher to recount in full their experience of every individual, but also leads him to draw a more specific and detailed conclusion about the applicability of social influence in particular social settings.

These qualitative investigations provide a unique line of inquiry into our experiential understanding of complex socio-psychological phenomena to reveal the complex inter-relationships between social influence phenomena and individuals' SNS based utilitarian and hedonic social interactions. The impact of such influences on behaviours is key (Müller et al., 2016). Such a methodology helps academic researchers as well as professional experts to carry

out a subjective analysis of empirical knowledge based on their theoretical preconceptions. These shape factual information about SNS interactions and consumer purchase intentions for commercial use through self-evaluation and personal reflection (Snelson, 2016). Creswell (2014) argued that qualitative research investigates the principles of subjective constructionism and phenomenological interpretism, thus enabling the application of the phenomena in the real world by involving strong empathetic engagement to qualitatively probe the more empirically interesting aspects associated with the phenomena. On a micro level, this approach facilitates an understanding of the lived experiences of participants in SNS brand communities using the principles of social influence theory. A qualitative methodology can also lead to a new understanding of abstract knowledge about how multiple heterogenic interactions lead to new theoretical additions (McKenna et al., 2017). In particular, the small sample size associated with qualitative interpretive analysis illuminates empirical clues grounding the socio-psychological impact of social media on behaviours and attitudes as a result of the close examination of the participants' lived experience and views (Crouch and McKenzie, 2006; Snelson, 2016; Dworkin, 2012).

3.3.2. Social media and Consumer Purchase Intentions in Qualitative Research

Qualitative research explains the nature of reality as the product of a constructionist process based on the researcher's intimate relationship between his/her intervention, the phenomenon under study and the situational constraints that shape the investigation (Creswell, 2013). It is approached as a value-laden inquiry, since the researcher dives deeper into an existing problem and uncovers significant trends in the thoughts, opinions and behaviours of individuals using social media (Blachnio et al., 2013). The researcher seeks answers to questions about the creation of a social phenomenon and the meanings associated with it, such as individual heterogenic SNS brand community-based interactions and the development of purchase intentions. This is achieved by investigating individual opinions and behaviours, considering these as information-rich and illuminative. In contrast, a quantitative methodology underpins the measurement and analysis of causal relationships and hypothesis/hypotheses among multiple variables. Such an approach however cannot investigate the social process (Snelson, 2016). Unlike quantitative methodologies which explicitly value the measurement of data and the

generation of explanation, qualitative methods provide a holistic understanding of the phenomenon under investigation, rejecting the positivist world view that numerical results are more significant than observations and spoken words (Creswell, 2014). Within social media research, quantitative research mostly involves the collection of numerical data types such as message counts, numbers of messages downloaded, numbers of posts, the level of participation, friend counts and online surveys (McKenna et al., 2017). Such quantitative methodologies chime with positivist beliefs and they underpin the linear and unidirectional sequence of research design whereby the researcher has pre-defined goals and research outcomes in mind. This contrasts with qualitative methodologies which involve researcher reflexivity to interpret human behaviour and real-life experiences such as interviewing social media users to provide a more realistic understanding of the lived world (Vaast and Levina, 2015). Creswell (2013) states that the process of reflexivity is triggered by the researcher him/herself through the identification of preconceptions in the study, which represent beliefs as to how a particular phenomenon exists in society, and how the reality of such a phenomenon can be constructed. These approaches form the social underpinning of research perspectives, motivations, qualifications and theoretical foundations.

In contrast with quantitative methods, whereby the researcher imparts pre-determined constraints to outcomes using numerical data and statistical inference, qualitative methods enable the researcher to study social influence in real-world situations as they unfold naturally. This is facilitated by non-manipulative and non-controlling analytics allowing the development of conclusions on the basis of whatever emerges from the investigation (Green et al., 2007). This differentiates quantitative from qualitative methods on the basis of the orientation of the analysis. In quantitative studies, greater priority is given to research outcomes based on the principles of “whats and ifs”, whereas in qualitative methods a deeper investigation is undertaken based on the principles of “hows and whys” to find meaning (Nelson, 2016). For example a qualitative study might look at how online social interactions develop social influence amongst social media consumers. Yilmaz (2013) stated that qualitative methods of study hold significantly more value over quantitative methods on the basis of three key factors: the naturalistic, emergent and purposeful elements. Naturalistic features confirm the investigation of a phenomenon in the real world on a non-manipulative and non-controlling basis. An example might be an investigation of

social consumer influence phenomenon. To achieve this, the researcher might accept multiple meanings in the form of whatever emerges from the investigation. Similarly, the emergent features confirm the flexibility of the design, ensuring openness, sensitivity, and responsiveness to accept situational change during the observation of the individual experiences. This can lead the researcher to new opportunities and new paths for discovering meanings. Finally, the third and most important element of the qualitative method is that it is purposeful, which explains that the sampling is aimed at individuals with insight into the phenomenon under investigation in order to achieve useful manifestations and a clear understanding of the social phenomenon. This contrasts with quantitative methods, where empirical generalisation of the sample is applied to the whole population (Muller et al., 2016).

Qualitative research design offers more intense engagement between the researcher and the individuals, situation and phenomenon under investigation. It carefully explores the contextual understanding of the multiple meanings of social influence, such as heterogenic social interactions, beliefs and the desire to connect with a social circle on social media (McKenna et al., 2017). Gay and Airasian (2000) argue that within applied research, qualitative research is methodologically more successful when the aim is to understand how a certain phenomenon could possibly influence a strategic goal. This is useful for solving such a specific problem. For example using a qualitative methodology to investigate a social influence phenomenon will not only provide a deeper understanding of the investigation but it will also enable the marketers to change the marketing strategy to encourage greater online interactions. The intense engagement of the researcher with the study helps produce richer and deeper data by responding to the situation, condition and needs of the participants. This impacts significantly on the generalisability of the findings to provide a theoretical understanding of the phenomenon. These findings could not be achieved using statistical and numerical inferences with quantitative methodology (Patton, 2002). In the context of quantitative methods, the researcher pre-designs statistical inferences which reduce the generalisability of results in terms of the validity of the research. This occurs on the basis of the anticipated and unanticipated threats to validity. However the generalisability of findings is less likely to be influenced as the researcher is attentive to situational dynamics and uses appropriate inferential techniques. The researcher also

follows a pattern wherever the investigation takes him to make generalisability more theoretical than statistical (Patton, 2002).

3.4. Research Strategy

3.4.1. Case Study Research

The diverse epistemological and interpretive roots of social constructionism imply multiple qualitative approaches such as case studies, which converge within the socio-psychological behavioural context. These explain the constructionist meanings of a specific phenomenon (Barratt et al., 2011). Qualitative methodologies are characterised by the constructionist and interpretist paradigm. Their aim is to subjectively investigate the development of multiple levels of social influence through the lens of heterogenic social interactions within SNS brand communities. This approach draws multiple meanings based on intentional social actions. These case-based investigations have been considered as the foremost interpretive research strategy used for qualitative investigations (Beverland and Lindgreen, 2010). Within the context of the practice-oriented fields of social-psychology, such as management or marketing, case-based research has been a valuable tool that espouses the investigation of subjective constructionism and epistemological assumptions within the interpretive paradigm. The interpretive phenomenological approach within the constructionist paradigm provides the fundamental basis for a scientifically pragmatic case-based qualitative investigation of the link between individual experiences on SNS brand communities and social influence. Scientific pragmatism espouses the significant link of the characteristics of case study research with an interpretive paradigm of research (Steenhuis, 2015). This helps to construe the detailed meaning and justification of subjective social influence as it impacts on individuals' purchase intentions. This case study research has been explained as a real-life detailed exploration and explanation of the multiple perspectives of complexity and the significance of a specific research phenomenon (Simons, 2009). Thus, based on epistemological and interpretive constructionist assumptions, case-based research comprehensively explains individual cases and present analyses of multi-dimensional social influence and the characterisation of features such as individual social action, the desire to

interact and social exchange. A similar view has been posed by Mills et al. (2010) who explained that case-based research is used in socio-psychological behavioural studies to understand individual and group-based activities in detail.

3.4.2. Social Media and Consumer Purchase Intentions in a Case Study

Case study research is one of the more popular research strategies within the multiple disciplines of online and industrial marketing due to the nature and ontology of the subject (Barratt et al., 2011). This is especially the case within the context of online consumer markets. Case-based research underpins the epistemological assumptions of the constructivist paradigm through analysing SNS brand community-based interactions and relationships. It provides the interpretive foreground for the development of social influence and its subjective impact on individual attitudes and behavioural change. Most importantly, case-based research enables an understanding of the ambiguities, inconsistencies and behavioural actions of members of online social media, making it the most appropriate methodological choice in qualitative empirical investigations (McKenna et al., 2017). It further enables subjective investigation and interpretation of the deeper meaning of social influence as a resultant phenomenon of individual social interaction. As a detailed contextual analysis of individual social interactions in SNS brand communities and their impact on individual purchase behaviors, case research leads to the application of an interpretive phenomenological analysis of individual experience. It illuminates the conditions of social interactions and suggests how such interactions change the prospective mind-set of online consumers.

One of the commonly accepted propositions about the epistemological perspective of social media and social influence knowledge are based on the concept of interpretive and pragmatic constructionism. This is a subjective matter of empirical observation and consensus. Case-based analysis explains the existence of reality within qualitative text based on the individual's experiences and interpretations (Mills et al., 2010). This leads to the conclusion that reality is a construct of online social influence, in addition to constructing its local and specific meaning in society. This perspective helps the researcher to overcome the empirical limitations imposed by quantitative methodological approaches by using case-based research to understand the holistic

view of social interactions on online media, and the subjective construction of behavioural and social propositions as they impact on individual actions. This perspective strengthens the constructivist stance in case-based research, which poses the question from a constructivist view that, apart from the construction of social meanings in online SNS community based social influence, where are the causes of social events and social interactions that lead to the development of the social influence phenomenon? To answer to this question, the ideologies of subjective constructionism and critical realism must be approached as mutually exclusive. Therefore, by recording and analysing the associated events of social actors, such as mutual participation, entertainment, collaborative learning, socio-emotional support and social informational exchange (UGC, Blogs and reviews) in SNS brand communities, a greater understanding of such socio-psychological phenomena as consumers' social influence can be obtained.

A case study as applied to this research can provide the contextual meaning of SNS and user behavior in online brand communities using social influence theory to analyse a particular industrial sector. Therefore it is important to provide a detailed description of the case starting with the research question (Patten, 2002). The research questions and sub questions reflect the aims and motivations of the investigation. The case study can thus explain how heterogenic SNS interactions shape the purchase intentions of consumers in response to three main research questions which are 1. What are the different purposes of consumer social media interactions, and how do these heterogeneous social media interactions develop multiple levels of social influence? 2. How do the multiple levels of social influence that are developed through heterogeneous social media interactions change consumer purchase intentions in the financial services industry? 3. In what ways the role of social media and its impact on consumer purchase intentions in online marketing strategies create a significant impact in financial services industry?

Having a unique research context helps clear the way to understanding how heterogeneous social media interactions in SNS brand communities influence consumer purchase behaviors. This knowledge can provide a guide to make a rational buying decision in relation to retail financial services in Pakistan. The financial industry of Pakistan is chosen because the retail financial

services industry has shown considerable growth in Asia (World Bank, 2017). The growth of the industry is accounted for by the fact that financial companies have gone global and have established their goodwill in the market (United Bank, 2018). The researcher's experience and affiliation with the industry shows that, even with tremendous growth in terms of sales and portfolio, social media marketing has not been considerably used in relationship marketing to promote two-way communication between users and companies in the industry. Although the multiple platforms of social media such as SNSs have been popular and extensively used as online interactions and social connectivity channels, such platforms are not being used for commercial purposes giving rise to the contextual nature of the research problem. As explained by Eisenhardt (2007) case studies lead the researcher to study phenomena in a specific context subjective to its existence. That phenomenon cannot be isolated and separated from its existence. Indeed, the existence of the phenomenon of investigation possesses objects which cannot be created artificially. Such experiences and association contribute to accession in the knowledge (Maxwell, 2013).

3.5 Sample Selection

The purpose of sampling is to maximise the efficiency and validity of the study, irrespective of whether the methodology is qualitative and quantitative (Robinson, 2014). From the perspective of qualitative methods, sampling must be consistent with the assumptions inherent in the research design (Patton, 2002). Sampling in qualitative methods is intended to obtain a depth of understanding to provide the foundations for the success or failure of the implementation of evidence-based strategies, rather than testing a hypothesis linked to an existing conceptual model, and giving more attention to the breadth of understanding and predictors of research implementation associated with quantitative methodologies (Coyne, 1997). Qualitative sampling involves the selection of a sample of individuals and groups who have significant knowledge and real-life experience of the research phenomenon under investigation (Luborsky and Rubinstein, 1995). To this end, a purposeful sampling technique is used in this study. This approach has been widely used in qualitative research to identify and select information-rich individuals, and groups of individuals in terms of the effective use of resources (Given, 2008). Within the social sciences, purposeful sampling has been considered as the most appropriate sampling technique for qualitative methodologies aiming to achieve an in-depth understanding of a social

phenomenon while applying constructivism (Sandelowski, 1995). Patton (2002) states that purposeful sampling is not only used to select information-rich, knowledgeable and experienced individuals but to select a sample of individuals who can communicate, articulate and express their lived experiences in a reflective manner. Compared to the type of probabilistic random sampling which intends to ensure the researcher's control over the outcome(s) by testing pre-determined assumptions and the generalisability of the findings, purposeful sampling enables the researcher to explore a social phenomenon in depth to provide an applied understanding using existing theories that reveals how a particular phenomenon works in real life (Sandelowski, 2000; Coyne, 1997) Using purposeful sampling, the participants of the study have been selected on the basis of two important factors. Firstly, participants had to be financial services customers and had to be active members of financial services SNS communities. They had to have experienced the consumption and co-creation of information and promotional content in relation to financial services. Secondly, they had to be industrial professionals who are not only customers, but are also engaged in promotional communications and social media marketing management.

The selection of participants on such grounds was undertaken to explore and investigate their lived experiences of SNS interactions in brand communities to understand how these utilitarian and hedonic social interactions influenced their consumption and purchase behaviours. Additionally the participants had to have not only consumed and co-created marketer-generated and consumer-generated content, but had to also have promoted brand awareness about financial services brands in SNS communities and groups. As argued by Lu (2018) consumer experiences of heterogenic social interactions on SNS brand communities enable marketers to better understand consumer engagement and social influence phenomena to support online behavioural modelling.

3.5.1. Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted before the interview and focus group data collection practices went 'live' to check whether the questions were clear and to ensure they conveyed clear meaning which fulfilled the purpose of the research. The pilot test confirmed that there was no research

bias involved in data collection. As argued by (Given, 2008) pilot testing is an indicator of possible methodological errors while interviewing respondents. It helps the researcher to overcome such issues beforehand. Using a similar sampling technique, three participants were interviewed, and their responses were recorded. Minor changes were made to the interview questions and recording process after the pilot study, however the respondents appeared comfortable with the questions and no major issues were highlighted.

3.5.2. Data Collection and Sample Size

The current study incorporates reflexive inquiry into the research methodology. Using this approach, the researcher involves him/herself in the methodology by intrinsically linking with the participants who are expressing their views and experiences about the topic using semi-structured and focus group data collection methods. Such a form of reflexive inquiry is similar to critical ethnography approaches to social influence. The latter approach holds that individual social groups, and social interactions within SNS brand communities and groups, are categorised as heterogeneous, and distinct in nature (Lu, 2018). They cannot be unified or static, and they therefore explicitly contribute to the knowledge gained (Tsai and Men, 2013). Critical ethnography can be applied to a value-laden methodology by arguing the fact that the modification and creation of knowledge is mutually exclusive to the values of humans, and social communities (Denzin et al., 2016). This consequently strengthens the interconnectedness between social influence and individual social action by helping the researchers to uncover patterns of realities of individual behaviour on SNSs, and it implies that interpretive and recursive methods of qualitative data collection can help develop insights into the symbolic meanings of the real-life experiences of individuals. Methods like semi-structured interviews and focus groups are useful to unfold the hidden meaning inside individual experiences by observing and recording experiences, activities and expressions during interviews in audio or video format (Tong et al., 2007; Liamputtong, 2009). Such methods were used in this study thus to record participants' beliefs and attitudes regarding how social influence impacts socio-psychological behaviour and the attitudes of individuals in the real world. There are implications for purchase intentions in the retail financial services industry. Establishing facts through for example transcribing recorded conversations and interviews can uncover the broader meaning

of the context of social influence. This can help to explain diversity in behaviour and can view online social interactions as significantly associated with social influence.

The semi-structured interviews and focus groups are recursive data collection processes that enable the researcher to categorise to draw patterns out of participant attitudes, interactions, social beliefs, behaviours, and social practices (Dicicco-Bloom and Crabtree, 2006; Hennik et al., 2010). This enables the researcher to extract meaning in relation to how individuals, in particular in their online social settings, experience their social world. The current study involved 30 semi-structured interviews and two focus group interviews with financial services customers and corporate employees. Focus group interviews were conducted in the presence of groups of 8 employees of the company as a process of triangulation to ensure the validity of the evidence. This was achieved through the implementation of a systematic process of searching the data for facts and confirming or rejecting evidence relating to individual online heterogenic social behavioural interactions.

3.5.2.1 Sample Size

Sandelowski (1995) explained that there are no established rules for qualitative sample sizes because the sample size is based on what the researcher knows, what the purpose of the research is, and the associated usefulness and credibility of the project. Brymann and Bell (2007) suggest that, usually in qualitative research the emphasis is on small-scale data compared to large-scale numerical data of the type seen in quantitative methodologies. Usually, using qualitative research methodologies, the sample size is primarily based on saturation (Saunders et al., 2018), i.e. continuing to sample individuals to achieve a comprehensive understanding about the phenomenon continues until the researcher no longer acquires new and substantive information (Charmaz, 2011). Therefore it is impossible to determine the final numbers of a sample beforehand. Qualitative interviews must proceed until saturation is reached, and this is the point when new theoretical insights or patterns associated with the phenomenon of the study are no longer revealed (Saunders and Townsed, 2016). Previous research (Dworkin, 2012; Charmaz, 2006; Morse, 1995; Morse et al., 2002) argues that, in most studies, a sample of between 25-30 in-depth interviews is appropriate. However the researcher must proceed if he observes that the

lived experiences of individuals reveal multi-dimensional insight into the phenomenon under investigation (Charmaz, 2006).

3.5.3. Semi-Structured Interviews

The interview format used to obtain the responses of respondents was semi-structured interviews. These were used due to their methodological superiority over structured and formal interviews in qualitative studies (Adams, 2010). Semi structured interviews enhance the researchers' ability to understand and contextualise the meaning of phenomena as an investigator. The phenomenon is this approached from the participant's point of view, and this allows the researcher to adjust questions or ask sub-questions over the course of the interview to gain a detailed understanding of the phenomenon (Hong and Ilardi, 2010). It is also useful to support the open-ended questions with follow up queries (Adams, 2010). For the purpose of interviews, a consent form and invitation to participate in the study was sent to the participants in advance of meeting each of them. Upon obtaining their consent, the venue of the interview was decided on basis of convenience to the participant (Mueller and Segal, 2015). During the interviews the responses of participants were recorded on a device for data transcription and analysis purposes. Furthermore verbal and non-verbal clues were also noted by the researcher by observing the body language of respondents during interviews. This enhanced the quality of the discussion and maximised the value of the data (McIntosh, 2015). Each of the semi structured interviews lasted 35-40 minutes which is considered appropriate for conducting semi-structured interviews (Adams, 2010).

3.5.4. Focus Groups

Within the study two focus group interviews were also conducted. The researcher assembled a group of nine participants to discuss their complex personal experiences, their perceptions and their beliefs and attitudes about the phenomenon. This was achieved through moderate discussion (O.Nyumba et al., 2018). Focus groups are considered to be cost effective qualitative data collective techniques in which the researcher adopts the role of facilitator or moderator and

adjunct responder (Ozuem, 2004). This contrasts with semi-structured interviews where discussion occurs between the participants and the researcher (Kitzinger 1995). Focus groups are considered a valuable technique where semi-structured interviews cannot provide enough information about the dynamic view of group-based discussion around the phenomenon (Krueger, 1994). Each focus group contained eight participants selected through purposive sampling (Morgan, 1988). The number of participants in each focus groups ranged between 4 and 12 and this is considered generally accepted practice when conducting a focus groups session (Kitzinger, 1995; Krueger and Casey, 2009). Based on the research objectives, a list of questions were prepared for each focus group discussion session (O.Nyumba et al., 2018). The participants of each focus group shared similar characteristics in terms of age, gender and professional background.

The focus group sessions were conducted in the company's regional offices as this location was convenient for the participants who worked within these premises. Furthermore each focus group lasted for about 50-55 minutes, which is considered widely acceptable practice. Although the participants of the focus groups shared the same characteristics, they held different opinions and beliefs about SNSs interactions in brand communities and their tentative influence on individual behaviours. This justifies the adoption of focus group discussion data collection using social constructionism, as researchers may practically come across and understand the different meaning and perceptions of the phenomenon of the study from different points of view (Ozuem, 2004). As with the semi-structure interviews, each focus group discussion was recorded on a voice recorder, and non-verbal cues such as body displacements, postures, gaps in speech, silence and hesitation were noted to add value to the analysis (Gorden, 1980)

3.6. Limitations of the Methodology Applied

Though the inductive research methods were used to investigate the phenomenon in depth, a number of limitations must be identified. For example, qualitative inquiry explicitly depends on the researcher's association with the investigation, which sometimes leads to researcher bias. Usually, using a qualitative methodology two types of research errors can arise during the investigation i.e. participant bias and researcher bias. Participant bias is connected to responses

to questions asked during interviews. Participant bias occurs when the respondent answers a certain question in the interview on the basis of what he/she considers right or socially acceptable, rather than what he/she feels. Such bias could compromise the validity of the data. Secondly researcher bias is an error concerned with the researcher's involvement in the research process that may arise during the data collection or data analysis process. The qualitative research methodology applied provides in depth answers to the research questions. However, such a methodology could make the researcher more fallible which could impact on the validity of the research methods in multiple ways. Firstly, research bias that may arise on the basis of sampling times, place, respondents and questions. Secondly, research validity may be compromised on the basis of the personal qualities of the researcher, such as their concentration, patience, tolerance, ambiguity and certainty. Third, the researcher's affinity with a specific group of people in terms of sampling, research design, theories and concepts is a consideration. Finally the ability of the researcher to conduct the research process in terms of knowledge, skills, and methodological strength has to be considered. Such limitations could impact the accuracy and reliability of the qualitative research methods used in the investigations..

3.7. Research Ethics

The study was conducted in fulfilment of the ethical standards of research set by the University of the West of Scotland. Before conducting the research, the researcher gained permission from the university. The researcher also made a list of the participants of the study participating in the semi-structured interviews, focus group discussions along with the venue of such interviews and focus groups. The participants' invitation letter and consent form were also approved by the university. Upon approval of the ethics committee of the university the research work proceeded. The recordings of interviews and focus group discussions were destroyed once the transcription of data was completed. Furthermore this work is a sole contribution of the researcher and is free from plagiarism and copy right issues.

Chapter 4: Analysis of Factual Evidence

4.1. Introduction

The methodology explained the role of the social constructionism paradigm and constructivist epistemology in understanding the multiple meanings of the social influence phenomenon. Furthermore, the methodology also justified the adoption of qualitative data collection techniques such as semi-structured interviews and focus group interviews for conducting case-based research. The adoption of an inductive qualitative methodology has also been supported by the social constructionism paradigm. This chapter explains the interpretation of the interview-based qualitative responses of retail financial services customers in Pakistan. Social constructionism supported the inductive qualitative methods for data analysis. For this study, six major themes were identified in the light of existing literature and data, which significantly explain the role of online social media in developing consumers' purchase intentions. The patterns and themes identified in the research add explicit quality to the study and explain how consumer purchase intentions are developed through individual online social interactions upon accepting one of three different levels of social influence on SNSs .

4.2. Rationale of Thematic Analysis

Within the framework of complex and diverse qualitative data analysis approaches, thematic analysis is considered an explicit and foundational method for data analysis (Holloway and Todres, 2003). Thematic analysis is a form of inductive analysis to interpret semi-structured interview-based qualitative data. As explained by (Ozuem et al., 2008) the constructionism paradigm of research supports a constructivist epistemology. Inductive thematic analysis is considered appropriate for data analysis and interpretation since it enables the researcher to move back and forth between the literature and data using multiple iterations for identifying themes and patterns. Not focusing on motivations involves inductive analysis and interpretations with a focus on themes within data sets that explain the socio-cultural meaning of phenomena (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Moreover, inductive thematic analysis is a data-driven approach that supports the direct involvement of researchers through inductive data collection methods, such as semi-

structured interviews in order to achieve the experiential and information-rich data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; King, 2004).

Thematic analysis is a process of the identification of themes and analysis of the patterned responses or data themes which exist within qualitative data sets (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Nowell et al., 2017). Thematic analysis helps report the themes and describes the entire set of data in meaningful detail. A theme is an extract of data in the form of a pattern that captures the important information related to the research question (Green et al., 2017). "Themes are abstract (and often fuzzy) constructs the investigators identifies before, during, and after analysis" (Ryan and Bernard, 2000 p.780). The significance of the theme explains the valuable and important information within the data extract, and it is not essentially dependent on quantifiable measures. Thematic analysis involves the researchers' constant interpretation of data by moving back and forth in each data set to extract the codes within a theme and to analyse codes in relation to prospective themes (Fereday and Muir-Cochrane, 2006). Thematic analysis provides a rich and detailed understanding of data sets on the basis of theoretical freedom, making it a flexible and useful qualitative data analytical tool in qualitative research (Jones et al., 2011).

The key benefit of thematic analysis is flexibility of analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Flexibility in this case refers to the frequency of occurrence of a theme within a data set. The themes identified within the data are strongly connected to the data and may hold little connection with the interview questions. Within thematic analysis, there is no hard and fast rule for the occurrence of a theme as it is not necessary that a certain proportion of data should display evidence of the existence of a theme (Nowell et al., 2017). For example, it is not the case that a certain data pattern is considered as a theme if it exists in 50 per cent of the data, and another pattern will not be considered as a theme if it is found in 47 per cent of the same data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). However, more importance for the existence of a theme is given to the information-rich data patterns that significantly explain in greater detail the research question under investigation (King, 2004).

Since the research epistemology provides the foundation for thematic analysis, the level of analysis could yield different results (Holloway and Todres, 2003). In the current study, the

philosophical foundations of the qualitative study support the use of thematic analysis to interpret interview-based qualitative data. The transcription of data was carried out upon completion of each interview. Data transcription was carried out manually and by using Nvivo software to ensure that the most important and significant patterns of data were identified. As stated by Kelle (2004), the identification and coding of data patterns in thematic analysis can be done by the researcher himself, instead of using software. For this purpose several iterations were needed to identify and refine the central themes among the thirty transcribed interviews and two focus groups. Also in the data transcription process every respondent was assigned a unique reference number such as R1, R2 etc. [*Sic*] has been used to indicate the incorrect, meaningless statements and grammatical mistakes which were intentionally left out in the interview data. Since the themes were identified using multiple iterations within data sets and literature, the existing literature also supports the explanation and existence of themes and concepts that are identified in the data. Finally, to form a coherent and consistent interpretation of the data, six major themes were identified in the data sets. The six major themes are consumer media fulfilment, social complaisance, value incorporation, self-fulfilment, online verbal evidence, and buying intentions.

Themes	Definitions	Codes	Keywords
Consumer's Media Fulfilment	<p>Consumers' media fulfilment is the gratification value that consumers get by choosing the social media as the channel of interaction. This includes enlightenment value, informational acquisition, guidance, networking and support.</p>	<p>Enlightenment Value</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Interactive Content ▪ Blogs ▪ Knowledge ▪ Reliable information ▪ Extensively shared likes and re-posts ▪ Top rated ▪ User reviews opinions ▪ Personal experiences ▪ Pros and cons ▪ Problem solving ▪ Awareness ▪ Search ▪ Cost benefit analysis ▪ Value of money ▪ Discounts ▪ Offers and promotions ▪ Blogs ▪ Engagement
		<p>Networking</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Speedy exchange ▪ Collaborative learning ▪ Interactive ▪ Status ▪ Social Interaction ▪ Gratification ▪ Need recognition ▪ Entertainment

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Adaptability ▪ Socialisation ▪ Transformation ▪ Change ▪ Heterogeneity ▪ Diversity ▪ Popularity ▪ Access ▪ Influence ▪ Perception ▪ Group discussion ▪ Professional ▪ B2C communication
		Customer Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Technical help ▪ Responsiveness ▪ Quick fixing of problems ▪ Guidance ▪ Explanation ▪ Empathy ▪ Financial advice and expertise ▪ Convincing ▪ Communication ▪ Variety ▪ Benefits of purchasing ▪ Accurate facts and figures ▪ Efficient complaint handling ▪ Stimulating ▪ Regularly posting new information and updates ▪ Encouraging members to ask questions ▪ Online polls

Social Complaisance	The level of social influence that explains the change in the individuals' attitudes, beliefs, opinions and intentions in which individuals during social interaction comply with the beliefs and choices of the existing majority, comply for the sake of reward and avoiding punishment, or comply due to willingness and wish to be part of the group.	Concurrence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Most purchased ▪ Trend following ▪ Willingness to experience the same ▪ Majority opinion ▪ Top rated
		Reward Anticipation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Bonus on offers ▪ Special rates for returning customers ▪ Reward-based purchase ▪ Financial support in everyday spending ▪ Rewards for constructive group activity
		Wish To Fit In	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Wish to contribute ▪ Support for group expansion ▪ Social education and information ▪ Global online social platform ▪ Benefit for benefit ▪ All my family and friends bank with them ▪ Global brand ▪ I don't want to switch ▪ Trust ▪ Sustainable improvement

Value Incorporation	<p>The level of social influence that explains the long-term rational change in attitudes, beliefs, opinions and intentions on the basis of internalising the social values such as informational conformity and adoption, reasonability, self-reasoning, social collaboration and cooperation for making rational buying decisions.</p>	Informational Conformity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Self-guide ▪ Better decision-making ▪ Change ▪ Pros and cons ▪ New ideas and information ▪ Guidance ▪ Standing with facts rather than the majority ▪ Accurate content ▪ Self-reasoning ▪ Meaningful Insight ▪ Connection ▪ Planning ▪ Risk assessment ▪ Establishing facts
		Social Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ongoing interaction ▪ Active participation ▪ Help ▪ Accommodation ▪ Solution ▪ Inter-dependence ▪ Congruence ▪ Values ▪ Agreement ▪ Flexibility ▪ Strength ▪ Intention ▪ Specific ▪ Goal ▪ Cooperation ▪ Consensus ▪ Decision ▪ Help in unclear

Self-Fulfilment			situations
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Knowledge ▪ Logic ▪ Clarity ▪ Attitude ▪ Belief ▪ Confidence ▪ Ability to interpret information ▪ Improved choice ▪ Strong group membership ▪ Rational mindset ▪ Verifying the experiences of other members ▪ Preference ▪ Opinion ▪ Informational evidence
		Self-worth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Recognition ▪ Importance ▪ Standard ▪ Impact ▪ Point of attention ▪ Buying the best in the market ▪ Huge group following
		Involvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Brand promoter ▪ Group expansion ▪ Content creation ▪ Engagement ▪ Contribution ▪ Invitation ▪ Informational help ▪ Building Brand trust

This is explained as the aspects of the individuals, identification within the group in terms of their self-worth, self-esteem, involvement and belongingness and unique representation within the group.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Willingness ▪ Group testimony
Online Verbal Evidence	<p>Online verbal evidence is explained as the positive or negative statements, reviews, recommendations and beliefs about the products or services generated by the actual or formal customers and socially made available to multitudes of people and businesses on social media platforms such as SNSs.</p>	Trustworthiness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reliability ▪ Quality ▪ Accuracy ▪ Benefit ▪ Secure ▪ Help ▪ Dependable ▪ Satisfaction
		Authenticity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Top rating ▪ Top shared ▪ Positive and negative Reviews ▪ Blogs ▪ Recommendation ▪ Personal experience ▪ Likes ▪ Discussion ▪ Online customer service
		Satisfaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fulfilment ▪ Value ▪ Expectation ▪ Utility ▪ Affordability ▪ Peace of mind ▪ Positive experience
		Approval	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Trend ▪ Favour ▪ Interpersonal influence ▪ Most comments, shares and likes ▪ Persuasive content ▪ Interactive promotion

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Most followed thread ▪ Admired ▪ Practical ▪ Recognition ▪ Reputation
Buying intention	Buying Intention is explained as the situation where a consumer develops a desire or intends to make a purchase of certain products or services with certain underlying conditions such as a change in perception, attitude, belief and behaviour based on the product or service quality, utility and value.	Intention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Change of mind ▪ Willingness ▪ Satisfactory feelings ▪ Desire ▪ Righteous decision
		Influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Persuasion ▪ Quality ▪ Suggestion ▪ Agreement ▪ Exchange ▪ Attitude ▪ Belief ▪ Family's choice
		Decision	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conclusion ▪ Commitment ▪ Benefit ▪ Information evaluation ▪ Chance ▪ Solution ▪ Best seller ▪ Choice ▪ Customer service ▪ Conformity ▪ Wider picture ▪ Logic ▪ Deep insight ▪ Risk and benefit analysis ▪ Facilitation

Table 3: Thematic Analysis

4.3. Major Themes Reflecting Antecedents of Social Media Use

4.3.1. Consumers' Media Fulfilment

Consumers' media fulfilment denotes individuals' perceptions of value from the social media that satisfy their specific needs and lead to ultimate gratification. Quan-Haase and Young (2010) in their research argued that social media gratification is the explicit reason online users choose social media to fulfil their media consumption needs, where the most important gratification factors are connectivity, interactive informational content and active participation in content creation at an individual or group level, especially on SNSs . Within the social media gratification theme three sub-themes have been identified which play a significant role in social media fulfilment. These sub-themes are enlightenment value, networking and customer support.

Enlightenment value is the value derived from sharing information on social media. This creates engagement with informational content and changes the perceptions, attitudes and beliefs of those that use social media. Informational value is the benefit that online members receive from belonging to an online social networking group and using that information to create a difference in their lives (Nam and Kannan, 2014; Colicev et al., 2018). As is particularly on the case with Facebook, the information shared within groups about financial services brands creates brand trust worthiness, and satisfaction with the information on financial services. Further, the 'informational value' theme also serves as a determining factor and antecedent towards customer value perceptions in the process of developing social influence.

One of the significant characteristics of enlightenment value is informational credibility. This holds that the members of an online social group consider that the information shared and exchanged amongst group members holds explicit reliability and trustworthiness, and creates awareness and know-how that supports purchase decisions (Nam and Kannan, 2014). The data confirms the members' trust in the validity of the information posted in the group which helps them to make a rational purchase decision.

This was been explained by the respondent R1 in the following way:

“Well! There is no doubt that the social media is changing the world and giving more insights [sic] and knowledge about the products and services we use in everyday life. This online group is operated by the bank itself so there is 100 per cent credibility and truth in the information they bring in [sic] the group. Obviously when you see [sic] certain piece of information or a post is extensively shared, liked and commented it gives you the reason to believe that the information is valid. Also that when you read the online reviews, ratings and personal experiences about the utility and use of the financial services you believe in it.”

This respondent confirms that the information which is shared and endorsed within the group holds originality and accuracy. The information in the brand’s social media group emerges in multiple ways, such as via reading posts, comments, product and service reviews and ratings. Furthermore, the respondent confirmed how the credibility of the information shared in the group created value and helped him make a rational purchase decision. Nam et al. (2017) in their research argued that user-generated media content has enabled online members to develop trust and that social informational interactions and knowledge exchange change the perceptions of online members, transforming them into potential customers.

Similarly, social media plays a significant role in knowledge exchange and informational interaction among the online members of social groups to create awareness and greater insight (Zhu and Chen, 2015). For example, SNSs such as Facebook serve as search engines to find information on financial services, and they stimulate increased knowledge amongst online members. The information shared in the form of blogs, reviews, discussions and personal experiences communicate essential knowledge about various pros and cons, value for money, know-how, discounts, offers and the associated benefits of financial services. The interviewee R5 noted:

“There is no doubt that social media is more popular than the conventional mode [sic] of information communication because it is quick and effective. You could [sic] ask any question any time as a proper section for this to enhance the knowledge gain about financial services offered starting from account overdraft to capital borrowing for business is available that supports the buying decisions [sic]. With every bit of information shared and posted in this group

very often detailed insight of utility, practicality such as cost benefit, associated benefits of purchase and expected returns of the purchase is shared sometimes by the members and most of the time by the written articles and blogs reviews by the online customers service members.”

This respondent confirms that social media plays a strong and significant role in knowledge exchange amongst members engaged in group-based interactions. The respondent also suggests that purchase intentions are the outcome of knowledge exchange in the group. These are motivated via social interactions and group discussion amongst members. They are also motivated by the knowledge exchanged between the company’s online customer services staff and site members. Lim and Heide (2015) in their research argued that social media has emerged as a potential source of information where such information is created, circulated and discussed and where it fills knowledge gaps about brand related services and issues amongst communities (Azemi et al., 2019).

Furthermore, the enlightenment value of the user-generated social media platforms such as SNS is associated with interactive promotional content containing information about bonuses, offers, rewards and value-for-money in financial services. This is communicated by the company within a Facebook group. Iankova et al. (2018) argue that advertisements and promotional content in Web 2.0 based social media settings enhance member engagement through interactions and the exchange of UGC. These subsequently add value to the consumers’ perceptions and loyalty.

The respondent R2 noted:

“Social media is [sic] a huge influence for the online members when it comes to promotions, advertisement and educating the online society. It cant [sic] be wrong to say that the group is very active and every now and then some new information about new financial services is posted containing interactive and interesting content about the promotions, bonuses and rewards and lucrative offers that holds [sic] certain value to everyone. It’s like every time when you login to Facebook you see thousands of likes, comments and shares of interactive content in the form of Web links, surveys or informational videos in your profile newsfeed. I put my case here that I am

a genuine foodie and there is a 20 per cent discount for Mastercard holders when they visit Pizza Hut. So here we go. Haha.”

This respondent confidently approves of the informational value associated with the UGC. He is persuaded that extensive group interactions can help to create awareness. In addition, the informational and promotional content influences a rational change of perceptions amongst group members, increasing satisfaction levels with purchases and driving their motivation to become loyal customers Helal and Ozuem (2017) in their research note that interactive and informative UGC facilitates consumer-to-consumer and consumer-to-marketer communication which further influences the consumers' mindset and perceptions, subsequently driving purchase intentions.

Online Customer Support

One of the features of user-generated media is direct company involvement in facilitating discussion amongst online users to transform them into potential customers. Compared to the traditional virtual communities, social media platforms such as SNSs offer customer support services to their online group members to enhance their group interaction and engagement with content, to educate them about products and services and to support information-based change in their attitudes and intentions. Felix et al. (2017) argue that one of the explicit reasons for social media dominance is direct organisational interactions with potential customers, supporting their informational needs by encouraging them to interact with content and ask questions. In this way companies can ascertain their problems and ensure technical support and solutions to problems are provided.

The respondent R7 highlighted this phenomenon in the following way:

“This social media group is very active, supportive and in fact you get more [sic] a quick response to any problem or information you need. Interestingly there is a 24/7 customer service where I can easily get information or detail [sic] of any financial services that [sic] I am interested in. An important part is that they support your query and provide a solution which

practically works in reality. I remember when I had a problem with mobile app registration I asked about the problem in this group and they replied to me in detail on how I can [sic] fix it, which I think is way better than asking the same by going to the bank branch or asking on a phone call.”

This respondent respects the supportive role of the group admin , and the efficiency of the customer support services when it comes to solving problems for group members. The respondent mentioned that the responsiveness of customer service and its tenacity have established credibility in terms of complaint handling and this provides solutions for technical problems, which subsequently contributes to membership strength within the group.

Another respondent R12 reflected on SNSs customer support services as follows:

“You won’t see very often in other social media groups that admin replies to hundreds of questions asked every day.”

Clearly, customer support enhances the interaction between online users and companies, and enhances their association with the brand by solving their problems. Previous research (Arrigo’s, 2014; Ozuem et al., 2017) argued that customer services create fulfilment in customers by answering their questions and offering information about products and services as a solution upon identifying their needs.

Customer support entails a variety of dynamic communications that stimulate change in consumer beliefs and attitudes. Such services provide support to make a rational decision (Sparks et al., 2013). The members of the online group are presented with accurate facts and figures about financial services such as life insurance, mortgages and car finance, and admin creates greater awareness amongst the group members enabling them to make rational purchase decisions.

The respondent R7 explained this phenomenon as follows:

“Certainly [sic] good thing about this group is that apart from learning and getting information from the social interaction in the form of discussion or reading the content you also get the specific information you are after. The people managing this online group work more than a customer service, I must appreciate. They explain every bit of information on any sort of issue being raised to them apart of [sic] sharing the informative content and discussing the practical things that affects [sic] decisions like affordability, expenses and so on, which I found very helpful and satisfactory. I mean you won’t expect such variety on a social media group sometimes even when you call the customer services and ask them about, let’s say, car finance. They won’t give the answer you are looking for; in fact sometimes they behave a bit rudely.”

This respondent agrees with the fact that the group customer support team is skilful and provides appropriate answers to problems when asked. The respondent further explains that customer service is empathetic, since whatever financial services they suggest are subject to the current financial stability of the inquirer. A similar view was presented by Davis et al. (2012) in their research. They stated that, rather than flooding customers with information, customer services listen to what they are saying and show empathy. Such variety in dynamic communications plays a determining role in changing the mind-sets of individuals with information to transform them into potential customers.

Since group-based social interaction helps online members to generate information and facilitate learning about the use of financial services, the role of the group admin and customer support team further cushions this process. The admin and support team in the online group retain the attention of members with regularly updated information, announcements and group polls. The posts, regular reviews and analysis and personal experiences encourage the members with greater knowledge-based intimacy within the group.

One respondent R15 who is a marketing operations manager in a banking company explained:

“Well, nowadays things have become very competitive and only facilitating the customers in every possible way can let you stay in the game. We are global company now and educating the

customers is necessary because most of the time people don't know the exact need they have and helping them to reach a correct decision is what customer service is about. We manage our own social media Facebook group unlike most other brands because posting informational bits and content support [sic] the rational decision-making. Since in the online medium social media is an extensively popular source of information and education compared to websites we put greater effort in [sic] publishing content, rating our services through creating polls and regularly educating our online group members so that more and more people can interact and trust our brand."

This respondent views the role of customer support as having a hand in educating members of online social media groups to support rational decision-making. The respondent also explains that helping group members to create greater awareness has multiple benefits for consumers from the company's perspective, as it builds greater trust in the brand and enables the company to achieve its global vision by adopting a customer-centric approach. Empirical research supports the fact that, with the use of social media, companies can educate and inform their customers with greater ease and reach out to a wide audience as a strategic marketing function (Felix et al., 2017; Arrigo, 2014; Ansarin and Ozuem, 2014).

Networking

Networking is explained as the benefit of using SNSs to stay connected for maintaining contact and support with friends, family peers and co-workers. Networking facilitates the diffusion of information through social interaction and accelerates change in individuals' beliefs and value systems. Such change is described by (Dholakia et al., 2004) as 'social action'. The SNSs, and especially Facebook, are an explicit platform for socialisation and gratify members with interactive features like speedy exchange, responsiveness, social learning and entertainment, which subsequently lead to the transformation of the perception and values of the online members. Within the sub-theme of networking the communication between the individual and his/her social circle leads to collaborative learning, speedy exchange, media gratification and the adaptability of the social media. The research of (Endress, 2014) found that user-generated media stimulates communication and interactivity by using multiple features such as messages,

picture sharing and tagging, which leads to greater intimacy, interdependence and changes of perception.

The respondent R9 explained this phenomenon as:

“Social media is extremely popular in people of all age ranges. I mean you see them spending most of their time using mobiles and interacting on social media, updating their status, learning new things or doing something else to keep themselves busy. It has become [sic] the prominent platform to stay connected with friends, family members, peers, co-workers and class fellows as you not just interact with them but also [sic] follow their likings and interaction patterns as well. I believe that connecting on social media bring [sic] change in your choices and decisions. For example, I have joined a few groups of renowned brands and engage myself in group chat and comment very often as my friends and co-workers are doing so.”

The respondent is confirming that the benefits of networking and interacting activities on social media lead them change their perception and engage with certain groups and participate in them. The respondent also explained that apart from the communication and connectivity they keep an eye on the interaction patterns of their friends and family and engage with certain brand communities or groups on Facebook. This shows that interpersonal connectivity and communication lead to joining groups, which initiates the social influencing process. Mitic and Kapoulas (2012) argued that the interpersonal communication and connectivity within a social network triggers learning and facilitation through greater engagement with informational and UGC in the form of comments, likes, posts and group discussions.

The global network of social media explains its diversity, reach and heterogenic scale which enable participants from all parts of the world to interact and exchange information in a quick and convenient way. The great usability of the globally wide user-generated media has enabled two-way communication and the transforming of perceptions with a powerful impact on everyday lives. Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) stated that Web 2.0 based social media has increased its boundaries and has enabled the geographically diverse population to interact on basis of heterogeneous social interaction.

The respondent R11 explained this phenomenon as follows:

“Well, social media is a global network and people from all over the world can connect and share their ideas, thoughts, and learn from each other. It keeps us updated about what is happening in different parts of the world in such [sic] a way that facilitates us to communicate with the people and learn new things about the people, politics, business, sports and about [sic] different cultures to increase our knowledge. Most importantly the global brands selling goods and services have their groups in the social media keeping us updated about what coming and what is in the trend, and related informative content is a good way to update yourself. I think it’s the same case with everyone that you would like to interact with and it’s part of the global brand group on Facebook which has more than [sic] million members and is consistently growing, as obviously something important and valuable is there for us.”

The respondent acknowledges the importance of a globally wide network facilitating interpersonal connectivity. As a global network, social media is a source of gratification for people from different parts of the world, and it enables them to engage through heterogeneous interactions. Furthermore, globally recognised brands attract the attention of individuals on social media on two bases: firstly because of the huge membership size, giving an impression of something valuable to online members and secondly, these groups interact with other members by publishing informative content about the latest trends and new products, and service-related information. Similar views have been expressed by Holsapple et al. (2018) who stated that Web 2.0 is geographically diverse, and the heterogeneous nature of social media has enhanced online individual dependence and interdependence on informational accomplishment. This has shown more growth compared to Web 1.0 based media where individuals were only passive recipients of information.

4.4. Major Themes Reflecting Social Influence

4.4.1. Social Complaisance

Social complaisance is a form of social influence which develops when an individual conforms to social beliefs, and agrees with the majority of other group members without objections. This behaviour is undertaken to reflect the same beliefs as others for the sake of the happiness amongst group members. It also consists of the individual's approval of the subjective norms of the group, i.e. what has already been decided and established by the group members in the social network (Bagozzi and Lee, 2002). Social complaisance influences individuals to accept the choices, values, decisions, recommendations and opinions of group members for the sake of happiness or to ensure loyalty or in anticipation of rewards that come with making a financial services purchase decision. Thematic analysis has identified that, within the theme of social complaisance are three main sub-themes that confirm the existence of social complaisance in the data sets. These sub-themes are concurrence, reward anticipation, and a wish to fit in.

Concurrence is one of the explicit outcomes of social complaisance, denoting that individuals accept social influence and confirm to the values, opinions and choices of the majority without looking for an alternative (Bagozzi and Lee, 2002). Within brand social media groups, concurrence can be the result of members coming to a decision quickly by avoiding any unnecessary discussions taking place in the group. An example might be following 'top rated' content on the basis of something very popular, or experiencing the same change in everyday life that has been expressed by someone upon purchasing a financial service.

The respondent R22 acknowledged this phenomenon as follows:

“Certainly it is a benefit of the social media that it has made things more easy and achievable. I have been looking for car finance for a couple of months because the new model of Honda Civic is very popular and everyone is buying it. I come [sic] across the car finance promotion offered by this bank on Facebook. The thing is that there is plenty of evidence available about car

finance regarding its benefits as thousands of the people like this promotion and have given it the top rating compared to what other brands are offering, so definitely it's confirmed that this the best in the market."

This respondent agrees that he accepts what the majority of members in this specific Facebook group think, and he conformed to their opinions by making a similar decision. The respondent also confirmed that he bases decisions on a wish to have the same experience as others when trends emerge. He therefore quite naturally conforms to similar decisions made by thousands of other group members.

Another respondent R16 noted:

"I would rather go with the majority's choice and experience the same rather [sic] making my own choice as you know there could be a risk in it. Since so many people have been recommending this purchase and sharing [sic] experience of banking with them I am into it because it's more close to reality."

This respondent accepts the importance of complying with the opinion and choices of the majority, explaining that he has been influenced by other people's opinions, personal experiences and the benefits of making a purchase. This makes him feel secure and likely to recommend various products and services. Cialdini and Goldstein (2004) argue that compliance has a significant impact on conformity that leads to elevated purchase intentions, as individuals change their beliefs to seek approval from group members according to how the majority behaves.

Similarly, another significant code of compliance is reward anticipation, which means that the members of the group comply with the group's values, decisions, choices and recommendations on the basis of anticipating rewards and benefits (Cialdini and Goldstein, 2004). In the context of online social media, individuals tend to buy particular financial services that give them greater benefits than what those they are currently paying for, such as discounts and bonuses. With the anticipation of the rewards associated with purchase decisions, individuals comply and conform to group members' discussions, promotional content and offers.

During an interview the respondent R24 said:

“Well obviously it is the [sic] matter of financial services so the greater the benefit the better it is, haha. I would ask you a question that who doesn't want extra? This is beneficial from both [sic] company's point of view for keeping the customers' interest in the [sic] services and for customers themselves as well. I [sic] put it in this way, that there are lots of companies offering credit cards but should I be banking with this bank as they offer discounts on foods and leisure activities and most importantly cashback when I use the credit card for shopping? So even if it's not too much, still it's better to use their service than any others and I would go for it without second thoughts.”

This respondent feels that the rewards associated with financial services underpin his purchase decisions. The allure of a better offer motivates him towards particular purchase decisions. Of relevance here is Kelman's (1974) finding, that reward anticipation is one of the strong pillars of accepting social influence at a compliance level, as the greater the benefit an individual sees within a group, the greater the impact of compliance will be.

Another important code of social complaisance is loyalty, which explains the association of the individual in online social media settings with the brand, and with trust in the brand (Labrecque et al., 2011). Such loyalty and association with the group can also be developed as a subsequent outcome of the influence of individual social circles, such as parents, friends, family and co-workers. As a result of this loyalty and trust, online members show their support for the group, conforming to the actions of thousands of other members by regularly participating in the group.

The respondent R20 explained this phenomenon as follows:

“Well, first things first, this is a global bank and is at number one position among [sic] rest of [sic] banks in terms of deposits and assets. Certainly things put influence on you in making a choice in your life. In my case my family like my father and my brother bank with this company so without going somewhere else I went straight in [sic] this bank when I started banking. Also, millions of people have joined their Facebook group, which got me into it.”

This respondent accepts the fact that, being the number one bank and seeing the association of his family and friends with the brand develops normative influence. This respondent also states that the huge number of members in the group caught his attention and confirmed his perception of something valuable happening in the group. He explained that his decision to become a customer was influenced by family members and friends who had an existing association with the brand. Without much thought, the respondent conformed to their choice and became a member.

Another respondent R28 noted:

“I mean, it’s sensible that you follow someone on social media which is being followed by the [sic] millions of other people. It’s kind of satisfactory to be a member of global brands’ social media groups when you see them on your profile.”

This respondent explains that, since the brand is so popular, he was convinced to become a customer. Furthermore, such significant number of members and the obvious popularity of the brand made him join the group because he wanted others to see his affiliation with the brand on SNSs.

4.4.2. Value Incorporation

Value incorporation is a form of social influence based on which an individual group member accepts social influence after internalising the group’s values, beliefs and intentions into their personal value system. Such value incorporation results in a long-term change in the behaviour, attitudes and intentions of online members by incorporating the group’s norms and values, such as social information sharing, participation in informative discussions, informational content creation and personification of available information about the financial services. Unlike social complaisance, incorporation occurs at the level of social influence whereby individuals accept social influence on the basis of their own choices, desires and personal likings after deciding what values and beliefs need to be internalised into their own value system. Within the theme of value incorporation, three essential sub-themes have been identified within the interview data sets. These are informational conformity, social collaboration, and behavioural manifestation.

Informational conformity is a form of informational and knowledge-based support for online members in the group, which enhances their knowledge. It offers them precise insights and analytical abilities (Gubanov et al., 2011). Informational conformity comes from communicating and interacting with group members and customer services, and from informational promotional content such as blogs, advertisements, comments, reviews and ratings which change perceptions and influence subsequent actions, such as purchase intentions.

The respondent R23 explained this phenomenon in their words as follows:

“I believe that social media is the most valuable source of information on the Internet today. Within this bank’s social media group there is not just the basic information, there is a variety of information which enlighten [sic] you and predict [sic] the possible picture of the financial services you are looking at. Although you do find such information on the websites, on social media it’s not just the information, it’s about the accuracy and credibility of the information because it’s coming from different people who have undergone certain experiences and it creates more understanding. Furthermore, the informational blogs’ technical information about the mobile app and especially informative answers from group admin and the latest information in promotional advertisements help you making [sic] a rational choice to get maximum value for money.”

This respondent accepts that the Facebook group is a significant source of information and that information holds credibility and accuracy. The respondent further explains that such information adds significant value to decision-making as it changes perceptions and provides the group with a deep insight into the financial services. In addition, a social interaction within the group and with the group admin helps members to obtain the information they are looking for to make decisions. (Hutter et al., 2013) stated that UGC media has facilitated group-based interaction and informational exchange amongst group members, enhancing their interdependence and greater knowledge, which changes their mind-set.

Social collaboration is defined as the set of values and beliefs of members within a group that explains their understanding and commitment to the group (Dholakia et al., 2004). Within a social group, social collaboration usually develops an internalising influence that occurs either when individuals join the brand group as new members or as existing members via socialization and interactions with others at a later stage of membership (Postumes et al., 2000). On SNSs, social collaboration leads to long-term change within individuals' behaviours and choices because of value incorporation in the form of seeking information, actively participating in discussions, posting comments and accommodating informational needs related to financial services. This helps members to find financial solutions. It is a form of informational interdependence and is based on the availability of awareness and support when making a purchase decision.

The respondent R6 explained this as follows:

“The thing I really like about this group is that it’s very active and has key information on various financial services being offered. Furthermore, [sic] the activity ongoing here is very productive as every day there are hundreds of new posts, adverts, promotions and a long chain of comments and discussions, plus the members are very helpful. These discussions are very real and productive as they lead you to some realistic outcome. You can discuss mortgages, loans, life insurance or another thing [sic] as you get enormous informational support from all the group members and especially from admin.”

The respondent confirms that group-based social collaboration is very strong and the members facilitate each other to engage. Further, the group members accommodate one another and show hospitality in the way that they provide informational support, which can help with making rational decisions. Such cooperation and consensus over the informational discussion leads to greater insight which impacts purchase intentions.

On this note, the respondent R8 reflected as follows:

“I must say that this brand’s social media group is very accommodating as ongoing interaction and informational exchange keep you engaged and you adopt new information for [sic] making improved choices.”

This respondent accepts the fact that incorporating the group's values, such as information sharing leads to rational behavioural change. The respondent admired the collaborative learning values which exist in the brand's group such as accommodating the informational needs of other group members. Furthermore, individuals internalise such collaborative learning values into their own behaviour, and personify their behaviour and choices in reflecting such information-based change. (Hogg and Reid, 2006) stated that such social information sharing enhances socialisation through UGC exchange, and incorporates group values into individual value systems, which enhances the commitment of group members.

Similarly, one of the sub-themes of this incorporation is the behavioural manifestation which reflects rational change in individuals' behaviour and choices as a result of informational exchange and knowledge-based social interaction. This change shows how individuals find themselves capable enough to engage with digital content and use the available informational evidence to evaluate the alternatives and make plans to complete a purchase (Cheung et al., 2011). By contributing UGC information on Facebook, members accept social influence and internalise changes in their opinions, beliefs and attitudes. This occurs through the development of logic and by verifying the experiences of others in relation to financial services. Such services include mortgage, loans, car finance, child education, credit cards and savings and, most importantly, the discounts, bonuses and offers associated with them.

The respondent R22 explained this phenomenon as:

“There is a lot of information and talk going on in the group which will [sic] get [sic] your attention. This bank is a global brand as it is serving all the continents of the world so it's offering so many financial services. One of the best things about this group is that I learnt how we can use the financial help to educate our children. There is a complete children's education development plan available for the middle-class people and it's really worth it. I have read so many blogs and reviews about this plan in this group and have made up my mind to become a member of that scheme as it's a huge benefit to your family.”

This respondent observed a change in his perceptions and thinking when exposed to information in the online group. He was attracted to the extensive group activities and consistent information in the social media group. He was able to access informational content in the form of group discussions and blogs, which subsequently created the opportunity for him to benefit from financial services.

Another respondent R26 shared his view as follows:

“Every day you will see that [sic] there are lots of updates with new information and updates about improving this scheme for giving greater benefit to the customers, which is a very good and unique initiative.”

This respondent confirmed that the activities and information he interfaced with became incorporated into the group members’ behaviours and value systems. These were reflected in the form of rational buying decisions. The respondent also admired the provision of extensive informational evidence and informational promotional content in the group which served to create awareness. This observation resonates with earlier research (Hutter et al., 2013) which explains that information-based changes of perception and rationalisation as a result of social media interactions create a desire to engage and to purchase.

4.4.3. Self-Fulfilment

Self-fulfilment refers to the aspects of the individuals’ social identification within the group in terms of their self-esteem, belonging and membership. Self-fulfilment holds a certain level of similarity with social identity as it is the psychological state presenting a unique representation of oneself within the group on the basis of one’s association and loyalty. Tajfel and Turner (1979) explained that the social identity of an individual within a social group confers their self-awareness within the group on the basis of (Ellemers et al., 1999):

- similarities with group members (cognitive identity)
- being emotionally involved in the group activity and demonstrating loyalty (emotional identity)

- having awareness of one's self-worth within the group (evaluative identity)

In this study the self-fulfilment theme yielded two sub-themes which have been identified in the data sets: self-worth, and involvement.

Self-worth in a social group, which is commonly known as evaluative identity, describes the individual's self-worth within the group. It evaluates the group based on individual self-esteem, which explains the individual's self-worth in terms of belongingness with the group. It further explains the identity, importance and value an individual receives from being a member of the group (Dholakia et al., 2004). Within an online social media group, self-worth denotes the individual's recognition, status and impact on their life from being a customer or being associated with the group. It further highlights the individual's satisfaction and feelings in their social circle from being an active member in the global brand, which subsequently creates trust and the motivation to be part of the 'best' in the market.

The respondent R14 explained this phenomenon as follows:

“Honestly speaking, this [sic] is a kind of satisfaction that I am a member of a global brand on Facebook. It looks better on your Facebook profile. Getting popular on Facebook isn't [sic] easy thing but you see this is a banking group and has more members than most of the famous fashion brand groups on Facebook. You'll see [sic] lot of advertisements and promotions of this brand and it's very popular in our society and most of the people in my social circle bank with this company. Especially when the people around you see that you are a customer of this bank and show a desire to do the same then it motivates you. More importantly, it gives a satisfactory feeling that you are buying what's best and most recognised in the market.”

This respondent confirms the role of positive self-worth of in terms of being associated with the group. The respondent is openly accepting of that fact and evaluates his identity in terms of the identification it gives him when he is seen to be a member of a global brand community, which is extensively popular. He is comfortable with recommending the brand to others and passing on information about its financial services. The respondent also explained that this increases his belongingness with the group and supports his self-esteem when he makes a purchase decision because he is buying the best and most popular brand in the market. Wang's (2017) research

revealed that, within the business context, evaluative identity reflects the individual's self-worth from being associated with a certain brand group, and increases their self-esteem through increasing their confidence and motivation to be a customer.

Similarly, emotional identity explains group members' activities within the group as a means of showing loyalty to the group (Dholakia et al., 2004). The emotional association and involvement of individuals in the social group develops attachment and affective commitment and enhances the willingness of the group members to not just be part of the group but to become active members and play a part in its development (Ellemers et al., 1999). In a business context, the emotional component of identity explains the role of individuals in the online social group supporting the group activities and participating in discussions and informational social interaction to enhance the trust and credibility of the brand and information about the financial services. Emotional identity also leads to the individuals' contribution and efforts towards brand promotion and support by, for example, playing an active part in creating the UGC in the form of writing blogs and reviews, publishing their own analyses of the brand's financial services or starting group discussions.

This is explained by the respondent R17 as follows:

“To me this group is a place where I could [sic] share my opinion and have my words influence others. It's always a good idea to endorse the truth about certain brands and bring reality to [sic] public. I would like to share my experience about this bank from when I bought my first mortgage. I use [sic] to read the blogs and articles on the Internet and on social media but I found the social media content more close to reality. I would like to remain with this bank and contribute my part in the group development in the same way it enabled me to make a financial decision. It's more like a chain of cooperation on the social media. I have contributed in this group on mortgage services and written a few blogs and reviews which have been widely appreciated by admin and other members. In fact I have recommended my friends and fellows to use the information available in this group, as the discussions, comments and rating of financial services provides [sic] you with real-time value to make a decision.”

Here the respondent explains his emotional involvement and expresses that he wants to contribute to the development of the group and promote the brand as a function of his loyalty. He

explains that informational social interaction yields factual and real evidence and supports him in making a purchase decision. The respondent further explains that he would like to promote the brand and bring facts to the attention of other members of the group, using their personal experiences. Other members have played an active role in group discussions, helping others make purchase decisions and creating informational content in the form of blogs and reviews to facilitate purchase decisions. These findings align with research carried out by Reid (2004) who stated that emotional identity enhances the individual's group involvement, and increases their loyalty in the form of group development and group welfare.

4.5. Major Themes Reflecting Purchase Intentions

4.5.1. Online Verbal Evidence

Online verbal evidence is described as positive or negative statements, reviews, recommendations and beliefs about products or services generated by present or former customers and socially made available to a multitude of people and businesses on electronic platforms such as the Internet. Online verbal evidence can also be termed as eWOM, which is a source of potential information about the credibility, quality and utility of products and services in the computer-mediated marketing and other Web 2.0 based digital forms such as social media (Okazaki, 2009). Online verbal evidence influences the perceptions of consumers and explains the real-time facts associated with financial services, subsequently leading to rational purchase decisions. On SNSs informational social interactions between the online members' blogs, reviews, ratings, comments and interactive promotional content contributes significantly to developing eWOM (Lee et al., 2012). Within the theme of online verbal evidence, four sub-themes were identified in the data sets. These are trust, authenticity, satisfaction, and approval. Each of these codes is explained in the analysis below.

Trust refers to beliefs and opinions about quality and satisfaction developed through trustworthy information exchange and unbiased communication. Trust creates a strong bond between the consumer and the brand, based on reliability, accuracy and the dependability of products and services (Elliott and Yannopoulou, 2007). Within online SNSs, group-based social interactions

change the perceptions of consumers by fostering trust and reliability, which enhance the consumers' association with the brand and subsequently lead to purchase decisions. Group-based social interactions enable members to gain deep insight into financial services in terms of the expenses, benefits, utility and security that establish the brand's dependability and trustworthiness (Habib et al., 2014).

The respondent R8 reflected as follows:

“This is a popular and well-known brand of financial services. You’ll see most of the people in our community bank with them and they recommended [sic] this because it’s worth it. Their social media page is also very active as very important and accurate information which helps you to make a decision in less time. Most importantly there are stories about the experience of existing customers which you can read any day in the Facebook group which gets our trust. Because everyone wants to get [sic] benefit of money so being a first time buyer the informational content, blogs, comments and [sic] reviews and ratings give you satisfaction in the way that someone else has been there before you and it was a good experience being a consumer.”

This respondent agrees that the online social interactions in groups have enhanced his engagement and trust in the informational and promotional content about the various products and service. The respondent mentioned that existing customer experiences and opinions are a key to trust building and associations with the brand, as their knowledge exchange in the social group confirms the benefit of the financial services in terms of reliability, cost effectiveness, stability and the accuracy of the financial information. Chiu et al. (2010) explained that SNSs enable greater involvement and engagement of individuals with interactive and informative content. This influences individual perceptions, and establishes brand trustworthiness that subsequently develops purchase intentions.

Another significant sub-theme from the online verbal evidence is authenticity, which explains that factual information confirms the belief or proposition is ‘truth’. The evidence confirms the credibility and authentication of promotional information about the products and services being offered. Within the online social medium, evidence includes recommendations, extensive

likes, comments and shares, personal experiences, top ratings and best-selling informational content published by companies in the online brand community (Tiago and Veríssimo, 2014).

The respondent R2 explained this in their words as follows:

“Social media is a huge benefit in conveniently learning and getting practical information. Nowadays every financial service brand has their own group on Facebook and keep [sic] posting very interesting and interactive videos and informational content that keep you busy and develop your interest in the brand. Most importantly it’s the people’s choice and opinion on social media that impact [sic] on your choice. It’s not always the case that you go and read long bits of information but rather you see a brand page is liked and its informational videos about customers’ experiences and use and informational content about best-selling and top rated by customers posted on Facebook make [sic] you believe in what they are saying.”

This respondent accepts the role of social media group in providing evidence about the credibility of information and the utility of the financial services being promoted. The respondent also notes that social media is more productive than websites as such platforms allow the user to take a close look at reality in terms of interactions between group members which influence changes in opinions. The respondent suggests that widely shared and commented- on information and promotional content about financial services develops evidence of originality that essentially creates willingness and interest amongst consumers to engage with the product or service.

Satisfaction refers to the positive feelings that individuals get from something they are associated with (Baker and Crompton, 2000). Satisfaction obtained from online verbal evidence can manifest as positive feelings about products and services. These arise out of interactions, communication and knowledge exchange in social media. Wang et al. (2018) stated that satisfaction strengthens eWOM through positive reviews, recommendations and ratings about quality, utility and benefits.

The respondent R23 explained this phenomenon as follows:

“In my view the greater benefit from social media is that you connect with your people and at the same time you get in touch with lots of other things extremely valuable in everyday life. For example, you get lots of information and see certain products and services related to food, clothing, finance and fitness. The important thing is that before you make a purchase you can use the plenty of evidence and reviews which clear your doubt [sic] and give you a satisfactory feeling about a purchase. I am a regular traveller and found out that the credit card of this bank has the lowest APR and doesn't adds [sic] charges when you make a payment in a different currency or withdraw abroad. Further, I have read in the Facebook group that there is an additional discount on food when I make an online transaction, which is actually more satisfying.”

This respondent accepts that informational content and knowledge-based exchange clarify doubts and questions and enhance satisfaction. The respondent also explains that the availability of plenty of informative content in the group helps users make a rational decision. Furthermore, the respondent confirms that, as an existing customer, group-based interactions have enabled him to understand additional benefits such as discounts, bonuses and offers associated with financial services. These strengthen the group's affiliation with the brand through increased satisfaction.

Similarly, this explains why certain brands are favoured and command more recognition and reputation amongst consumers. It also explains the impact of the interpersonal influence of family, friends, peers and other social actors in developing recognition and wider acceptance of the brand (Bearden et al., 1989). Within online social media, approval covers the wider picture of belief about financial services when online members like and favour the brand compared to other brands in the market, and when they appreciate and support the other group members' association with the brand.

The respondent R1 explained this as follows:

“I consider social media a guide and driving force that change the way you think. I mean it contains the information and evidence, and most importantly the social media shows what's in trend and obviously when something is in trend it mean [sic] that it has been favoured and appreciated by a vast majority. Most of the people in my social circle bank with this company

and do [sic] recommend the same to me when I asked them, which I think is more valuable than making a choice by yourself. And when you see the similar likings and compliance with the brand by millions on social media who have joined the social group you think this is the best in the market.”

This respondent explains that wide acceptance in social media and in social circles can be influential in encouraging users to favour the brand’s financial services. The respondent further explained that they like to see that the brand is trending on social media, as vast numbers of people have joined the social media group.

4.5.2. Buying Intentions

Buying intentions refer to the situation where a consumer intends to make a purchase of a certain product or service based on certain specific conditions. These conditions include changes in perceptions, attitudes, beliefs and behaviours based on the product or service quality, utility and value (Hausman and Siekpe, 2009). Consumer buying intentions are a complex process. Buying intentions are similar to purchase intentions and reflect a change in the consumers’ mindset as an outcome of the value perception, influence and word-of-mouth in the online medium (Hutter et al., 2013). Informational interactions on social media influence consumer perceptions about the quality, credibility, informational adaptability and usefulness of products and services. Such group-based interactions on SNSs enable consumers to gain deeper insight into the utility and benefits of products and services in real life in terms of information sharing, comments, discussions, interactive content, reviews, blogs, online customer support and members’ personal experiences. This creates the motivation for a rational purchase decision. Within the theme of purchase intentions, three codes were identified in the data sets, which are motivation, influence and decisions.

An intention is a stimulation to the individuals’ behavioural direction or the cause of a person’s repeat behaviour. In the context of buying behaviour, motivation is a psychological stimulation that triggers purchase intentions on the basis of value perceptions and likings (Erkan and Evans, 2016). Motivation explains how the individual’s social interaction in the online social medium

influences a change in their perceptions, and creates a willingness to make a rational decision. Moreover, informational interactions in the form of communication and engagement with the interactive content about the financial services develop a desire amongst individuals to make a rational purchase decision.

The respondent R14 explained this phenomenon as follows:

“Social media is a huge point of interest for people of every age, race and ethnicity. It has lots of interactive features which keep your attention and most of us spend most of our time on it. In addition to being interesting media it also keep [sic] us updated and makes us aware about new things every day. Most of this new information usually arises from the brands’ Facebook groups, who promote their products and services and create attractive promotions and advertisements which stimulate desire in you when you see the pictures and read the content information. It also contributes to the credibility of the decision when you read comments and see peoples [sic] liking the posts in the group, which you see very often in this brand group.”

This respondent explains the motivation that Facebook groups foster by playing a significant role in generating new information and stimulating a desire amongst online members to make a purchase decision. The respondent also confirms the fact that social media group interactions develop more engagement with the informational and interactive content when it comes to financial services. This changes one’s perceptions and increases their motivation to make a purchase decision. (Wang et al. 2012) argue that group-based social interactions in user-generated social media bring consumers and companies closer. They influence the individuals’ value perception and change their attitudes and intentions, which create the motivation to make rational purchase choices.

Influence refers to the psychological impact of social interactions which leads to a change in attitude and intentions. Influence is a driving force that enhances the willingness of individuals to make a decision by changing their attitude and intentions, either by accepting group decision for sake of reward or for fear of punishment, or through a willingness to review their attitudes and beliefs on the basis of informational interactions and logical reasoning (Bagozzi and Dholakia, 2002). Influence in social media could be a benchmark of a brand for consumers

which impacts on rational purchase decisions when individuals conform to the majority opinion regarding the utility and value of financial services or by evaluating the informational and promotional content available in the social group in the form of members' recommendations, comments, discussions, reviews and blogs.

The respondent R25 explained this phenomenon in the following way:

“The interesting factor of the social media is that it enables you to look at both sides of the pictures. You get to know deeply about the financial services the company is offering when someone comments negatively or rate [sic] the financial services they are offering. This impact on your decision as when you see a majority has liked and strongly recommended a financial service, you also desire to purchase that one. I give you a [sic] example: the foreign remittances offered by this bank service are the best rated by thousands of customers and group members because the company provides reasonable transfer and currency exchange rates. I choosed [sic] this service as the majority has recommended it and also I read about it in the promotional content which further clarified me and supported my decision.”

This respondent accepts that social group interactions lead to multiple forms of influence which subsequently develop into purchase intentions. The respondent confirms that the opinions and beliefs of the majority are the basis of social influence and that informational interactions and knowledge-based social exchange are the concluding factors behind purchase decisions. This informational interaction drives consumer engagement and provides factual evidence as to whether the socially accepted phenomenon holds benefit for them. As argued by (Wang et al., 2012), informational social interactions provide insight, know-how and evidence about the products or services which leads to purchase intentions.

One of the significant sub-themes associated with the buying intention theme is the decision which explains the conclusion or action behind making a choice. The decision in the context of buying behaviour is the evaluation solution of a problem or the logical finding of a consumer about the product or service which leads to a rational purchase decision (Hudson and Thal, 2013). Within SNSs the decision explains the evaluation, choice and conformity of individuals based on their engagement with the informational content and information-based social

interactions with members of the group (Wang et al., 2012). Furthermore, the decision could be the solution to a financial problem based on informational social interaction or conformity to the brand as a result of loyalty or affiliation, or for sake of benefits.

The respondent R20 explained this in their own words as follows:

“Yes, I agree with the role of social media in helping you make choices. Especially in the case of buying a financial service you need a bit more push and support as this [sic] is a matter of money. I think it influences our choices in two possible ways, like you could [sic] go with the trend, best seller, rumours and brand reputation and save time or you can investigate by yourself and reach at [sic] the conclusion. In either way you can get a clear picture of what you should expect from making a decision of purchase. And that’s how social media has become a point of attention and educate [sic] you in multiple ways.”

This respondent accepts the role of social media interactions in terms of informing decisions. The respondent explained that social interactions influence choice in multiple ways, and they change the beliefs, opinions and perceptions of people in relation to products and services. Further, the respondent accepts that social media is a major influence when it comes to making a rational choice and developing purchase intentions about financial services. This is because social media facilitates learning and knowledge sharing about the essential features of the financial services, providing a realistic picture of the utility associated with them. The also endorse the majority opinion and customer experiences and ratings in terms of sales. These findings are in line with those of (Zhu et al., 2016) who also confirmed that heterogenic social media interactions stimulate individuals towards a rational choice and conclusion.

4.6. Summery of Key Findings of Factual Analysis

This section provides a detailed explanation of the themes identified in the interview data sets. The findings show the six themes identified in thematic analysis. The six major themes are consumer media fulfilment, social complaisance, value incorporation, self-fulfilment, online verbal evidence, and buying intentions. The identified themes support the fact that online social interactions on social media, especially SNSs, influence consumer attitudes, opinions, intentions

and decision-making and they shape purchase intentions. The data shows how group-based heterogenic online social interactions develop social influence at different levels, and uniquely change the opinions, thoughts and behaviour of retail banking customers in Pakistan. These findings find support in the existing literature which argues that heterogenic online social interactions within SNS groups and communities on user-generated media implicitly influence customer value perceptions and fulfilment. They also influence brand awareness, brand value and buying behaviour (Wang et al., 2012; Hutter et al., 2013; Fuller et al., 2012; Divol et al., 2012). The literature provides a general conceptualisation of social media and its significant role in transforming consumer behaviour with implications for purchase intentions. The findings of the current study not only support the existing literature and empirical research, but also contribute to the conceptualisation of social media. They provide an empirical basis to apply such user-generated media for social media marketing to create greater value for financial services customers in the B2C environment.

The thematic findings reveal the heterogeneity of social interactions in SNSs, and shed light on the unique impact of online brand group-based social interactions, informational exchange and engagement with promotional content. For example, online social interactions influence the intentions and attitudes of online brand group members who develop a form of social influence at three different levels: compliance, internalisation, and identity. This increases the trust and credibility of the brand amongst consumers by developing online verbal evidence as an intentional social action which impacts purchase intentions. The discussions explicitly answer the research question: 'In what ways does the social media develop consumers' purchase intentions and how can this knowledge be used to create an impact?' The findings of the thematic analysis are organised into three sections. The first section explains the implications of social media gratification for increasing the value of online social interactions on SNSs among users. Secondly, it explains the implications of group-based heterogenic social interactions on SNSs, which lead to multiple levels of social influence and prospective intentional social action. Finally, the implications of social media gratifications and social influence to create impacts and develop the consumers' purchase intentions are clarified.

Consumers' Media Fulfilment

Social media fulfilment is the explicit reason behind the use of social media platforms such as SNSs as a mode of interaction by online users to fulfil their need for gratification by, for example, information acquisition, social connectivity and entertainment. Social media gratification enhances the interest and engagement of online users to interact with promotional content published in a brand group. Users participate by asking questions, posting opinions in group discussions, liking and sharing, and commenting on the interactive informational and promotional content. These gratification features enable online users to interact by making it easier to ask, explore and speedily exchange information about the brand's financial services such as mortgages, credit finance, lease, life insurance, remittances, travel money and car finance. Importantly, these gratification features enhance the awareness and engagement of the online users with the promotional content, current promotional offers, bonuses and discounts associated with the purchase and use of financial services, thus establishing psychological association with the brand.

Within the thematic analysis, major themes and sub-themes have been identified from the interview data sets. The emergent themes and sub-themes of social media gratification such as informational value, interpersonal connectivity and support are considered the main sources of social media gratification, as shown in the thematic analysis table given above.

Social media gratifications hold explicit value for marketing managers when it comes to identifying consumer search patterns about informational content related to financial services on SNSs. The informational value provides marketers with an understanding of the reasons that customers join SNS groups. It sheds light on the orientation of social interactions amongst online users and potential customers. This provides the measures for the marketers to take the necessary steps in order to maximise the consumers' association with the brand by offering them updated informational and promotional content in the form of interactive advertisements, blogs and reviews. This provides online users with a greater chance to consume content and to interact with other group members and companies.

A respondent R7 who is a marketing manager in the company expressed the importance of informational value as follows:

“Using our brand group page on social media as a platform our goal is to create significant awareness about financial services by [sic] publishing interactive informational content about the benefits and utility of financial services on [sic] regular basis, keeping members of our brand group busy and updated.”

Clearly, social media gratification is a useful tool to capture the consumers’ attention and engage them with the brand’s financial services. Brand communities and groups on SNSs serve as a platform through which marketers can understand the gratification needs of consumers and publish appropriate content into those groups and communities. Such content not only creates awareness amongst online users, but also supports the informational needs of existing customers as the company’s social media teams solve their queries and provide them with technical help and guidance in a speedy and accurate way. For example, problems related to mobile app use and Internet banking can be addressed. Brand recognition and eWOM are developed when online customer support regularly publish informational content about financial services and when they release news about lending and borrowing policies, financial services ratings and best-selling information. Customer experiences are provided as testimonials and consumer satisfaction surveys legitimate strong products. Furthermore, promoting the brand’s financial services through associating it with social influencers on SNSs makes a positive impact on online users and develops social influence.

The respondent R9 noted:

“I like this brand because it’s famous! You see lots of people following the [sic] page on Facebook and so I would like to do it as it’s famous.”

The interactive nature of SNSs enables consumers to connect socially and to follow trends, which are perhaps the strongest gratification features of social media. Using such gratifications could enhance competitive advantage and open new dimensions of social media research in the context of consumer buying behaviour. Such knowledge can be further used to target the specific needs of consumers and enlist their involvement to improve the brand’s products and services in online media.

Social Influence

Social influence is the psychological agreement between a social actor and a community or group which results in uniformity of beliefs, opinions, attitudes and intentions. As with conventional media, social influence online exists across multiple levels and transforms attitudes and intentions. Within this study, data interpretation using thematic analysis has revealed three levels of social influence : social complaisance, value incorporation and self-fulfilment. The analysis shows how individual interactions in SNSs play a significant role in changing the attitudes, mind-set and intentions of online members. Within these SNSs informational and knowledge-based social interactions enable the online customer to engage with interactive informational content and update themselves with the latest promotions associated with the purchase of financial services. So as a platform for global online social interaction for the purpose of knowledge and informational digital content exchange in the form of comments, likes, content share, reviews, personal experiences, and promotional content, such brand communities ultimately develop a rational mindset for making a purchase decision.

Using online social media brand communities as a platform for two-way user-generated communication, marketing managers can make use of all three levels of social influence to transform attitudes and beliefs about financial services such as life insurance, credit cards, mortgages, lease and car financing. These support rational purchase decisions. For example, marketers can use compliance social influence to develop purchase intentions in online brand communities by regularly publishing digital content such as the most purchased financial services, customers' post-purchase experiences and the most commented and shared informational content to enhance interest. This creates greater engagement with online users via content, which not only helps them to decide more quickly, but also develops a strong association with the brand.

One of the customers of the company R3 noted of social complaisance:

“I always read the reviews, top ratings and most importantly about [sic] best-selling products and services as they have 100 per cent value before making a purchase decision, because the majority has [sic] already done the work for you and leave [sic] you with their precious reviews and comments which you can simply comply with.”

This customer confirms that buying products that are endorsed by the majority is value for money. The respondent also mentioned that social complaisance saves time in terms of making the correct choice, and has an explicit and significant role in transforming customers' purchase intentions. By using such psychological triggers, marketers can influence the circle of brand community members to accomplish their global vision.

As with social complaisance, social influence value incorporation holds implicit value for the firm to enjoy a long-term relationship with customers. Value incorporation enables the members of the brand community on SNSs to act independently and reflect rationality and mindfulness instead of acting upon the majority's point of view and choices. Value incorporation effects change amongst members in multiple ways, such as by adopting information and knowledge that are shared in the form of interactive informative content and group discussions on specific financial services. Participating in discussions by giving and receiving information on the benefits of financial services is also key. Such knowledge exchange and informational social interactions, whereby members share real-life experiences create a wider awareness amongst members, and influences them to internalise such information and reflect on changes in their behaviour by means of rational and value-for-money purchase decisions. This phenomenon is particularly useful for marketing managers who seek to maximise members' activities and engagement in the brand's social media group by regularly publishing informational and analytical content on the utility of financial services. In addition to the social interaction and publishing informational content, the brand group accommodates customers by supporting them with timely solutions for their technical queries related to online banking and the brand's mobile app. This enhances the customers' association with the brand. Such activities facilitate behavioural manifestations amongst members of the group as a result of informational conformity, because informational conformity incorporates the values of reasonability and rational thinking that influence beliefs and attitudes towards the brand's financial services.

This phenomenon has been explained by one of the company's marketing managers R7 as follows:

"We try to compensate our customers and other social media members which [sic] could be potential customers through consistently creating and publishing the informational and valuable content such as offers, promotions, bonuses and updates on financial services so that they can

make better decisions. By doing this [sic] we have achieved tremendous success as our Facebook group has grown globally with more than a [sic] 15 million brand group members.”

The above statement confirms the fact that for managers to enhance engagement and interaction with their customers on social media it is explicitly important to publish information in these groups to address specific queries. Furthermore, such practices also entice new members into the group to participate in group-based informational interactions and to receive and share new information which incorporates value into their purchase behaviour.

Online social interactions within brand groups has a unique influence on the self-fulfilment of members, which confirms a change in their attitudes and intentions on the basis of their association with and loyalty to the brand. Such social influence is particularly effective in developing trust in the brand, and the online verbal evidence that is conventionally known as word-of-mouth. Self-fulfilment is another major form of social influence, helping managers to achieve online brand awareness and brand recognition at the same time. Such influence is particularly useful for managers in building the brand in a society of online consumers. The act of being associated with a famous brand makes customers feel more satisfied and accomplished. Promoting the brand's products and services on SNSs in the form of the brand group or community increases their self-worth and stimulates customers to pay attention, consequently leading to purchases. Using self-fulfilment influence as a tool, marketers can not only develop brand recognition but can also assure customers that they are part of the best brand in the market. The respondent R23 noted that:

“SNSs play a vital role in updating us about what's famous and in the trend. I would like to make a purchase and associate myself with something which [sic] is [sic] in trend as it increases my self-esteem and kind of contributes to my social circle. It's so because I am associated with what's best in the market.”

From the above statement it is clear that self-fulfilment has significantly changed this customer's perception and beliefs about financial services and has shaped his buying intentions. The increase in a customer's self-worth from being associated with a renowned brand not only increases self-fulfilment but also develops the customer's trust in that brand. This trust is reflected in the form of online verbal evidence such as eWOM which proclaims the utility and

usefulness of financial services and further acts as evidence for other potential customers on social media, especially while they are making a buying decision.

4.6.1. Managerial Implications

From a managerial point of view, by incorporating such findings into social media marketing strategies, managers can influence the behaviour of online members using the SNSs brand communities and groups as a platform to attract more potential customers to consume interactive informational content. This drives engagement and in-group activity. Such in-group engagement and informational social interaction changes the behaviour and beliefs of group members, creating behavioural uniformity upon accepting social influences. Such uniformity resultantly creates intentional social action such as online verbal evidence, which subsequently leads to greater buying intentions amongst online users.

Managers should incorporate appropriate consumer media fulfilment, such as informational value by enriching their financial services content and enhancing the provision of online customer support to maximise heterogenous social media interactions. Multiple levels of social influence could be developed within the financial brand community to develop uniform beliefs and intentions by creating a group-based intentional social action. An example of this might be online verbal evidence on social media. Such group-based intentional social actions and online verbal evidence promotes buying intentions amongst consumers. An explicit managerial implication of the key findings within the financial services industry is that the social influence of value incorporation has a more significant impact on the buying intentions of consumers, compared to social complacency and self-fulfilment. Since value incorporation provides implicit support for the consumption of informational content, it enhances the consumers' independent reasoning through the internalisation of knowledge and information in relation to performing self-driven analyses and interpretation of content such as cost-benefit analysis. Finally it improves rational purchase decisions.

Chapter 5: Conceptual Framework

5.1. Introduction

In chapter 2, a critical review of literature explained how social media was developed based on the principles of UGC on Web 2.0 and Web 3.0. These technologies facilitate two-way marketing communications in the B2C environment and enable complex and heterogenic social interactions amongst online users. It further set the foundation for how heterogenic online social interactions on SNSs develop the multiple forms of social influence which significantly impact on the purchase intentions of retail financial services customers. The social constructionism paradigm of the research set out in chapter three explained the philosophical foundations of the development of online social influence on social media. It provided an in depth understanding of the multiple meanings of online social influence from social-psychological and online marketing communication perspectives. Similarly, the thematic analysis presented in Chapter Four explained the emergent themes, sub-themes and codes that emerged from the qualitative data that justified the multiple epistemological stances of the researcher. This chapter explains how social media, from the perspective of social influence shapes consumer purchase intentions.

This chapter explains the conceptual framework of the current study and explicitly answers the key research question, which is as follows: “In what ways do social media develop consumer purchase intentions and how can this knowledge can be used to create impact”. The chapter first explains existing theory and literature findings around the relationship between social media and social influence. Secondly, it explains the empirical findings of the existing research and finally it identifies a conceptual framework based on the findings of the research.

5.2. Existing Literature and Research

As explained earlier in the introduction and literature review, Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 based social media is capable of UGC exchange. This enables online users to socially interact and exchange digital content across the entire online social network. This enables online users to communicate with marketers and companies in a B2C environment. This means users consume, alter and create digital content at the same time. This contrasts with traditional Web 1.0-based online media whereby online users were only passive consumers of promotional, informative and interactive content. Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 based social media have revolutionised marketing communications and have enabled marketers to directly reach out to and communicate promotional messages to potential customers. It also helps online users to socially interact, connect and exchange information and interactive digital content through forms of social media including SNSs (Ozuem et al., 2016).

These media support utilitarian and hedonic interactive experiences through social information as well as knowledge sharing. They facilitate socio-emotional support amongst online members, further providing a fundamental basis for the development of online social influence with implications for consumers online behavioural modelling (Gutiérrez-Cillán et al., 2017; Zaglia, 2013; Kang and Schuett, 2013). Furthermore, such digital platforms help consumers and online users on social media to interact, influence, consume, co-create and communicate information about products and services. They can therefore share content with millions of other members to promote the goods and services sold by various financial services companies. Furthermore, the commercialisation of social media has enabled companies to achieve this outcome with the development of social media brand communities or groups where online users enjoy intimacy, interactivity, socialisation and engagement with financial services (Bonson and Flores 2011; Proenca et al., 2010; Jin and Phua, 2014).

Such online social interactions on social media have multiple outcomes for the behavior of individuals (Zhou, 2017). For example, SNSs develop online social interactions to create

multiple levels of social influence which can transform the buying behaviors of online users by changing their attitudes, beliefs, opinions and intentions. Changes in consumers' behaviour are subjective in nature and are the outcome of heterogenic SNSs brand group and community-based interactions. They are influenced by the level of engagement, and the extent of consumer-brand communications (Chan and Guillet, 2011). Firstly, interactive promotional messages are broadcast to consumers following careful analysis of their online behaviour. Second, companies facilitate consumer-to-consumer interactions on social media to give their advertisements greater exposure. Consequently, this transforms the behaviour and perceptions of users and creates an opportunity for them to become potential consumers in the process of making rational purchase decisions (Ozuem and Tan, 2014). The heterogenic nature of SNSs brand groups encourages complex interactions between users (Hoffman and Fodor, 2010). At the same time, this enables marketers to harness information relating to consumer behavioural patterns while interacting and engaging with online content. Such intelligence provides a wider picture of aggregate behaviour and user opinions in order to tailor information to particular audiences (Hearn et al., 2009; Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010; Berthon et al., 2008).

As mentioned as part of the discussion about the rationale of the study, social influence has been empirically studied in a social context by adopting a social-psychological lens to study changes to the social behaviors, attitudes and intentions of individuals in society. Such a positivist stance about the reality of social influence has limited the scope and meaning of social influence, as each of three forms of social influence have had different outcomes and impacts on consumer attitudes, beliefs, opinions and intentions when studied in a business context. The research epistemology of this study thus states that multiple forms of social influence, such as compliance, internalization and identity are developed as a result of user-generated social interactions on social media. This has hitherto not been empirically investigated in the context of online marketing communications. A research gap still exists in terms of how the multiple forms of interactive digital content initiate content engagement and online social interactions amongst users who form multiple levels of online social influence. Such influence shapes consumer perceptions and enhances trust and insight about utility and the consumption of retail financial services. These include mortgages, credit finance, lease and insurance. Such a form of influence shapes purchase intentions.

Technologically advanced Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 based social media offer higher levels of ease for social interaction and engagement with digital content to online users compared to other online medias such as virtual communities (Kaplan and Haenlien, 2011). Since social media is developed on Web 2.0 based technologies and since it has dramatically improved the interactive features of the web compared to Web 1.0 based applications, it has come to be called “user-generated media” (Al-Saleh et al., 2019). Social media comprises of a set of UGC based applications for ubiquitous social interactions. For example Facebook is used for social connectivity and networking, YouTube for hedonic social interactions (consuming, creating and sharing the interactive video and streaming content) and Twitter for collaborative learning through blogging and micro-blogging. These provide intelligence on consumer preferences and choices in relation to certain products and services and offer clues as to the motivations of those that interact on social media (Hollebeek et al., 2014). The greater the usefulness and value perception of the UGC based information, the higher the level of online traffic (Kietzmann et al., 2011). Such an aggregate of opinions, online search data and interaction patterns yields valuable information and insight for marketers about trends in consumer society. Within the retail banking industry, such an in-bound consumer centric focus particularly helps with the development of brand related social media marketing strategies by means of multi-dimensional consumers engagement with UGC (see Kupp and Anderson, 2007 ; Liang et al., 2008). Marketing communications involving the communication of information-based content about financial services creates a sense of affiliation between online users and financial services brands (Mavri, and Ioannou, 2006). Indeed, such promotions-based brand content speeds up the lines of communication between online users, and presents them with promotional content in relation to consumer finance, credit cards, leases, mortgages and other banking services. This not only adds value to marketing communications to educate consumers about existing products and services, but also communicates knowledge about forthcoming products and services as brand extensions. Consequently, this two-way communication influences significantly the socio-cognitive behaviours of online consumers, helping them to come up with a rational buying decision (Alalwan, 2018; Lu, 2018; Vollmer and Precourt, 2008).

Social networking sites are significant in this regard, and enable online users to use social media for awareness, entertainment, maintaining social connection and, most importantly for interacting with promotional content and advertisements in online brand groups and communities (Bonson and Flores, 2011). Such gratification features of SNSs enhance the consumer's value perception and invites customers to learn more about products and services by becoming members of a community (Phua et al., 2017). Casaló et al. (2013) argued that the social and communal nature of SNS brand communities nurture media fulfilment amongst community members. By yielding four important gratification values, namely social value, hedonic value, informational value and economical value, the multiple levels of individual engagement with UGC in brand communities can be determined. This also serves as a principle guide for consumers to make rational decisions. Indeed, such social interactions are deeply rooted within the value perceptions of online users, and in media fulfilment which also reflects why consumers choose particular media for social communications and interactions (Hsiao and Chiou, 2015). Within the retail financial services industry, the informational and social value of SNS online brand groups and communities enable the members of the group to maximise social collaborative learning around brands. De Valck et al. (2009, p. 185) describe the brand community as “web of personal relationships” UGC driven applications for developing the B2C relationships. Likewise (Wu and Fang, 2010) define brand communities as online spaces facilitating consumer-to-consumer relationships (C2C) in consumer brand triad.

The SNS brand community strengthens the association between consumers and products and services. It fortifies the relationship between consumer and brand, and also the association between consumer and company, and consumers and other consumers (Laroche et al., 2013). Within these online spaces, members of communities gain new insights, such as information, experiences, socio- emotional support, exchange share and pool resources, updates and brand awareness. They can share and receive valuable knowledge about products and services in the form of comments, ‘likes’, group discussions, blogs and informative and promotional content shared in it (Lu, 2018).

Marketers consider such SNS brand communities as a means of strengthening the consumer-brand relationship, and as a cornerstone of individual self-fulfilment. They consider the members

of these communities as enthusiastic and loyal supporters of brands (Schau et al., 2009). However the utilitarian perspective of heterogenic social interactions in such brand communities reveals the reality; that the individual memberships in brand communities are subjective in nature; i.e. most individuals seek membership of such brand communities to find exclusive, offers, rewards, promotions and bonuses, and some individuals seek informational value by confirming to the available information in the form of consumer generated content for a long term change in behaviour and attitude (Sung et al., 2010).

Pullizi (2013) noted a significant change in the attitudes of online buyers in relation to the online content they access on social media. Selling products and services online to customers has become increasingly difficult due to the fact that buyers prefer to look for focussed content that will inform their purchase decisions. Interactive, informational content in SNS brand communities is valued as a form of digital information, and many consider that social media offers the most valuable information available. This approach is particularly helpful for the marketing of products and services that solve a specific problem, and it sits in contrast to the idea of unfocussed promotional information (Proenca et al., 2010). Furthermore, online social interactions within brand groups and communities creates brand value and develops behavioral uniformity due to the implicit impact of multiple levels of social influence, which also changes the customer's mind-set and purchase intentions.

Dholakia et al. (2004) argue that the social media value perception is a psychological trigger that can be considered an antecedent to the use of online media while measuring behavioural change amongst individuals of social community. The multiple dimensions of the uses and gratification paradigm developed by (Katz et al., 1974) have been considered as a means of understanding consumer value perceptions. These are considered to be the antecedents of online social interactions on social media by many scholars (Cheung et al., 2011; Zhou, 2011; Dholakia et al., 2004). The uses and gratification paradigm consists of value perception and gratification factors such as purposive value (informational and instrumental value), self-discovery, entertainment value, interpersonal connectivity and social enhancement value which develop changes in the behaviour of individuals. Such changes propel many towards participation in SNSs. Okazaki (2009) argued that the online social uses and gratification factors create gratification value in

online settings. The researcher suggests the purpose of social interactions boosts the credibility of online sources which further helps companies target potential customers with products and services. More recently, consumer value perceptions of social media have been used to study goal-directed consumption behaviour (Kwon et al., 2014; Muntinga et al., 2011; Papacharissi and Mendelson, 2011). Analysis suggests that, in terms of consumer-brand interaction and consumption, online users simultaneously use multiple platforms of social media which offer multiple features and fulfil different purposes in terms of social interactions. In addition, consumers increasingly rely on SNS platforms and consider them as useful communication and informational tools to facilitate the speedy exchange of data for informational, social hedonic, economic and utilitarian needs (Phua et al., 2017).

Within large and complex Web 2.0 based user-generated media platforms such as SNSs, the informational and entertainment appeal are seen as very strong by customers, compared to other gratification values. The informational value of social media is considered of holistic and auspicious media fulfilment value by online users with regards to purchase decision making (Taylor et al., 2012). Furthermore, information value has also proved to be the most significant gratification value and antecedent of consumer social influence in online social communities (Shen et al., 2011). For example, within the financial services industry, SNSs hold pertinent informational value in the form of blogs, reviews, brand ratings, group discussions, comments and even likes. This is particularly the case with financial services brand groups and communities, which not only facilitate the speedy exchange of information about financial services but also help consumers plan for future purchases. In addition, brand groups and communities gratify existing customers with informational and entertainment value in the form of promotions, bonuses and discounts for future financial services purchases.

Such value perceptions confirm the ubiquity of social media and heterogenic social interactions in SNS brand communities. This creates behavioural uniformity by developing multiple levels of social influence. (Cheung et al., 2011) states that consumer value perceptions provide the motivation for informational, social, hedonic and economic social interactions which develop into three distinctive levels of social influence (compliance, internalisation and identity). This leads to the transformation of attitudes and intentions amongst individuals. The acceptance of

each of three levels of social influence occurs either through the normative conformity of values and beliefs (subjective norms), through informational conformity and value incorporation, or through self-fulfilment (self-defined relationship with group). Deutsch and Gerard (1955) argued that within the socio-psychological disciplines, social influence is the product of social interactions between social actors which develops into one of two distinctive levels of social influence; namely normative social influence and informational social influence. The social actors conform to one of these existent social influence levels either by accepting the social values, opinions, beliefs and norms they come across (subjective norms) or by internalizing information on the basis of personal reasonability. On this basis, they rationally incorporate such values and beliefs into their own value system. As argued by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) the theory of reasoned action holds that subjective norms constitute conformity behaviour which leads to the development of normative social action in which the individuals in society accept social influence for the sake of happiness, or as a favourable reaction to others to avoid punishment or to comply with the anticipation of reward (Dholakia et al., 2009). Similarly, informational conformity develops into a form of informational social influence in which individuals choose to accept the values and beliefs they believe fit with their value system.

The work of Deutsch and Gerard (1955) on the typology of social influence was empirically modified by Kelman (1958), who developed the social influence framework and argued that individuals' social influence is the outcome of individual social interactions. Three distinctive levels within society exist: compliance, internalization and identity. In terms of user-generated media, the typology of social influence holds unique outcomes for individual behaviours that are subjected to heterogenic social interactions and engagement in SNS groups and communities (Kang and Schuett, 2013). The 'compliance' form of social influence develops when individuals conform to social values, norms, beliefs and attitudes without choice for the sake of reward, to avoid punishment or to achieve happiness for their significant others. 'Internalization', as a form of social influence is based on informational conformity and long-term change in behaviours upon rationally accepting and incorporating social values (e.g. social information and experience sharing) into the individual value system. Finally, 'identity' reflects the development of social influence upon accepting social values on the basis of self-determined relationships between individuals and in society in terms of recognition and self-identity. Kelman's (1958) social

influence theory has proven to be a significant contribution to the existential literature on social influence, and it further provide the basis for the majority of the empirical investigations conducted on SNSs and user behaviour (Zhou, 2017; Zhou, 2011; Dholakia et al., 2004; Kang and Schuett, 2013; Cheung et al., 2011). However, the argument about the potential implications of such a social influence framework in the retail financial service industry in a B2C environment has never been ignored by researchers, as it underpins the fact that social influence is developed as a result of heterogenic SNS brand group and community based social interactions. Such utilitarian and hedonic brand group-based interactions could potentially enable businesses to communicate with customers to shape their behavior.

Such media fulfilment enhances the consumer's engagement with the interactive promotional and consumer generated content in brand communities and they come to trust and show loyalty towards the brand, subsequently leading to eWOM (Laroche et al., 2013). Rialti et al. (2017) argued that eWOM is a form of verbal evidence about the brand, and is the outcome of multiple levels of consumer social influence developed through heterogenic, utilitarian and hedonic SNS brand community based social interactions. These are motivated chiefly by consumer value perceptions. Within the context of social media, brand communities have a positive impact on consumer-brand relationships (Chu and Kim, 2011) and customer purchase intentions (Erkan and Evans, 2016). Likewise, consumer-brand, consumer-company and consumer- consumer relationships develop trust and positive influence based on loyalty and identification. Nevertheless, consumer to consumer relationships in social media settings exert the most significant influence on developing brand trustworthiness and loyalty. Such findings speak volumes about UGC which incorporates the foundation of social media. Since the online spaces in the form of brand communities provide the basis for the development of consumer trust and loyalty, such consumer-based brand trust and loyalty develops and drives eWOM. In other words, eWOM translates consumer trust and association with the brand in SNS brand communities as a result of consumer to consumer social interaction and exchange. The intensity of the consumer-brand and consumer – consumer relationship, homophily, trust and social influence are the major factors contributing to eWOM on social media networks (Chu and Kim, 2011). The intensity of the relationship influences search behaviour and propagates opinions and knowledge sharing with others.

The research epistemology states that heterogeneous social interactions within SNS brand groups or communities influences the behaviour and intentions of individuals, and develops uniformity of beliefs amongst individuals and groups at multiple levels. This occurs, firstly by changing the attitudes, beliefs and opinions of individuals when they conform to the values and beliefs of the group. Second, it occurs on the basis of internalizing the social values and beliefs into their own value system, before finally accepting and adopting the values and beliefs of the group on the basis of a self-defined relationship with other members of the community. Such a constructivist epistemology fills the empirical gap in research in relation to SNS and user behaviours based on social influence theory. The positivist research paradigm used in many previous studies states that individual heterogenic social interactions in SNS communities can be understood using social influence theory. This leads to socio-psychological behavioural analysis and attitudinal change (Dholakia et al., 2004; Cheung et al., 2011; Zhou, 2011; Zhou, 2017; Dholakia et al., 2009; Hwang, 2014). The current research thus confirms that, based on a marketing and communication perspective, such heterogenic, hedonic and utilitarian social interactions in SNS brand groups have multiple impacts, directly and indirectly on consumer purchase behaviours and intentions. The fundamental epistemological stance of the current study thus provides the unique opportunity to empirically study the multiple levels of consumer social influence. The aim has been to explore the multiple meanings of social influence from a marketing perspective. These have different impacts on consumer purchase intentions.

5.3. Conceptual Framework

The current research builds upon the work of (Zhou, 2017) and concludes that the impact of social media on individual behaviours is subjective in nature, as social media interactions develop multiple levels of social influence which change attitudes and behaviours, and develop purchase intentions in online users of retail financial services. Zhou (2017) examined individual interactions on social media platforms such as SNSs. They developed three distinctive levels of social influence compliance, internalisation and identity that change individual attitudes, behaviours and intentions. Zhou (2017) found that the multiple forms of social influence subjectively impact on individual behaviors on social media platforms, and many develop the

motivation for knowledge adoption. Such individuals continue to use SNSs. They further suggested that informational and social support are the two essential determinants of individual social media interactions on SNSs which lead to the development of multiple levels of social influence. These subsequently shape individual behaviors and intentions. They found that the role of informational support in developing social influence was significant, as individuals share and receive information and participate in SNS communities which increases their trust and satisfaction with the community by strengthening the group norms. Zhou (2017) provided a platform for understanding how social media interactions develop into multiple forms of social influence, which then either change or modify individual behaviours and intentions. Participation in online SNSs communities is an example of this. However, their work is greatly limited to a socio-psychological context, as their study explains that such phenomena, in a business context could possibly lead to changes in consumer behaviour and perceptions about products and services. This is especially the case within electronic commerce and online marketing settings and in SNS community-based interactions. These often create social influence that can transform consumer purchase intentions. The current research provides evidence to support the idea that social media has a significant impact on user behaviour (purchase intentions) from the perspective of social influence theory. This applies to the context of marketing. It also creates an impact when studied in the context of the socio-psychological disciplines. Heterogenic social media interactions (social, informational, hedonic, utilitarian and economic) in SNS brand communities enhance the experiential value of online users and create three distinctive levels of social influence (social complaisance, value incorporation and self-fulfilment). These subsequently shape purchase intentions. Such findings have been supported by the extent of literature in the literature review chapter.

The current research findings add new knowledge to existing empirical evidence. The study identifies six major themes that explain the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions in the retail financial industry. These are consumer media fulfilment, social complaisance, value incorporation, self-fulfilment, online verbal evidence and buying intentions. Individual social media interactions are heterogenic in nature, and the outcome of such interactions are subjective in nature. Social media has unique implications for online user behaviours in the context of social influence theory, and when studied in the retail financial

services industry. Consumer media fulfilment provides essential gratification when choosing a social media format for informational, social, hedonic and economic social interaction purposes. Within the financial services industry, such media fulfilment values motivate consumers to interact within SNS brand communities. The heterogenic social interactions of consumers in those brand communities transform their attitudes and behaviour upon developing distinctive social influence as a result of accepting the social norms and values of the group. Such norms and values include social information sharing in the form of blogs, product reviews, comments, opinions, active participation in group discussion, publishing interactive content (pictures, videos, statistics), liking and sharing group posts (Zhou, 2017). Distinctive social influence develops upon the acceptance and adaptation of such social values and norms upon interacting within the SNS brand communities (i.e. social complaisance, value incorporation and self-fulfilment). Social complaisance explains how consumers accept widely known propositions, values and beliefs about financial services for the sake of reward or the happiness of significant others. For example, consumers who accept social influence at the social complaisance level develop their beliefs, attitudes and behaviours on the basis of the majority opinion, and widely held beliefs about financial services. Many seek to avoid the risks associated with making a new choice. Such normative conformity to subjective group norms and values develops normative intentions (Kang and Schuett, 2013). Similarly, social complaisance motivates consumers to make a buying decision on the basis of the evidence of utility perceived of by the majority of existing customers. Such evidence includes knowledge of bestselling products and services, and the most reviewed products and services that are advertised by companies in SNS brand groups and communities. Unlike the socio-psychological context, social complaisance, in this context is concerned with the acceptance of the socially held values and beliefs of individuals for the sake of rewards, and to avoid risk. Consumers tend to choose products and services which have been purchased by the majority of group members so that they can avoid any risk in product utility upon making a purchase decision.

The purchase decision, in this regard originates from the influence of social beliefs, and the opinions of others. This matters more than the individual's own rational evaluation and analysis. Such compliance with the majority of beliefs, attitudes and behaviours leads to the conformity or uniformity of attitudes and beliefs between individuals and the group, as the intention of social

action (Dholakia et al., 2004). Intentional social action, in this context refers to positive online verbal evidence about products and services, whereby the individual, himself develops trust and loyalty in the brand's products and services. This trust leads to the development of motivation to buy. Buying intentions are the explicit motivational impact of positive verbal evidence (eWOM) whereby individuals make rational purchase decisions based on trust, brand loyalty, evidence of post purchase reviews posted by previous buyers, product quality and utility (Okazaki, 2009). Similarly, value incorporation is another distinctive level of social influence which results in a change of attitude and behaviours as the result of informational conformity, social collaboration and informational and knowledge exchange. Value incorporation describes the internalisation of the values and norms of the social group into the individual's own value system, which develops into a set of purchase intentions. Unlike social complaisance, value incorporation transforms the attitudes and beliefs of individuals upon accepting shared information and knowledge about the brand. Based on the actions of other group members, they develop capability and imperative judgement to make a rational purchase decision rather than merely complying to the majority opinion. Shared information and knowledge about brands in such communities is based on members exchanging personal experiences and product reviews. It is also based on active group discussions, blogs, micro blogs, testimonials, informational content about products and service utility, technical help and customer support in the form of questions and answers. Value incorporation develops a long-term change in the individual's behaviour and attitudes, as individuals internalise pertinent information and knowledge about products and services through social collaborative learning and informational social interaction in brand groups (Kang and Schuett, 2013; Wood and Hayes, 2012). Changes in individuals' attitudes and behaviours are subjected to higher levels of individual engagement with informational content. This enables them to analyse and evaluate such information and develop a rational mind-set for making an imperative purchase decision (Kuan et al., 2014). Social influence is developed on the basis of such group values, information and knowledge conformity and it has been considered significant in developing consumer purchase intentions. Many individuals incorporate values into their own value system, and develop personal capabilities and wider insight to make a rational purchase decision, rather than confirming to the majority's purchase decision. Individual purchase behaviours are subjective, and tend to be influenced by what is admired and proclaimed as top rated by the majority on social media. Such information might not be as useful to a specific

individual. Rather, he/she may consider the majority opinion as one important factor that will shape their judgement. Such social influence constitutes the individual's intentional social action in the form of verbal evidence about products and services on basis of their own judgement, trust and value perception. As argued by (Tsao et al., 2015) information conformity leads to information-based social influence which not only catalyses long term change in individual attitudes and behaviour, but also develops trust and loyalty towards the brand in the form of electronic word of mouth. Such positive verbal evidence about financial services products and services in the form of reviews, comments and opinions may also influence the purchase behaviour of other consumers.

Social influence at the self-fulfilment level defines the distinctive self-defining relationship of an individual within the brand group on the basis of group-based social interaction in SNS brand communities. Self-fulfilment describes the social identity of individuals as members of the brand group. It describes their association and worth, relative to other individuals (Okazaki, 2009). Individuals' social interactions in SNS brand groups and communities develop based on emotional associations and involvement with the brand. Loyalty and identity are therefore formed (Barreda et al., 2015). Self-fulfilment social influence develops when individuals accept the group norms and values, and develop behavioural uniformity with other members of the social group. They proclaim the worth and value of the brand's products and services which satisfies their self-esteem. Such self-fulfilment is associated with self-recognition in which individuals consider that being a customer of the brand increases their social identity amongst their peers, friends, family and co-workers. Within the financial services industry, individual social identity is the outcome of perceived self-worth and involvement in group activities. Individuals evaluate the benefit they get from being part of the brand, which not only demonstrates their association with the brand in terms of loyalty, but also explains the value they perceive of from being a member of the brand community. Furthermore, self-fulfilment explains the self-worth that individuals perceive of after becoming a customer of the best, and highest profile global brand in society. As a stakeholder of a popular and global financial services brand, individuals enhance their self-worth and believe that the brand they are associated with is the best in the market. In addition to self-worth, individuals feel it is their duty to contribute to the brand community's development to promote the benefits and awareness of brand products and

services through product reviews and active participation in group discussion. Another way to achieve this is to provide socio-emotional support to other members and to share knowledge (Kang and Schuett, 2013). Self-fulfilment is the evaluation of the individual's worth after being associated with the brand. This has a positive impact on eWOM (Okazaki, 2009). Since self-fulfilment elicits greater involvement from individuals in brand communities, it further enhances brand promotion, trustworthiness and positive verbal evidence on social media which influences purchase behaviours.

The current study contributes new knowledge to existing literature about the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions in the financial services industry. This informs the conceptual framework in the figure below. The conceptual framework provides a detailed understanding of how heterogeneous social media interactions influence consumer purchase intentions in the context of retail financial services. The framework explicitly helps marketers understand consumer behaviour and problems, and sets out how the multiple levels of social influence develop as a result of informational, social, hedonic and economic transactions. These are the bedrock of social influence which help transform online members into potential consumers. The ubiquity of social media solves many B2C communication problems and allows companies to engage with SNS brand community members to share informational and promotional content. This creates brand awareness and leads to sales.

Fig. 3. Conceptual Framework

Chapter 6: Conclusions

6.1. Introduction

This chapter discusses the contribution this thesis makes to knowledge based on research into social media and consumer purchase intentions. This contribution to the knowledge is based on new empirical findings that harness social influence theory. The conceptual findings of the study can be seen in fig 3. This chapter presents the conclusion to the study, and makes sense of the empirical findings. Secondly it discusses the contribution of this work to existing theory and to the literature in the area of social media and consumer purchase intentions. It then discusses the managerial implications and identifies the limitations of the study.

6.2. Conclusions

The study explains the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions in the context of the retail financial services industry. It is based on the perspective of social influence theory which holds unique value by contributing new knowledge to existing empirical research. The study underpins the social behavioural context of social media in influencing the attitudes, beliefs and intentions of customers of retail financial services businesses. It presents a conceptual model to achieve this.

Social media has recognised benefits for both brands and relationship marketing due to its dynamic features, and its ability to increase brand awareness, exposure, brand identity, loyalty, and consumer-brand engagement. It can also lead to an increase in website traffic. In addition, these pervasive online spaces have enabled marketers to gain leads in terms of market intelligence in the context of consumer value perceptions and buying behaviour (Xie and Lee, 2015). Previously social media has been studied and conceptualized from the perspective of various personal behavior, social behavior and mass communication theories (Ngai et al., 2015). However, very few studies have been carried out to determine the impact of social media on

consumer purchase intentions. Existing empirical evidence is limited in terms of explaining the impact of Web 2.0 based social media on consumers purchase intentions. Social behavioral theories have not been comprehensively applied in previous research into this area. Further the existing literature does not explore the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions using social influence theory. The use of this theory in the current study adds significance to the outcome, and makes it unique in nature.

Social media supports utilitarian, social and hedonic interactive experiences through SNS brand groups and communities by means of providing information and supporting knowledge sharing. It facilitates interpersonal socio-emotional support amongst online members, further providing a fundamental basis for the development of online social influence. There are implications for online consumer behavioral modelling (Gutiérrez-Cillán et al., 2017; Zaglia, 2013; Kang and Schuett, 2013). Changes in consumer behaviour are the outcome of social media communications, and such behaviours represent a clear opportunity for companies to drive profit (Chan and Guillet, 2011). First, promotional messages are broadcast to consumers following careful analysis of their online behaviour. Second, companies facilitate consumer-to-consumer interactions on social media to give their advertisements greater exposure. Consequently, this transforms the behavior and perceptions of users, and creates an opportunity for users to become potential consumers in the process of making rational purchase decisions (Ozuem and Tan, 2014).

Heterogenic social media interactions (informational, social, hedonic and economical) in SNS groups and communities develop into distinctive levels of social influence (social complaisance, value incorporation and self-fulfilment) as a result of behavioral uniformity, accepting and incorporating group norms and values. Such behavioral uniformity leads to the development of new attitudes, behaviors, beliefs and intentions. Such findings resonate with Zhou's (2017) argument that heterogeneous social media interactions in SNS communities and groups can effect changes to individual behaviors upon accepting one of three distinctive levels of social influence (compliance, internalization and Identity).

The model of the study explains how consumer media fulfilment drives the motivation to interact using social media. It further explains how social media interactions drive consumer purchase intentions when they accept one of the distinctive levels of social influence. It also explains that intentional social action, such as social influence develops the online verbal evidence about financial services, and this subsequently influences consumer purchase intentions.

6.2. Contribution to Literature and Theory

Previously, social media has been studied and conceptualized using various socio behavioral theories such as social capital theory (Chai and Kim, 2010), social exchange theory (Lin et al., 2009), social identity theory (Kwon and Wen, 2010), social influence theory (Zhou, 2017), social interaction theory (Fischer and Reuber, 2011), social power (Wei, 2009) and social ties (Shiue et al., 2010). Most of these theories have been used to conceptualize social media rather than to investigate and measure their applied impact on social behavioral outcomes. Amongst these social behavioral theories, social media has been a particular area of focus from the perspective of social influence theory. Such theory has been useful to measure changes in the attitudes and intentions of online users. However, most of these studies have investigated the role of social media in changing behaviors, attitudes and intentions from a socio-psychological context (Hwang, 2014; Zhou, 2017; Kang and Schuett, 2013; Zhou 2011; Cheung et al., 2011). None of the studies has deployed social influence theory to provide evidence about the role of social media as a means to influence attitudes and behaviors to drive purchase intentions. The current study thus holds implicit value in the existing literature and provides evidence of role of heterogenic social media interactions as a means of developing some distinctive levels of social influence which drive purchase decisions.

The main focus of this study has been to establish empirical evidence about the role of social media from the perspective of social influence theory. In previous studies, the role of social media in consumer purchase intentions has been studied using various concepts such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Social Capital Theory, Goal Directed Behavior, Social Impact Theory, the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behavior

(TPB). Nonetheless social influence theory has been used to study the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions.

Similarly, the existing literature explains individual social interactions on social media-based communities and groups to observe changes in the attitudes and behaviors of consumers. The use of social influence theory to do this has been limited to socio-psychological contexts only. For example, (Cheung et al., 2011) note the impact of social media on consumer attitudes and intentions from the perspective of social influence theory and concluded that consumer value perceptions and heterogeneous social interactions develop multiple levels of social influence which intensify the intentions of consumers to participate in Facebook communities. Likewise (Kang and Schuett, 2013) measured the impact of social media impact on user behaviors from the perspective of social influence theory, and in the context of travel planning. Hwang (2014) measured the impact of social media using social influence theory and in the context of self-learning. Zhou (2017) measured the impact of mobile social media using social influence theory to observe the continuous commitment of users in SNS communities. (Shen et al., 2011) measured the impact of social interactions on Web 2.0 based applications. They sought to understand the development of we-intentions and usage experiences using social influence theory. Zhou (2011) studied social media interactions using social influence theory to identify the factors that affect online community participation.

Another significant contribution to the literature and empirical evidence is that the current study adopted a qualitative approach, and used social constructionism to understand the phenomenon in a particular setting, rather than applying a positivist research strategy and quantitative research methods. The latter approach was preferred by the majority of previous researchers. The social constructivist paradigm explains multiple meanings surrounding phenomena and sets out that the role of social media in developing purchase intentions is subjective in nature. By applying qualitative research and using case-based research methods, the current study explains in detail how heterogeneous social media interactions (Informational, social, hedonic and economic) drive consumer purchase intentions in the retail financial services industry. Furthermore, the extent of the literature does not clarify the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions using social influence theory. The retail financial services industry is a unique research setting to apply

this conceptual lens. In this sense, the study addresses a gap in knowledge by determining the role of social media in influencing the intentions and attitudes of consumers using social influence theory. The marketing context of the study provided a unique opportunity to address this gap. The current study therefore sets a foundation for understanding the impact of social media impact on consumer purchase intentions in the retail financial services industry. It adds new knowledge to the existing empirical evidence.

Wang (2014) states that individual social interactions in society generate social influence which impacts on purchase behavior and decisions. Multiple levels of social influence theory are implicated, such as compliance, internalization and identity. These have an impact on consumer purchase intentions. However, the real question which led to the current investigation was whether heterogeneous social interactions (informational, social, hedonic and economic) in UGC based social media brand groups and communities create multiple levels of social influence which subsequently drive purchase intentions. Consumer social interactions in social media brand communities and groups hold explicit values of reciprocity and intimacy, enabling members to share consumer-generated information to solve problems and receive technological support. A unique feature of the nature of the membership of such brand communities is that the members are not necessarily loyal “brand enthusiasts”. Indeed, most members of these communities interact within them on the basis of receiving economic and utilitarian benefits such as exclusive offers, deals, promotions, bonuses etc. (Schau et al., 2009; Jin and Phua, 2014). The distinctive nature and unique features embedded in SNS brand communities mean they are explicitly used for brand communication and the development of consumer-brand engagement. This is how consumers develop loyalty towards with brand with leads to rational purchase decisions (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2010). The commonly acclaimed benefits associated with these SNS brand communities are social and connectivity benefits (social interaction and exchange), informational benefits (sharing and seeking information), hedonic benefits such as entertainment enjoyment and fun and economic benefits such as engagement with promotional content.

Such brand groups and community based social interactions develop behavioral uniformity in groups, whereby individuals either conform to the group norms and values (subjective norms), internalize the group values and norms into own value system or develop uniformity of behavior

on the basis of a self-defined relationship with community. Within the retail financial services industry, individual social interactions in SNS brand communities develop normative social influence which explains individual conformity to group values and beliefs for the sake of its own rewards. For example, individuals comply with the majority view and engage with promotions in order to avoid the risk of product utility and to gain wider benefits. Likewise, value incorporation develops into long term influence upon internalizing the group norms and values into the individual's value system. Individuals seek information and knowledge resources and the provision of socio emotional support which drives rational change in behaviors on the basis of self-judgment and product evaluation. Similarly, the self-defined relationship as a result of behavioral uniformity develops social influence at the level of self-fulfilment. At this stage, individuals consider their self-worth as a result of their association with the brand. Consumer media fulfilment and multiple levels of social influence in SNS brand communities result in increased trust, loyalty, brand awareness and association with brand. Such trust, loyalty and association develops online verbal evidence (positive statement or recommendation about brand) which influences buying intentions and purchase planning.

6.4. Managerial Implications

The study sets out a number of managerial implications in the context of the retail financial services industry. The topmost managerial implication of the current study is the ability of managers to communicate with customers as part of a relationship-marketing strategy. This supports the consumer to company, consumer to consumer and consumer to brand relationship by maximizing engagement with interactive promotional content and UGC on social media. Social media supports in-bound consumer centric marketing activities in a B2C context making it a unique medium for promoting goods and services to reach a wider audience and to receive quick customer responses. Consumer engagement with interactive brand content is associated with the experiential value they derive through social media interactions (informational social, utilitarian, hedonic and economic). The fundamental intervention in this regard by marketers and companies could certainly enhance their knowledge about the specific needs of consumers to develop their brand awareness and self-identity. This drives word-of mouth about the brand's products and services.

Secondly, managers should explicitly focus on establishing their social media based brand communities and groups to maximize the promotion of financial services and to create brand awareness, brand identity, loyalty and consumers-brand engagement across the globe in a cost effective way. These pervasive online spaces have enabled marketers to gain leads on market intelligence about a far-reaching audience in the context of consumer value perceptions and buying behaviour. With SNS brand communities, marketers can attract the attention of individuals on social media who have a common interest in the brand. In sharing a mutual social interest, the community members share information and personal experiences. They provide socio-emotional support which is a testament to their strong engagement and consumer-brand ties. Perhaps the best thing about establishing brand communities is that they support consumer to consumer communication and interactions with the brand. Such brand communities value reciprocity and intimacy, enabling members to share consumer-generated information for problem solving and technological support.

To maximize consumer engagement with promotional content and advertisements, marketers should narrow down the key drivers of consumer motivation to participate in brand communities. They must understand why consumers want to interact, consume and create content. Within the retail financial services industry, interactive consumer experiences and heterogenic social interactions are subjected to their media fulfilment (informational, social, utilitarian and economic). Such media fulfilment values drive their motivation and initiate a change in their behavior and intentions. The media fulfilment and gratification values in relation to informational and social values are central sources of the motivation of consumers to interact on brand social media. Marketers and firms should focus on enhancing the value perceptions of consumers when it comes to brands on social media. It is important to develop informational value by regularly posting informative content about financial services. This can be achieved through blogs, micro-blogs, product reviews, post purchase reviews and by encouraging group participation, comments, sharing and interacting with brand posts. Users should be driven to share personal experiences, offer socio-emotional support and pool resources. Similarly, an important factor which changes the mind-set and leads to imperative purchase decision making is

content interactivity and the economic benefits associated with products and services such as rewards, bonuses and discounts associated.

Consumer interactions in SNS brand communities cultivate multiple benefits for companies such as greater engagement with brand content and brand loyalty. Most importantly it influences a change in the attitudes and opinions of online users about the products and services which subsequently elicit purchase intentions. Behavioral transformation is the outcome of the uniformity of beliefs, values and intentions, and is subjected to the acceptance of social influence, social complaisance, value-incorporation and self-fulfilment. The implicit value of such social influence enables the marketer to achieve multiple consumer behavioral outcomes. For example, consumers join brand communities and engage in these with an expectation of reward and benefit. The greater the promotional benefits, such as discount offers on financial services, the higher the level of engagement and trust in the brand. This is achieved when users conform to the majority opinion (best-selling, top-rated, most liked, shared and commented posts) and react to positive views about the brand. Further, marketers should support consumer-brand relationships through social collaborative learning in the form of consumer participation in brand activities to receive and share information, and to answer questions about financial services (e.g. mortgage, credit cards, travel insurance, car finance, personal loans etc.). Members enjoy providing technical help and support to others who are using mobile apps. Such consumer-brand engagement instigates long-term changes in behavior through informational conformity as individuals incorporate social collaborative learning values into their own value system. Furthermore, social media brand communities and groups are also used as customer service platforms where consumers communicate with companies, forwarding their suggestions or complaints. This contrasts with traditional channels for customer services. Based on these aspects, members of social media brand groups and communities identify themselves with the brand by showing a sense of moral responsibility to remain active in the group. They play an active part in promotion and expansion. Additionally, such behavioral modelling strategies in the context of social influence develop a sense of self-fulfilment amongst consumers, resulting in strong brand identity, loyalty and association with brand.

For marketers, the benefit of a change in consumers' attitudes and behaviors is the development of trust, loyalty and satisfaction with brand. As multiple levels of social influence develops, the online verbal evidence significantly enhances sales and the market share of a company. Online verbal evidence (eWOM) defines brand worth, authenticity and the value companies place in consumers. As a result, online verbal evidence (eWOM) is generated and transmitted on social media which is considered more reliable and authentic than traditional persuasive messages and promotions generated by companies. Marketers can use such verbal evidence about financial services for financial gains, since online verbal evidence takes the form of consumer-generated information recommendations based on the outcome of their real-life buying decisions. Many consumers seek such verbal evidence to inform their purchase decisions.

6.5. Limitations and Future Guidelines

The study adopted a qualitative research method to investigate the role of social media on consumer purchase intentions in the financial service industry. The study adopted a case study research strategy and used the social constructionism paradigm to investigate the phenomenon. This justifies the appropriate use of research methods. The use of a qualitative, case-based methodology involved information rich qualitative data collection through semi-structured interviews and focus group interviews. Thematic analysis yielded six major themes to underscore how heterogeneous social media interactions develop multiple levels of social influence which transform purchase intentions. Therefore, the qualitative methodology adopted in the study helped in terms of generalising the finding of this study which looked at the role of social media in consumer purchase intentions in the financial services industry. The qualitative investigation helped to conceptualise the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions in the context of social influence theory. Such qualitative inquiry further helped develop a conceptual model of the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions using social influence theory.

Future research, however, could add more value to the literature if the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions is studied using the positivist paradigm and a quantitative method of data collection and analysis. Furthermore, a mixed method research strategy could also build

towards understanding the phenomenon in the financial services industry. The limitations of the study are also noted, and more value could be added if the impact of social media on consumer purchase intentions was measured in new contexts, away from the financial services industry. The research suggests that the role of social media in consumer purchase intentions could yield different results when studied in different theoretical contexts. Furthermore, future investigation should be conducted on a time-series basis, rather than based on cross sectional analysis. In this way it is possible to accurately predict how social media could transform consumers purchase intentions when studied in multiple contexts.

7. References

- Abdullah, D., Jayaraman, K., and Kamal, S.B.M. (2016). A Conceptual model of interactive hotel website: The role of perceived website interactivity and customer perceived value toward website revisit intention. *Procedia economics and finance, the fifth international conference on marketing and retailing (5th INCOMaR)* 37, pp. 170-175.
- Achrol, R. S. (1997). Changes in the theory of inter-organizational relations: Toward a network paradigm. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 25(1), pp. 56–71.
- Adams, W.C. (2010). Conducting semi-structured interviews. In Wholey JS, Hatry HP and Newcomer KE. *Handbook of Practical program evaluation*. San Francisco: John Wiley and Sons
- Alarcón, C.N., Sepúlveda, A.N., Valenzuela-Fernández, L., and Gil-Lafuent, J. (2018). Systematic mapping on social media and its relation to business. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 24(2), pp. 104-113.
- Aiello, L., Barrat, A., Cattuto, C., Schifanella, R., and Ruffo, G. (2012). Link creation and information spreading over social and communication ties in an interest-based online social network. *EPJ Data Science*, 1(1).
- Aitken, R., Gray, B., and Lawson, R. (2008). Advertising effectiveness from a consumer perspective. *International Journal of Advertising*, 27(2), pp. 279–297.
- Airasian, P., and L. R. Gay. (2000). *Educational Research: Competencies for Analysis and Application Sixth Edition*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall Inc.
- Akehurst, G. (2008). User generated content: the use of blogs for tourism organisations and tourism consumers. *Service Business*, 3(1), pp.51-61.
- Alalwan, A.A., Rana, N.P., Dwivedi, Y.K., and Algharabat, R. (2017). Social media in marketing: A review and analysis of the existing literature. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34 (7), pp. 1177-1190.
- Alalwan, A.A. (2018). Investigating the impact of social media advertising features on customer purchase intention. *International Journal of Information Management*, 42, pp. 65-77.
- Alboqami, H., Karaghoul, W., Baeshen, Y., Erkan, I., Evans, C., and Ghoneim, A. (2015). Electronic word of mouth in social media: the common characteristics of retweeted and favoured marketer-generated content posted on Twitter. *International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising*, 9(4), pp.338.

- Algesheimer, R., Dholakia, U.M., and Herrmann, A. (2005). The social influence of brand community: Evidence from European car clubs. *Journal of Marketing*, 69(4), pp. 19-34.
- Aldrich, D., and Meyer, M. (2014). Social Capital and Community Resilience. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 59(2), pp.254-269.
- Al-ghamdi, H.A.K., and Al-ghamdi, A.A.K. (2015). The Role of virtual Communities of Practice in Knowledge Management Using Web 2.0. *Procedia Computer Science*, 65, pp. 406-411.
- Alsaleh, D. A., Elliott, M. T., Fu, F. Q., and Thakur, R. (2019). Cross-cultural differences in the adoption of social media. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 13, pp. 119–140.
- Ansarin, M., and Ozuem, W. (2014). Social media and online brand communities. In Bowen, G. and Ozuem, W. (eds.) *Computer-Mediated Marketing Strategies: Social Media and Online Brand Communities*. Hershey, IGI Global, pp. 1-27.
- Andrews, T. (2012). What is social constructionism? *The Grounded Theory Review*, 11(1). pp. 39-46.
- Arrigo, E. (2014). Social media opportunities for market-driven firms in I. Lee (Ed.), *Integrating social media into business practice, applications, management, and models*. Hershey: IGI Global, PA, pp. 180-199.
- Asch, S. E. (1956). Studies of Independence and Conformity: I. A Minority of One against a Unanimous Majority. *Psychological Monographs: General and Applied*, 70(9), pp.1–70.
- Augusto, M. Torres, P. (2018). Effects of brand attitude and eWOM on consumers' willingness to pay in the banking industry: Mediating role of consumer-brand identification and brand equity. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 42, pp. 1-10.
- Azjan, (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Process*, 50, pp. 179-211.
- Azemi, Y., and Ozuem, W. (2014). Social media and SMEs in transition countries. In Bowen, G. and Ozuem, W. (eds.) *Computer-mediated marketing strategies: social media and online brand communities*, IGI Publication, pp.144-133.
- Azemi, Y., Ozuem, W., Howell, K.E., and Lancaster, G. (2019). An exploration into the practice of online service failure and recovery strategies in the Balkans. *Journal of Business Research*, 49, pp. 420-431.
- Bai, Y., Yao, Z., and Dou, Y.F., (2015). Effect of social commerce factors on user purchase behavior: An empirical investigation from renren.com. *International Journal of Information Management* 35(5), pp.538–550.

- Balaji, M., Khong, K., and Chong, A. (2016). Determinants of negative word-of-mouth communication using SNSs. *Information & Management*, 53(4), pp.528-540.
- Bagozzi, R.P. (2000). The Self-Regulation of Attitudes, Intentions, and Behavior. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 55(2), pp. 178-204.
- Bagozzi, R. (2000). On the Concept of Intentional Social Action in Consumer Behavior. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 27(3), pp.388-396.
- Bagozzi, R.P., and Lee, K-H. (2002). Multiple Routes for Social Influence: The Role of Compliance, Internalization, and Social *Social Psychology Quarterly*, Vol. 65, No. 3 pp. 226-247
- Bagozzi, R. P. (2007). The legacy of the technology acceptance model and a proposal for a paradigm shift. *Journal of the Association of Information Systems* (4).
- Bagozzi, R., and Dholakia, U. (2002). Intentional social action in virtual communities. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 16(2), pp. 2-21.
- Bagozzi, R.P., Dholakia, U.P., and Mookerjee, A. (2006). Individual and Group Bases of Social Influence in Online Environments. *Media Psychology*, 8(2), pp. 95-126.
- Bamberg, S., Hunecke, M., and Blöhbaum. (2007). Social context, morality and the use of public transportation: Results from two field studies. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 27, pp. 190-203.
- Barreda, A.A., Bilgihan, A., and Kageyama, Y. (2015). The Role of Trust in Creating Positive Word of Mouth and Behavioral Intentions: The Case of Online Social Networks. *Journal of Relationship Marketing*, 14(1), pp. 16-36.
- Barratt, M., Choi, T., and Li, M. (2011). Qualitative case studies in operations management: Trends, research outcomes, and future research implications. *Journal of Operations Management*, 29(4), pp.329-342.
- Bauer, M. W. (2008). Social influence by artefacts. *Diogenes*, 55, pp. 68–83.
- Barreda, A., Bilgihan, A., Nusair, K., and Okumus, F. (2015). Generating brand awareness in Online Social Networks. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 50, pp.600-609.
- Baird, C.L., and Parasnis, G. (2011). From social media to Social CRM: reinventing the customer relationship. *Strategy & Leadership*, 39(6), pp.27-34.
- Beverland, M., and Lindgreen, A. (2010). What makes a good case study? A positivist review of qualitative case research published in *Industrial Marketing Management*, 1971–2006. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 39(1), pp.56-63.
- Bearden, W., Netemeyer, R., and Teel, J. (1989). Measurement of Consumer Susceptibility to Interpersonal Influence. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 15(4), pp. 473.

- Berkelaar, B. L. (2014). Cybervetting, online information, and personnel selection: New transparency expectations and the emergence of a digital social contract. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 26, pp. 377–403.
- Bergami, M., and Bagozzi, R.P. (2000). Self-categorization, affective commitment and group self-esteem as distinct aspects of social identity in the organization. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 39(4), pp. 555-577.
- Berger, P., and Luckmann, T. (1967). *The social construction of reality*. Penguin Publishers.
- Berthon, P.R., Pitt, L., and Campbell, C. (2008). Ad lib: When customers create the ad. *California Management Review*, 50(4), pp. 6–31.
- Berthon, P.R. , Pitt, L.F. , Plangger, K., and Shapiro, D. (2012). Marketing meets Web 2.0, social media, and creative consumers: Implications for international marketing strategy. *Business Horizons*, 55, pp. 261-271.
- Beukeboom, C.J., Kerkhof, P., and Vries, M.(2015). Does a Virtual Like Cause Actual Liking? How Following a Brand's Facebook Updates Enhances Brand Evaluations and Purchase Intention. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 32, pp. 26-36.
- Bhatli D., and Mejri C.A. (2015). The Influence of Social Media on Consumption Practices. In: Kubacki K. (eds) *Ideas in Marketing: Finding the New and Polishing the Old. Developments in Marketing Science: Proceedings of the Academy of Marketing Science*. Springer.
- Billig, M. (1987). *Arguing and thinking*. Cambridge, England: CambridgeUniversity Press.
- Bikhchandani, S., Hirshleifer, D., and Welch, I. (1992). A Theory of Fads, Fashion, Custom, and Cultural-Change as Informational Cascades. *Journal of Political Economy* 100(5), pp. 992–1026.
- Bird, E.L., Panter, J., Baker, G., Jones, T., and Ogilvie, D. (2018) Predicting walking and cycling behaviour change using an extended TPB. *Journal of Transport & Health*, pp. 2214-1405.
- Błachnio, A., Przepiórka, A. and Rudnicka, P. (2013). Psychological determinants of using Facebook: A research review. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 29, pp. 775–787.
- Blanchard, A. L. (2008). Testing a model of sense of virtual community. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24(5), pp. 2107–2123.
- Bojars, U., Breslin, J.G, Finn, A., and Decker, S. (2008). Using the Semantic Web for linking and reusing data across Web 2.0 communities. *Journal of Web Semantics*, 6, pp. 21-28.

- Bond, R. M., Fariss, C. J., Jones, J. J., Kramer, A. D., Marlow, C., Settle, J. E., and Fowler, J. H. (2012). A 61-Million-Person Experiment in Social Influence and Political Mobilization. *Nature*, 489(7415), pp. 295–98.
- Boyd, D. (2008). Why youth (heart) social network sites: the role of networked publics in teenage social life. In Buckingham, D. (ed.) *Youth, Identity, and Digital Media*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press, pp. 119–142.
- Bonson, E., and Flores, F. (2011). Social media and corporate dialogue: the response of global financial institutions. *Online Information Review*, 35(1), pp. 34-49.
- Boyd, D., and Ellison, N.B. (2007). Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), pp. 210-230.
- Brengarth, L., and Mujkic, E. (2016). WEB 2.0: How social media applications leverage nonprofit responses during a wildfire crisis. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 54, pp.589-596.
- Brewer, M. B. (1979). In-group bias in the minimal intergroup situation: A cognitive-motivational analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 86(2), pp. 307-324.
- Briley, D., Morris, M., and Simonson, I. (2000). Reasons as Carriers of Culture: Dynamic versus Dispositional Models of Cultural Influence on Decision Making. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 27(2), pp.157-178.
- Brown J.S., Collins, A., and Duguid, P. (1989). Situated cognition and the culture of learning. *Educational researcher*, 18(1), pp.32-42.
- Brodie, R.J., Hollebeek, L.D., Juric, B., and Ilic, A. (2011). Customer Engagement: Conceptual Domain, Fundamental Propositions, and Implications for Research. *Journal of Service Research*, 14, pp. 252-271.
- Brodie, R. J., Ilic, A., Juric, B., and Hollebeek, L. (2013). Consumer engagement in a virtual brand community: An exploratory analysis. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(1), pp. 105–114.
- Bryman, A., and Bell, E. (2007). Planning a research project and formulating research questions. *In: Business Research Methods*. New York. *Oxford University Press*. pp. 75-92.
- Bukovina, J. (2016). Social Media and Capital Markets. An Overview. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 31, pp. 70-78.
- Burnkrant, R.E., and Cousineau, A. (1975). Informational and Normative Social Influence in Buyer Behavior. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 2(3), pp. 206-215.

Can, L. and Kaya, N. (2016). SNSs Addiction and the Effect of Attitude towards Social Network Advertising. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 235, pp. 484-492.

Cialdini, R. B., and Goldstein, N. J. (2004). Social influence: Compliance and conformity. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 55, pp. 591-621.

Carr, C.T., Wohn, Y.D., and Hayes, R.A. (2016). As social support: Relational closeness, automaticity, and interpreting social support from paralinguistic digital affordances in social media. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 62, pp. 385-393.

Carmichael, D., Archibald, J. and Lund, G. (2015). Social Capital Theory in Social Media Research. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.

Casaló, L. V., Flavián, C. Guinalú. M. (2010). Determinants of the intention to participate in firm-hosted online travel communities and effects on consumer behavioral intentions. *Tourism Management*, 31(6), pp. 898–911.

Casaló, L.V., Falvián, C., and Guinaliu, M. (2013). New members' integration: key factors of success in online travel communities. *Journal of Business Research*, 66, pp. 706-710.

Çelen, B., and Kariv, S. (2004). Distinguishing informational cascades from herd behavior in the laboratory. *American Economic Review*, 94(3), pp. 484–498.

Chai, S., and Kim, M. (2010). What makes bloggers share knowledge? An investigation on the role of trust. *International Journal of Information Management*, 30(5), pp. 408–415.

Charmaz, K. (2006). *Constructing grounded theory: A practical guide through qualitative analysis*. London: Sage Publications.

Chan, M. (2014). Social identity gratifications of social network sites and their impact on collective action participation. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 17(3), pp. 229-235.

Chen, H., and Li, X. (2017). The contribution of mobile social media to social capital and psychological well-being: Examining the role of communicative use, friending and self-disclosure. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 75, pp. 958-965.

Chan, N.L., and Guillet, B.D. (2011). Investigation of Social Media Marketing: How Does the Hotel Industry in Hong Kong Perform in Marketing on Social Media Websites?, *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 28(4), pp. 345-368.

Chan, Y. Y. Y., and Ngai, E. W. T. (2011). Conceptualising electronic word of mouth activity: An input-process-output perspective. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 29(5), pp. 488–516.

- Chang, H.H., and Wang, I.C. (2008). An investigation of user communication behavior in computer mediated environments. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24(5), pp. 2336-2356.
- Chang, Y. P., and Zhu, D. H. (2011). Understanding SNSs adoption in China: A comparison of pre-adoption and post-adoption. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27(5), pp. 1840–1848.
- Chang, A., Hsieh, S.H., and Tseng, T.H. (2013). Online brand community response to negative brand events: the role of group eWOM. *Internet Research*, 23 (4), pp. 486-506.
- Chang R.M., Kauffman, R.J., and Kwon Y.O. (2014). Understanding the paradigm shift to computational social science in the presence of big data. *Decision Support Systems*, 6, pp. 67-80.
- Chang, Y.T., Yu, H., and Lu, H.P. (2015). Persuasive messages, popularity cohesion, and message diffusion in social media marketing. *Journal of Business Research*, 68(4), pp. 777-782.
- Charmaz, K. (2011). *Constructing grounded theory. A practical guide through qualitative analysis* (Vol. 3). London: Sage.
- Chen, Y.H., Hsu, I.C., and Lin, C.C. (2010). Website attributes that increase consumer purchase intention: A conjoint analysis. *Journal of Business Research*, 63(9), pp. 1007-1014.
- Chevalier, J., and Mayzlin, D. (2006). The Effect of Word of Mouth on Sales: Online Book Reviews. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 43(3), pp.345-354.
- Chen, C-C., Hsiao, K-L., and Wu, S.J. (2018). Purchase intention in social commerce: An empirical examination of perceived value and social awareness. *Library Hi Tech*, 36(4), pp.583-604.
- Chen, J.V., Yen, D.C., Kuo, W-R., and Capistrano, E.P.S. (2016). The antecedents of purchase and repurchase intentions of online auction consumers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 54, pp. 186-196.
- Cheung, M., Luo, C., Sia, C., and Chen, H. (2009). Credibility of EWOM: Informational and Normative Determinants of On-line Consumer Recommendations. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 13(4), pp. 9-38.
- Cheung, C.M., and Lee, M.K. (2010). A theoretical model of intentional social action in online social networks. *Decision Support Systems*, 49, pp. 24–30.
- Cheung, C. M., Chiu, P. Y., & Lee, M. K. (2011). Online social networks: Why do students use facebook? *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27, pp. 1337–1343.
- Cheung, M., and To, W. (2016). Service co-creation in social media: An extension of the theory of planned behavior. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 65, pp. 260-266.

- Cheung, C., and Thadani, D. (2012). The impact of eWOM communication: A literature analysis and integrative model. *Decision Support Systems*, 54(1), pp.461-470
- Cheung, C.M.K., and Lee, M.K.O. (2012). What drives consumers to spread electronic word of mouth in online consumer-opinion platforms. *Decision Support Systems*, (53)1, pp. 218-225.
- Cialdini, R.B., and Goldstein, N.J (2004). Social influence: Compliance and conformity. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 55, pp. 591–621.
- Chiu, C-M., Hsu, M-H., and Wang E.T.G. (2006). Understanding knowledge sharing in virtual communities: An integration of social capital and social cognitive theories. *Decision Support Systems*, 42(3), pp. 1872-1888.
- Christodoulides, G. (2009). Branding in the post-internet era. *Marketing Theory*, 9(1), pp. 141-144.
- Chu, S.C., and Kim, Y. (2011). Determinants of consumer engagement in eWOM (eWOM) in SNSs. *International Journal of Advertising*, 30, pp. 47-75.
- Chu, S-H. (2011). Viral advertising in social media: participation in Facebook groups and responses among college-aged users. *Journal of interactive advertising*, 12(1), pp. 30-43.
- Chu, S. C., and Choi, S. M. (2011). EWOM in SNSs: A cross-cultural study of the United States and China. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 24(3), pp. 263– 281.
- Chu, S.-C., and Kim, Y. (2011). Determinants of consumer engagement in eWOM (eWOM) in SNSs. *International Journal of Advertising*, 30(1), pp. 47-75.
- Cheung, C.M.K., Chiu, P-Y., and Lee, M.K.O. (2011). Online Social Networks: Why Do Students Use Facebook? *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27(4), pp. 1337-1343.
- Cheung, C.M., Xiao, B.S., and Liu, I.L. (2014). Do actions speak louder than voices? The signaling role of social information cues in influencing consumer purchase decisions. *Decision Support Systems*, 65, pp. 50-58.
- Chiou, J.-S. (1998). The effects of attitude, subjective norm, and perceived behavioral control on consumers' purchase intentions: The moderating effects of product knowledge and attention to social comparison information. *Proceedings of the National Science Council*, 9, pp. 298-308.
- Chong, A., Lacka, E., Boying, L., and Chan, H. (2018). The role of social media in enhancing guanxi and perceived effectiveness of E-commerce institutional mechanisms in online marketplace. *Information & Management*, 55(5), pp. 621-632.
- Choi, B., and Lee, I. (2017). Trust in open versus closed social media: The relative influence of user- and marketer- generated content in social network services on customer trust. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(5), pp. 550-559.

- Chun, J.W.S., and Lee, M.J. (2016). Increasing individuals' involvement and WOM intention on SNSs: Content matters!. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 60, pp. 223-232.
- Christodoulides, G., Jevons, C., and Bonhomme, J. (2012). Memo to marketers: quantitative evidence for change: how UGC really affects brands. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 52.
- Constantinides, E., and Fountain, S. (2008). Web 2.0: Conceptual foundations and marketing issues. *Journal of Direct, Data and Digital Marketing Practice*, 9(3), pp. 231-244.
- Coyne, I.T. (1997). Sampling in qualitative research. Purposeful and theoretical sampling; merging or clear boundaries? *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 26, pp. 623–30.
- Cox, C., Burgess, S., Sellitto, C., and Buultjens, J. (2008). *Consumer-Generated Web-based Tourism Marketing*. Queensland, Australia: Sustainable Tourism Cooperative Research Centre.
- Creswell, J. W., and Miller, D. L. (2000). Determining validity in qualitative inquiry. *Theory into practice*, 39:3, pp. 124-130.
- Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *A concise introduction to mixed methods research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage
- Crowston, K., and fagnot, I. (2018). Stages of motivation for contributing UGC: A theory and empirical test. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 109, pp. 89-101.
- Crouch, M., and McKenzie, H. (2006). The logic of small samples in interview-based qualitative research. *Social Science Information*, 45(4), pp. 483-499.
- Curty, R.G., and Zhang, P. (2013). Website features that gave rise to social commerce: a historical analysis. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 12(4), pp. 260-279.
- Currás-Pérez, R., Ruiz-Mafé, C., and Sanz-Blas, S. (2013). Social network loyalty: evaluating the role of attitude, perceived risk and satisfaction. *Online Information Review*, 37(1), pp. 61-82.
- Darker, C.D., French, D.P., Eves, F.F., and Sniehotta, F.F. (2010). An intervention to promote walking amongst the general population based on an 'extended' theory of planned behavior: a waiting list randomised controlled trial. *Psychology and Health*, 25(1), pp. 71-88.
- Daugherty, T., M. Eastin., and L. Bright. (2008). Exploring Consumer Motivations for Creating UGC. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 8(2), pp. 16–25.

- Dang, Y., Zhang, Y., Jen-HwaHu, P. brown, S.A. Ku, Y.C., Wang, J., and Chen, H. (2014). An integrated framework for analyzing multilingual content in Web 2.0 social media. *Decision Support Systems*, 61, pp. 126-135.
- Davis, C. H. F., Canche, M. S. G., Deil-Amen, R., and Rios-Aguilar, C. (2012). *Social Media in Higher Education: A Literature Review and Research Directions*. Arizona: The Center for the Study of Higher Education at the University of Arizona and Claremont Graduate University.
- De Bruyn, A., and Lilien, G. (2008). A multi-stage model of word-of-mouth influence through viral marketing. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 25(3), pp. 151-163.
- de Gregorio, F., and Sung, Y. (2010). Understanding Attitudes Toward and Behaviors in Response to Product Placement. *Journal of Advertising*, 39(1), pp. 83-96.
- Degroot, M. H. (1974). Reaching a Consensus. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 69, pp. 118–21.
- Denzin, N., and Lincoln, Y. (2002). *Handbook of qualitative research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Denzin, N. (2016). Critical Qualitative Inquiry. *Qualitative Inquiry*, 23(1), pp.8-16.
- De Valck, K., Van Bruggen, G., and Wierenga, B. (2009). Virtual communities: a marketing perspective. *Decision Support Systems*, 47(3), pp. 185-203.
- Dellarocas, C., Zhang, X., and Awad, N. (2007). Exploring the value of online product reviews in forecasting sales: The case of motion pictures. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 21(4), pp. 23.
- Dessart, L., Veloutsou, C., and Morgan-Thomas, A. (2015). Consumer engagement in online brand communities: A social media perspective. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 24(1), pp. 28–42.
- Deutsch, M., and Gerard.H.B. (1955). A Study of Normative and Informational Social Influences Upon Individual Judgment. *Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*, 51, pp. 629-636.
- Dicco-Bloom, B., and Crabtree, B.F. (2006). The qualitative research interview. *Medical education*, 40(4), pp. 314-321.
- Dillenbourg, P. (2008). Integrating technologies into educational ecosystems. *Distance Education*, 29(2), pp. 127-140.
- Dhir, A.M., Kaur, P., and Rajala, R. (2018). Why do young people tag photos on social Inetworking sites? Explaining user intentions. *International Journal of Information Management*, 38(1), pp. 117-127.

- Dholakia, U., Bagozzi, R., and Pearo, L. (2004). A social influence model of consumer participation in network- and small-group-based virtual communities. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 21(3), pp. 241-263.
- Dholakia, U.M., Blazevic, V., Wiertz, C., and Algesheimer, R. (2009). Communal service delivery: how customers benefit from participation in firm-hosted virtual P3 communities *Journal of Service Research*, 12, pp. 208-226
- Dolan, R., and Goodman, S. (2017). Succeeding on social media: Exploring communication strategies for wine marketing. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 33, pp. 23-30.
- Dootson, P., Beatson, A., and Drennan, J. (2016). Financial institutions using social media – do consumers perceive value?. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 34(1), pp.9-36.
- Duan, W., Gu, B., and Whinston, A. (2008). Do online reviews matter? — An empirical investigation of panel data. *Decision Support Systems*, 45(4), pp.1007-1016.
- Dworkin, S. (2012). Sample Size Policy for Qualitative Studies Using In-Depth Interviews. *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 41(6), pp. 1319-1320.
- Eisenhardt, K. (2007). Theory building from cases: opportunities and challenges. *Academy of Management Journal*, 50(1), pp. 25-32.
- Elwalda, A., Lü, K., and Ali, M. (2016). Perceived derived attributes of online customer reviews. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 56, pp. 306-319.
- El Ouiridi, M., Segers, J., El Ouiridi, A., and Pais, I. (2015). Predictors of job seekers' self-disclosure on social media. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 53, pp. 1-12.
- Erkan, I., and Evans, C. (2016). The influence of eWOM in social media on consumers' purchase intentions: An extended approach to information adoption. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 61, pp.47-55.
- Faci, N., Maamar, Z., Buregio, V., Uglijanin, E., and Benslimane., D. (2017). Web 2.0 applications in the workplace: How to ensure their proper use?. *Computers in Industry*, 88, pp. 1-11.
- Farzin., M. and Fattahi., M. (2018). eWOM through SNSs and impact on purchase intention and brand image in Iran. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 15(2), pp. 161-183.
- Felix, R., Rauschnabel., P. and Hinsch, C. (2017). Elements of strategic social media marketing: A holistic framework. *Journal of Business Research*, 70, pp. 118-126.
- Filip, D., Jackowicz, K., and Kozłowski, Ł. (2017). Influence of internet and social media presence on small, local banks' market power. *Baltic Journal of Economics*, 17(2), pp. 190-214.

Fishbein M., and Ajzen A. (1975). Beliefs, attitudes, intentions, and behavior: An introduction to theory and research. Reading, MA: Addison-Wesley.

Fishbein M. (1979). A theory of reasoned action: Some applications and implications. In: Howe HE Jr, Page MM, eds. (1979) *Nebraska Symposium on Motivation*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press. pp. 65–116.

Fisher, T. (2009). ROI in social media: A look at the arguments. *Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, 16(3), pp. 189–195.

Fischer, E., and Reuber, A. R. (2011). Social interaction via new social media: (How) can interactions on Twitter affect effectual thinking and behavior. *Journal of Business Venture*, 26, pp. 1–18.

Flanagin, A., and Metzger, M. (2006). Internet use in the contemporary media environment. *Human Communication Research*, 27(1), pp. 153-181.

Flanagin, A.J., Hocevar, K.P., and Samahito, S.N. (2012). Connecting with the user-generated Web: how group identification impacts online information sharing and evaluation. *Journal of Information and Communication society*, 17(6), pp. 683-694.

Flanigan, A., and Babchuk, W., (2015). Social media as academic quicksand: A phenomenological study of student experiences in and out of the classroom. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 44, pp. 40-45.

French Jr., J. R. P., and Raven, B. H. (1959). The bases of social power. In D. Cartwright (Ed.), *Studies in social power (pp. 150-167)*. Ann Arbor, MI: Institute for Social Research

Friedkin, N. E. (1998). A structural theory of social influence. New York, NY, US: Cambridge University Press

Friedkin, N., and Johnsen, E. (2011). Social Influence Network Theory. Cambridge Univ. Press, New York

Friedkin, N., Jia, P., and Bullo, F. (2016a). A theory of the evolution of social power: natural trajectories of interpersonal influence systems along issue sequences. *Social Science*, 3, pp. 444–472.

Fortin, D.R., and Dholakia, R.R. (2005). Interactivity and vividness effects of social presence and involvement with a web-based advertisement. *Journal of Business Research*, 58(3), pp. 387-396.

Füller, J. (2006). Why consumers engage in virtual new product developments initiated by producers. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 33, pp. 639-646.

Fuchs, C. (2010a). Alternative Media as Critical Media. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 13(2), pp. 173-192.

Fu, S., Yan, Q., and Feng, G.C. (2018). Who will attract you? Similarity effect among users on online purchase intention of movie tickets in the social shopping context. *International Journal of Information Management*, pp. 88-102.

Gao, Q., and Feng, C. (2016). Branding with social media: User gratifications usage patterns, and brand message content strategies. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 63, pp. 868-890.

Gallaughner, J., and Ransbotham, J. (2010). Social media and customer dialog management at Starbucks. *MIS Quarterly Executive*, 9(4), pp. 197-212.

Garrigos, F., Gil, I., and Narangajavana, Y. (2011). The impact of social networks in the competitiveness of the firms. In Beckford, A.M., and Larsen, J.P. (Eds), *Competitiveness: Psychology, Production, Impact and Global Trends*, Nova Science Publishers, Hauppauge, NY.

Gebauer, J., Füller, J., and Pezzeri, R. (2013). The dark and the bright side of co-creation: Triggers of member behavior in online innovation communities. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(9), pp. 1516–1527.

Gehlbach, H. (2010). The Social Side of School: Why Teachers Need Social Psychology. *Educational Psychology Review*, 22(3), pp. 349–362.

Gendel-Guterman, H., Levy, S. (201). Does consumers' personal involvement have an influence on store brand buying proneness? *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 30 (7), pp. 553-562.

Ghahtarani, A., Sheikhmohammady, M., and Rostami, M. (2020). The impact of social capital and social interaction on customers' purchase intention, considering knowledge sharing in social commerce context. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 5(3), pp.191-199.

Given, L. (2008). *The Sage encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. Los Angeles, Calif.: Sage Publications.

Goh, K.Y., Heng, C.S., and Lin, Z. (2013). Social media brand community and consumer behavior: quantifying the relative impact of user- and marketer-generated content. *Information Systems Research*, 24(1), pp. 88-107.

Goh, K.Y., Heng, C.S., and Lin, Z. (2013). Social media brand community and consumer behavior: quantifying the relative impact of user- and marketer-generated content. *Information Systems Research*, 24, pp. 88-107.

Godey, B., Manthiou, A., Pederzoli, D., Rokka, J., Aiello, G., Donvito, R., and Singh, R. (2016). Social media marketing efforts of luxury brands: Influence on equity and consumer behavior. *Journal of Business Research*, 69 (12), pp. 5833-5841.

Gorden, R. L. (1980). *Interviewing: Strategy, techniques, and tactics*. Homewood, IL: Dorsey Press.

- Green, J., Willis, K., Hughes, E., Small, R., Welch, N., Gibbs, L., and Daly, J. (2007). Generating best evidence from qualitative research: the role of data analysis. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health*, 31(6), pp. 545-550.
- Greenhow, C., and Robelia, B. (2009). Old communication, new literacies: Social network sites as social learning resources. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 14(4), pp. 1130-1161.
- Groeber, P., Schweitzer, F., and Press, K. (2009). How groups can foster consensus: the case of local cultures. *Artificial Societies and Social Simulation*. 12, pp. 1–22.
- Gruen, T.W., Osmonbekov, T., and Czaplewski, A.J. (2006). eWOM: The Impact of Customer-to-Customer Online Know-how Exchange on Customer Value and Loyalty. *Journal of Business Research*, 59(4), pp. 449-456.
- Gutiérrez-Cillán, J., Camarero-Izquierdo, C., and San José-Cabezudo, R. (2017). How brand post content contributes to user's Facebook brand-page engagement. The experiential route of active participation. *BRQ Business Research Quarterly*, 20(4), pp. 258-274.
- Habibi, M., Laroche, M. and Richard, M. (2014). The roles of brand community and community engagement in building brand trust on social media. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 37, pp. 152-161.
- Hansen, D. L., Shneiderman, B., and Smith, M. A. (2011). *Analyzing social media networks with NodeXL: Insights from a connected world*, Burlington, MA: Morgan Kaufmann.
- Hajli, M. (2014). A study of the impact of social media on consumers. *International Journal of Market Research*, 55(6).
- Hajli, N., and Lin, X. (2014). Exploring the security of information sharing on SNSs: the role of perceived control of information. *Journal of Business Ethics*, pp. 1-13.
- Hajli, N. (2015). Social commerce constructs and consumer's intention to buy. *International Journal of Information Management*, 35 (2), pp. 183-191.
- Hajli, N., Sims, J., Zadeh, A.H., and Richardm, M-O. (2017). A social commerce investigation of the role of trust in a social networking site on purchase intentions. *Journal of Business Research*, 71, pp. 133–141.
- Hammersley, M. (1992). *Routledge Revivals: What's Wrong With Ethnography?*. Routledge, London.
- Harrigan, P., Evers, U., Miles, M., and Daly, T. (2018). Customer engagement and the relationship between involvement, engagement, self-brand connection and brand usage intent. *Journal of Business Research*, 88, pp. 388-396.

Harrysson, M., Metayer, E., and Sarrazin, H. (2012). How ‘social intelligence’ can guide decisions. *McKinsey Quarterly*, pp. 1-9.

Harary, F. (1959). A Criterion for Unanimity in French’s Theory of Social Power. In Cartwright, D. (eds) *Studies in social power*, pp. 168–82. Ann Arbor Institute for Social Research.

Hardey, M. (2009). The social context of online market research: an introduction to sociability of social media. *International Journal of Market Research*, 51(4), pp. 562-4.

Harton, H.C., and Bullock, M. (2007). Dynamic Social Impact: A Theory of the Origins and Evolution of Culture. *Social and Personality Psychology Compass*, 1(1), pp. 521–540.

Hau, Y. S., and Kim, Y. G. (2011). Why would online gamers share their innovation-conducive knowledge in the online game user community? Integrating individual motivations and social capital perspectives. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27(2), pp. 956–970.

Hendler, J. (2009). Web 3.0 emerging. *Computer*, 42(1), pp. 111-113.

Henningsen , M.L.M., Henningsen , D.D., Cruz, M.G., and Morrill, J. (2003). Social influence in groups: A comparative application of relational framing theory and the elaboration likelihood model of persuasion. *Communication Monographs*, 70(3), pp. 175-197.

Hearn, G., Foth, M., and Gray, H. (2009). Applications and implementations of new media in corporate communications: an action research approach. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*, 14(1), pp. 49-61.

Helal, G., and Ozuem, W. (2017). *Social Identity Matters: Social Media and Brand Perceptions in the Fashion Apparel and Accessories Industries*. In Ozuem, W. and Azemi, Y. (eds.) *Digital Marketing Strategies for Fashion and Luxury Brands*. Hershey : IGI Global Publishers.

Hennig-Thurau, T., Wiertz, C., and Feldhaus, F. (2015). Does Twitter matter? The impact of microblogging word of mouth on consumers’ adoption of new movies. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(3), pp. 375-394.

Hennink, M., Hutter, I., and Bailey, A. (2011). *Qualitative research methods*. Los Angeles, Calif.: SAGE.

Herget, J., and Mader, I. (2009). Social software in external corporate communications – a conceptual approach towards measuring, assessment and optimization of Web 2.0 activity. In *Social software in der externen unternehmenskommunikation – ein gestaltungsansatz zur messung, bewertung und optimierung von Web 2.0-aktivita`ten*. *Information-Wissenschaft und Praxis*, 60(4), pp. 233-40.

- Herding, B.A. (2010). Social influence and economic decision-making: Socio-psychological and neuro scientific analyses. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Science*, 365, pp. 281–290.
- Hennig-Thurau, T., Wiertz, C., and Feldhaus, F. (2015). Does Twitter matter? The impact of microblogging word of mouth on consumers' adoption of new movies. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(3), pp. 375-394.
- Hibberd, F. (2011). *Unfolding social constructionism*. New York: Springer.
- Hinkin, T. R., and Schriesheim, C.A. (1989). *Development and application of new scales to measure the French and Raven (1959) bases of social power*. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 74(4), pp. 561-567,
- Hlebec, V. Manfreda, K.L., and Vehovar, V. (2015). The social support networks of internet users. *New Media & Society*, 8(1), pp. 9-32.
- Hoffman, D.L., and Novak, T.P. (1997). Marketing in hypermedia computer-mediated environments: conceptual foundations. *Journal of Marketing*, pp. 50-68.
- Hoffman, D. L., Novack, T. P., and Schlosser, A. E. (2003). Locus of control, web use, and consumer attitudes toward internet regulation. *Journal of Public Policy & Marketing*, 22, pp. 41-57.
- Hoffman, D.L., and Fodor, M. (2010). Can you measure the ROI of your social media marketing? *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 52(1), pp. 41-49.
- Hoffman, D. and Novak, T. (2013). Online Experience in Social Media: Two Paths to Feeling Close and Connected. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1990005> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1990005>
- Hollebeek, L.D., Glynn, M.S., and Brodie, R.J. (2014). Consumer brand engagement in social media: conceptualization, scale, development and validation. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 28(2), pp. 149-165.
- Ho, H. Y., and Chang, C. P. H., (2010). Influence of message trust in online word-of-mouth on consumer behavior - By the example of food blog. In: *International conference on electronics and information engineering*, Tianjin, CN, pp. 395– 399. Los Alamitos: IEEE.
- Holsapple, C., Hsiao, S., and Pakath, R. (2018). Business social media analytics: Characterization and conceptual framework. *Decision Support Systems*, 110, pp. 32-45.
- Homans, G. C. (1950). *The Human Group*. New York: Harcourt, Brace & World.

Hong, P. Y., and Ilardi, S. S. (2010). Structured and semi-structured clinical interviews. In W. E. Craighead, C. B. Nemeroff, & G. Gaskell (Eds.), *The Corsini Encyclopedia of Psychology and Behavioral Science (4th ed.)*. New York: Wiley.

Hsu-Hsien, C. (2011). Interactive Digital Advertising vs. Virtual Brand Community: Exploratory Study of User Motivation and Social Media Marketing Responses in Taiwan. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 12 (1), pp. 44–61.

Hsiao C.C., and Chiou J.S. (2015) Social Influence and Customer Loyalty in a Collaborative Community:. In: Kubacki K. (eds) *Ideas in Marketing: Finding the New and Polishing the Old. Developments in Marketing Science: Proceedings of the Academy of Marketing Science* : Springer Publishers

Huang, Y.H.C, Wu, F., and Huang, Q. (2017). Does research on digital public relations indicate a paradigm shift? An analysis and critique of recent trends. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(7), pp. 1364-1376.

Hutter, K., Hautz, J., Dennhardt, S., and Füller, J. (2013). The impact of user interactions in social media on brand awareness and purchase intention: the case of MINI on Facebook. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 22(5/6), pp. 342-351.

Hwang, Y. (2014). Understanding social influence theory and personal goals in e-learning. *Information Development*, 32(3), pp. 466-477.

Iankova, S., Davies, I., Archer-Brown, C., Marder, B., and Yau, A. (2019). A comparison of social media marketing between B2B, B2C and mixed business models. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 81, 169-179.

Irmak, C., Vallen, B., and Sen, S. (2010). You Like What I Like, but I Don't Like What You Like: Uniqueness Motivations in Product Preferences. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 37(3), pp.443-455.

Iyengar, R., Han, S., and Gupta, S. (2009). Do Friends Influence Purchases in a Social Network?. *Working Paper 09- 123*. Harvard Business school USA.

Jansen, B. J., Zhang, M., Sobel, K., and Chowdury, A. (2009). Twitter power: tweets as electronic word of mouth. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science & Technology*, 60(11), pp. 2169-2188.

Jin, S.A.A., and Phua, J. (2014). Following celebrities' tweets about brands: the impact of twitter-based eWOM on consumers' source credibility perception, buying intention, and social identification with celebrities. *Journal of Advertising*, 43, pp. 181-195.

- Jia, A., Shen, S., Li, D., and Chen, S. (2018). Predicting the implicit and the explicit video popularity in a User Generated Content site with enhanced social features. *Computer Networks*, 140, pp. 112-125.
- Jiang, Z., Chan, J., Tan, B., and Chua, W. (2010). Effects of Interactivity on Website Involvement and Purchase Intention. *Journal of the Association for Information Systems*, 11(1), pp. 34-59.
- Johnson, B.R., and Onwuegbuzie, A.J. (2004). Mixed Methods Research: A Research Paradigm Whose Time Has Come. *Educational Researcher*, 33(7), pp. 14-26.
- Jun, J., Kim, J., and Tang, L.R. (2017). Does Social Capital Matter on Social Media? An Examination into Negative e-WOM Toward Competing Brands. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 26(4), pp. 378-394.
- Kang, M., and Schuett, M. (2013). Determinants of Sharing Travel Experiences in Social Media. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 30(1-2), pp. 93-107.
- Kang, I. (2016). Web 2.0, UGC and citizen journalism: Revisiting South Korea's Oh my News model in the age of social media. *Telematics and Informatics*, 33(2), pp. 546-556.
- Kaplan, M. F., and Miller, C. E. (1987). Group decision making and normative versus informational influence: Effects of type of issue and assigned decision rule. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 53(2), pp. 306-313.
- Kaplan, A. M., and Haenlein, M. (2009b). Consumers, companies, and virtual social worlds: A qualitative analysis of Second Life. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 36(1), pp. 873—874.
- Kaplan, A. M., and Haenlein, M. (2010). Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of social media. *Business Horizons*, 53(1), pp. 59–68.
- Kaplan, A. M., and Haenlein, M. (2011). The early bird catches the news: Nine things you should know about micro-blogging. *Business Horizons*, 54(2), pp. 105-113.
- Katz, E., Gurevitch, M., and Haas, H. (1973). On the use of the mass media for important things. *American Sociological Review*, 38, pp. 164–181.
- Katz, E., Blumler, J.G., and Gurevitch, M. (1973-1974). Uses and Gratification Research. *The Public Opinion Quarterly*, 37, pp. 509-523.
- Karaduman, I. (2013). The effect of social media on personal branding efforts of top level executives. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 99, pp. 465-473.

- Karahasanovic, A., BaeBrandtzaeg, P., Heim, J., Luders, M., Vormeir, L., Pierson, J., Lievens, B., Jeroen, V., and Jans, G. (2009). Co-creation and UGC—elderly people’s user requirements. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 25(3), pp. 655-678.
- Karnowski, V., Leonhard, L., and Kümpel, A. (2017). Why Users Share the News: A Theory of Reasoned Action-Based Study on the Antecedents of News-Sharing Behavior. *Communication Research Reports*, 35(2), pp.91-100.
- Kelman, H. C. (1958). Compliance, identification, and internalization: Three processes of attitude change. *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 2(1), pp. 51-60.
- Kelman, H. C. (1974). Further Thoughts on the Processes of Compliance, Identification, and Internalization, In J. T. Tedeschi (eds) *Perspectives on Social Power*. Chicago: Aldine, pp. 126-171
- Kelman, H.C. (1961). Processes of Opinion Change. *Public Opinion Quarterly*, 25(1), pp. 57-78.
- Kelley, H. H. (1967). Attribution theory in social psychology. In D. Levine (Ed.), *Nebraska Symposium on Motivation*, 15, pp. 129–238. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press.
- Kelly, L., Kerr, G., and Drennan, J. (2010). Avoidance of Advertising in SNSs: The Teenage Perspective. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 10(2), pp. 16–27.
- Kim, J., Kang, S., and Lee, K. (2018). How social capital impacts the purchase intention of sustainable fashion products. *Journal of Business Research*.
- Kitzinger, J. (1995). Qualitative research: introducing focus groups. *British Medical Journal* 3(11), pp. 299–302.
- Kietzmann, J.H., Hermkens, K., McCarthy, I.P., and Silvestre, B.S. (2011). Social Media? Get Serious! Understanding the Functional Building Blocks of Social Media. *Business Horizons*, 54(1), pp. 241-251.
- Kircaburun, K., Alhabash, S., Tosuntaş, Ş., and Griffiths, M. (2018). Uses and Gratifications of Problematic Social Media Use Among University Students: a Simultaneous Examination of the Big Five of Personality Traits, Social Media Platforms, and Social Media Use Motives. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, pp. 1-23.
- Kim, J., Kwon, O., and Lee, D.H. (2017). Social influence of hubs in information cascade processes. *Management Decision*, 55(4), pp. 730-744.
- Kim, H-W., Gupta, S., and Koh, J., (2011) Investigating the intention to purchase digital items in social networking communities: A customer value perspective. *Information & Management*, 48(6), pp. 228–234.

- Kim, S., Kandampully, J., and Bilgihan, A. (2018). The influence of eWOM communications: An application of online social network framework. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 80, pp. 243-254.
- Kim, E., Lee, J., Sung, Y., and Choi, S. (2016). Predicting selfie-posting behavior on SNSs: An extension of theory of planned behavior. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 62, pp. 116-123.
- Kim, S., Lee, J., and Yoon, D. (2015). Norms in Social Media: The Application of Theory of Reasoned Action and Personal Norms in Predicting Interactions With Facebook Page Like Ads. *Communication Research Reports*, 32(4), pp. 322-331.
- Kim, E., Sung, Y., and Kang, H. (2014). Brand followers' retweeting behavior on Twitter: how brand relationships influence brand eWOM. *Computer in Human Behavior*, 37, pp. 18-25.
- Kim, A., and Ko, E. (2012). Do social media marketing activities enhance customer equity? An empirical study of luxury fashion brand. *Journal of Business Research*, 65(10), pp. 1480-1486.
- Kim, M.S., and James, J. (2016). The TPB and intention of purchase sport team licensed merchandise, *Sport, Business and Management: An International Journal*, 6(2), pp.228-243.
- Kim, A.J., and Johnson, K.K.P. (2016). Power of consumers using social media: Examining the influences of brand-related UGC on Facebook. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 58, pp. 98-108.
- Kim, D., Kim, S., and Choi, M. (2016). Why Young People use Social Media for Sports: A Uses and Gratifications Perspective. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 9(26),
- Kim, J., and Song, H. (2016). Celebrity's self-disclosure on Twitter and parasocial relationships: A mediating role of social presence. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 62, pp. 570-577.
- Kim, E., and Ham, S. (2016). Restaurants' disclosure of nutritional information as a corporate social responsibility initiative: customers' attitudinal and behavioral responses. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 55, pp. 96-106.
- Kim, N., and Kim W. (2018). Do your social media lead you to make social deal purchases? Consumer-generated social referrals for sales via social commerce. *International Journal of Information Management*, 39, pp. 38-48.
- Kjos A.L., Worley M.M., and Schommer J. C (2013). The social network paradigm and applications in pharmacy. *Research in Social Adm Pharmacey*. 9(4), pp. 353-369.
- Kliatchko, J. (2005). Towards a new definition of Integrated Marketing Communications (IMC). *International Journal of Advertising*, 24(1), pp. 7-34.
- Klimis, C. (2010). *Digital marketing: the gradual integration in retail banking*. *EFMA Journal*, 4(226), pp. 16-19.

- Knoll, J., Matthes, J., and Heiss, R. (2018). The social media political participation model. *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*, pp. 1-12.
- Kozinets, R., de Valck, K., Wojnicki, A., and Wilner, S. (2010). Networked Narratives: Understanding Word-of-Mouth Marketing in Online Communities. *Journal of Marketing*, 74(2), pp. 71-89.
- Kohli, C., Suri, R., and Kapoor, A. (2015). Will social media kill branding?. *Business Horizons*, 58(1), pp. 35-44.
- Kochanska (1994). Beyond Cognition: Expanding the Search for the Early Roots of Internalization and Conscience. *Developmental Psychology*, 30(2), pp. 20-22.
- Kotler, P., Keller, K.L., Brady, M., Goodman, M., and Hansens, T. (2009). *Marketing Management*. London: Pearson Education Limited.
- Konuk, F.A. (2018). The role of store image, perceived quality, trust and perceived value in predicting consumers' purchase intentions towards organic private label food. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 43, pp. 304-310.
- KPMG (2012). *International Annual review*. <https://home.kpmg.com/content/dam/kpmg/pdf/2013/12/kpmg-international-annual-review-2012.pdf>
- Krueger, R. (1994). *Focus groups (Vol. 2)*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Krueger R.A. (1994). *Focus Groups: A Practical Guide for Applied Research*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publication.
- Krueger, R.A., and Casey M.A. (2009). *Focus groups: a practical guide for applied research*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publishers.
- Kuan, K.K.Y., Zhong, Y., and Chau, P.Y.K. (2014) Informational and Normative Social Influence in Group-Buying: Evidence from Self-Reported and EEG Data. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 30(4), pp. 151-178.
- Kuhn, T. (1970). *The structure of scientific revolutions*. University of Chicago Press.
- Kujur, F., and Singh, S. (2017). Engaging customers through online participation in SNSs. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 22(1), pp. 16-24.
- Kupp, M., and Anderson, J. (2007). Zopa: Web 2.0 meets retail banking. *Business Strategy Review*, 18(3), pp. 11-17.

- Küster, I., Vila, N., and Canales, P. (2016). How does the online service level influence consumers' purchase intentions before a transaction? A formative approach. *European Journal of Management and Business Economics*, 25(3), pp.111-120.
- Kwon, E.S., Kim, E., Sung, Y., and Yoo, C.Y. (2014). Brand followers: consumer motivation and attitude towards brand communications on Twitter. *International journal of Advertising*, 33, pp. 657-680.
- Kwon, K.H., Stefanone, M.A., and Barnett, G.A. (2014). Social network influence on online behavioral choices exploring group formation on social network sites. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 58(10), pp. 1345-1360.
- Labrecque, L. (2014). Fostering Consumer–Brand Relationships in Social Media Environments: The Role of Parasocial Interaction. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 28(2), pp. 134-148.
- Laroche, M., Habibi, M.R., Richard, M.O., and Sankaranarayanan, R. (2012). The effects of social media based brand communities on brand community markers, value creation practices, brand trust and brand loyalty. *Computer in Human Behavior*, 28, pp. 1755-1767.
- Laroche, M., Habibi, M. R., and Richard, M.-O. (2013). To be or not to be in social media: How brand loyalty is affected by social media? *International Journal of Information Management*, 33(1), pp. 76-82.
- Lau, M.M., Lam, A.Y.C., and Cheung, R. (2016). Examining the Factors Influencing Purchase Intention of Smartphones in Hong Kong. *Contemporary Management Research*, 12(2), pp. 213-224.
- Latané, B. (1981). The psychology of social impact. *American Psychologist*, 36(4), pp. 343-356.
- Latané, B., and Liu, J. H. (1996). The intersubjective geometry of social space. *Journal of Communication*, 46, pp. 26–34.
- Latané, B., Liu, J. H., Nowak, A., Bonevento, M., and Zheng, L. (1995). Distance matters: Physical space and social impact. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 21, pp. 795–805.
- Laestadius, L.I., and Wahl, M.M. (2017). Mobilizing social media users to become advertisers: Corporate hashtag campaigns as a public health concern. *Digital Health*, 3, pp. 1–12.
- Lee, M., and Youn, S. (2009). Electronic word of mouth (eWOM) How eWOM platforms influence consumer product judgment. *International Journal of Advertising*, 28, pp. 473-499.
- Lee, J. (2017). Social capital expectation and usage of social media: the moderating role of social capital susceptibility. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 36(10), pp. 1067-1080.

- Lee, J., and Lee, J. (2009). Understanding the product information inference process in eWOM: An objectivity–subjectivity dichotomy perspective. *Information & Management*, 46(5), pp. 302-311.
- Lee, H. (2011). The role of descriptive norm within the theory of planned behavior in predicting Korean Americans' exercise behavior. *Psychological Reports*, 109(1), pp. 208-218.
- Lee, M.K.O., Shi, N., and Cheung, C.M.K. (2011). Consumer's decision to shop online: the moderating role of positive informational social influence. *Information Management*, 48(6), pp. 185-191.
- Lempert, P. (2006). Caught in the Web. *Progressive Grocer*, 85(12), pp. 15–28.
- Leeraphong, A., and Mardjo, A. (2013, November). Trust and Risk in Purchase Intention through Online Social Network: A Focus Group Study of Facebook in Thailand. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 1(4), pp. 314-318.
- Lee, E., and Shin, S. (2014). When do consumers buy online product reviews? Effects of review quality, product type, and reviewer's photo. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 31, pp. 356-366.
- Leenders, R. T. A. J. (2002). Modeling social influence through network autocorrelation: Constructing the weight matrix. *Social Networks*, 24, pp. 21–47.
- Lee, K.T., and Koo, D.L. (2015). Evaluating right versus just evaluating online consumer reviews. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 45, pp. 316-327.
- Lee, Y-C. (2017). Effects of branded e-stickers on purchase intentions: The perspective of social capital theory. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(1), pp. 397-411.
- Lee, I. (2018). Social media analytics for enterprises: Typology, methods, and processes. *Business Horizons*, 61(2), pp. 199-210.
- Leiner, D.J., Kobilke, L., Rueb, C., and Brosius., H-B.(2018). Functional domains of social media platforms: Structuring the uses of Facebook to better understand its gratifications. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 83, pp. 194-203.
- Lehrer, K. (1975). Social Consensus and Rational Agnoiology. *Synthese*, 31, pp. 141–60.
- Levin, T., and Wagner, T.(2009). Mixed-methodology Research in Science Education: Opportunities and Challenges in Exploring and Enhancing Thinking Dispositions. In: *Dr. Mack C. Shelley II, Dr. Larry D. Yore & Hand, D. B. (Eds.) Quality Research in Literacy and Science Education*. Dordrecht The Netherlands: Springer.
- Li, K., Wang, X., Li, K., and Che, J. (2016). Information privacy disclosure on social network sites. *Nankai Business Review International*, 7(3), pp. 282-300.

- Li, C., and Bernoff, J. (2008). *Groundswell: winning in a world transformed by social technologies 1st Edition*. Harvard Business School Press
- Lin, M. J. J., Hung, S. W., and Chen, C. J. (2009). Fostering the determinants of knowledge sharing in professional virtual communities. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 25(4), pp. 929–939.
- Liamputtong, P. (2009). Qualitative data analysis: conceptual and practical considerations. *Health Promotion Journal of Australia*, 20(2), pp. 133-139
- Libai, B., Bolton, R., Bugel, M.S., de Ruyter, K., Gotz, O., Resselada, H., and Stephene, A.T. (2010). Customer-to-customer interactions: broadening the scope of word of mouth research. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 13, pp. 267-282.
- Liao, S., and Chou, E. (2012). Intention to adopt knowledge through virtual communities: posters vs lurkers. *Online Information Review*, 36(3), pp. 442-461.
- Lin, H., and Chang, C. (2018). What motivates health information exchange in social media? The roles of the social cognitive theory and perceived interactivity. *Information & Management*, 55(6), pp. 771-780.
- Liu, D., and Campbell, W. (2017). The Big Five personality traits, Big Two metatraits and social media: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 70, pp. 229-240.
- Lin, R., and Utz, S. (2017). Self-disclosure on SNS: Do disclosure intimacy and narrativity influence interpersonal closeness and social attraction?. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 70, pp. 426-436.
- Li, D., Browne, G.J., and Wetherbe, J.C. (2006). Why do Internet users stick with a specific web site? A relationship perspective. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 10, pp. 105-141.
- Li, M., Wang, X., Gao, K., and Zhang, S. (2017). A survey on information diffusion in online social networks: Models and methods. *Information*, 8, pp. 1–21.
- Liao, S., and Chu, H. (2013). Influence of consumer online resale awareness on purchase decisions: a mental accounting perspective. *European Journal of Marketing*, 47(10), pp.1576-1597.
- Litvin, S.W., Goldsmith, R.E., and Pan, B. (2008). EWOM in Hospitality and Tourism Management. *Tourism Management*, 29, pp. 458-468.
- Liang, C., Chen, H., and Wang, W. (2008). Does online relationship marketing enhance customer retention and cross-buying?. *The Service Industries Journal*, 28(6), pp. 769-87.
- Li, K., Zhang, L., and Huang, H. (2018). Social Influence Analysis: Models, Methods, and Evaluation. *Engineering*, 4, pp. 40–46.

- Liang, C., and Chen, H. (2009). How to lengthen, deepen and broaden customer-firm relationships with online financial services. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 14(3), pp. 218-31.
- Liu, D., and Campbell, W. (2017). The Big Five personality traits, Big Two metatraits and social media: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 70, pp.229-240.
- Lodhia, S., and Stone, G. (2017). Integrated Reporting in an Internet and Social Media Communication Environment: Conceptual Insights. *Australian Accounting Review*, 27(1), pp. 17-33.
- Lu, X. (2018). Cultural Differences in Consumer Engagement in Brand Related SNS Groups: A Cross-Cultural Study of China and the United States. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 31(5), pp. 295-307.
- Luborsky, M.R., and Rubinstein, R.L. (1995). Sampling in qualitative research: rationale, issues and methods. *Research on Aging*, 17, pp. 89–113.
- Luarn, P., and Lin, P.H.H. (2005). Toward an understanding of the behavioral to use mobile banking, *Computers in Human Behavior*, 21, pp. 873– 891.
- Luca, M. (2015). Chapter 12: User-Generated-Content and Social Media. *Handbook of Media Economics*, 1, pp. 563-592.
- Lueg, J.E., and R. Finney, Z. (2007). Interpersonal Communication in the Consumer Socialization Process: Scale Development and Validation. *Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice*. 15(1), pp. 25-39.
- Luo, P., Chen, K., and Wu, C. (2016). Measuring social influence for firm-level financial performance. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 20, pp. 15-29.
- Mahon, D., Cowan, C., and McCarthy, M. (2006). The role of attitudes, subjective norm, perceived control and habit in the consumption of ready meals and takeaways in Great Britain. *Food Quality and Preference*, (17)6, pp. 474-481.
- Mai, H.T.X., and Olsen, S.O. (2013). Consumer participation in virtual communities: The role of personal values and personality. *Journal of Marketing*, pp. 144-164.
- Mandal, D. (2012). Extending UTAUT to Explain Social Media Adoption by Microbusinesses. *International Journal of Managing Information Technology*, 4(4), pp. 1-11.
- Malhotra, Y., & Galletta, D. (2005). A multidimensional commitment model of volitional systems adoption and usage behavior. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 22(1), pp. 117–151.

- Masterman, M. (1970). The Nature of a Paradigm. In I. Lakatos & A. Musgrave (eds.), *Criticism and the Growth of Knowledge*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, pp. 59-89.
- Maxwell, J. (2013). *Qualitative Research Design: an Interactive Approach (Vol. 3)*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Maanen, J. (1979). The Fact of Fiction in Organizational Ethnography. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 24(4), pp. 539.
- Mangold, W.G., and Faulds, D.J. (2009). Social Media: The New Hybrid Element of the Promotion Mix. *Business Horizons*, 52(1), pp. 357-365.
- Mavri, M., and Ioannou, G. (2006). Customers' perspectives on online banking services. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 30(6), pp. 552-60.
- Manthiou, A, Chiang, L., and Tang, L. (2013). Identifying and responding to customer needs on Facebook Fan pages. *International Journal of Technology and Human Interaction*, 9(3), pp. 36-52.
- Michopoulou , E., and Moisa, D.G. (2018). Hotel Social Media metrics: The ROI dilemma. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 76(A), pp. 308-315.
- Malthouse, E., Haenlein, M., Skiera, B., Wege, E., and Zhang, M. (2013). Managing Customer Relationships in the Social Media Era: Introducing the Social CRM House. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 27(4), pp. 270-280.
- McDonald, R.I., and Crandall, C.S. (2015). Social norms and social influence. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 3, pp. 147-151.
- McGuire, W. J. (1968). Personality and Susceptibility to Social Influence. In E. F. Borgatta & W. W. Lambert (Eds.), *Handbook of Personality Theory and Research*. Chicago: Rand McNally
- McQuail, D. (1987). *Mass communication theory: An introduction. (2nd ed.)*. London SAGE
- McQuail, D. (2005). *Mass Communication Theory (5th Edition)*. London: Sage Publications
- McNeill, L., and Wyeth, E. (2011). The private label grocery choice: consumer drivers to purchase. *International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 21(1), pp. 95-109.
- Menon, K., and O'Connor, A. (2007). Building customer's affective commitment towards retail banks: the role of CRM in each 'moment of truth. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 12(2), pp. 157-68

- Miller, R., and Lammas, N. (2010). Social media and its implications for viral marketing. *Asia Pacific Public Relations Journal*, 11(1), pp. 1-9.
- Mills, A. J., Durepos, G., and Wiebe, E. (2010). *Encyclopedia of case study research*. London: Sage.
- Mitic, M., and Kapoulas, A. (2012). Understanding the role of social media in bank marketing. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 30(7), pp. 668-686.
- Morse, J.M. (1995). The significance of saturation. *Quality Health Research*, 5(2), pp. 147-149.
- Morgan, D. L. (1988). *Focus groups as qualitative research*. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Mow, S.M. (1996). Spatializing Culture: The Social Production and Social Construction of Public Space in Costa Rica. *American Ethnologist*, 23(4), pp. 861-879.
- Muhammad, L., Mahadi, B., and Hussin, N. (2017). Influence of social capital on customer's relationship satisfaction in the Pakistani banking industry. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 29(5), pp. 1036-1054.
- Müller, O., Junglas, I., vom Brocke, J., and Debortoli, S (2016). Utilizing big data analytics for information systems research: Challenges, promises and guidelines. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 25, pp. 289-302.
- Mueller, A., and Segal, D. (2015). Structured versus Semistructured versus Unstructured Interviews. *The Encyclopedia of Clinical Psychology*, pp.1-7.
- Mudrick, M., Miller, M., and Atkin, D. (2016). The influence of social media on fan reactionary behaviors. *Telematics and Informatics*, 33(4), pp. 896-903.
- Muntinga, D. G., Moorman, M., and Smit, E. G. (2011).Introducing COBRA: Exploring motivations for brand-related social media use. *International Journal of Advertising*, 30(1), pp. 13-46.
- Muniz, A. M., and O'Guinn, T. C. (2001). Brand community. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 27(4), pp. 412–432.
- Muniz, A. and Schau, H.J. (2007). The Impact of Market Use of Consumer Generated Content on a Brand Community. In Fitzsimons, G. And Morwitz, V. (Eds) *Advances in Consumer Research*, 34. Association of Consumer Research.

- Munzel, A., Meyer-Waarden, L., and Galan, J-P. (2018). The social side of sustainability: Well-being as a driver and an outcome of social relationships and interactions on SNSs. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, pp. 14-27.
- Murugesan, S. (2007). Understanding Web 2.0. *IT Professional*, 9(4), pp. 34-41.
- Murray, L. , Durkin, M., Worthington, S., and Clark, V. (2014). On the potential for Twitter to add value in retail bank relationships. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 19(4), pp. 277-290.
- Mutch, C. (2005). *Doing Educational Research: A Practitioner's Guide to Getting Started*. Wellington: NZCER Press.
- Myers, D. G. (1982). Polarizing Effects of Social Interaction. In Brandstätter, H., Davis, J. H. and Stocker-Kreichgauer, G. (eds). *Group Decision Making*, pp. 125–61. London: Academic Press.
- Nazar, M. (2013). Knowledge Sharing Intention Through the Social Media using Theory of Planned Behavior Approach. *SSRN Electronic Journal*.
- Naylor, R.W., Lamberton, C., and West, P.M. (2012). Beyond the ‘like’ button: the impact of mere virtual presence on brand evaluations and purchase intentions in social media settings. *Journal of Marketing*, 76(6), pp. 105-120.
- Negoescu R.A., and Gatica-Perez D (2008). Analyzing Flickr groups. In: *Proceedings of the 2008 international conference on content-based image and video retrieval, CIVR '08, ACM*. New York, pp. 417–426.
- Newman , R., chang, V., Walters, R.J., and Wills, G.B. (2016). Web 2.0 – The past and the future. *International Journal of Information Management*, 36(4), pp. 591-598.
- Nelson-Field, K., Riebe, E., and Sharp, B. (2012). What's Not to “Like?”. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 52(2), pp. 262-269.
- Ngai, E., Tao, S., and Moon, K. (2015). Social media research: Theories, constructs, and conceptual frameworks. *International Journal of Information Management*, 35(1), pp. 33-44.
- Norman, W. E., and Wolfe, A.W. (1974). Network analysis. In Honigmann, J. (1974) (eds) *Handbook of social and cultural anthropology*. Chicago: Rand McNally.
- Norris, N. (1997). Error, bias and validity in qualitative research. *Educational Action Research*, 5(1), pp. 172-176.
- Nov, O. (2007). What Motivates Wikipedians? *Communications of the ACM*, 47(12), pp. 41–46.

Nyumba, T. O, Wilson, K., Derrick, C., and Mukherjee, N. (2018). The use of focus group discussion methodology: Insights from two decades of application in conservation. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 9(1), pp.20-32.

OECD, (2007). Participative Web: user-created content - OECD. Available online: http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/science-and-technology/participative-web-and-user-created-content_9789264037472-en

Okazaki, S. (2009). Social influence model and electronic word of mouth. *International Journal of Advertising*, 28(3), pp. 439-472.

Okazaki, S., Natalia, S., and Sara, C. (2014). Gossip in SNSs: why people chitchat about campaigns. *International Journal of Market Research*. 56.

Ozuem, W. (2004). Conceptualising marketing communication in the new marketing paradigm. (DBA) Thesis, Ashcroft International Business School, Ashcroft.

Ozuem, W., Kerry, H., and Geoff, L. (2008). Communicating in the new interactive marketplace. *European Journal of Marketing*, 42(9/10), pp. 1059-1083.

Ozuem, W., and Tan, K. (2014). *Reconciling Social Media with Luxury Fashion Brands: An Exploratory Study*. In Aiello, L. (eds.) *Handbook of Research on Management of Cultural Products: E-Relationship Marketing and Accessibility Perspectives*. Hershey: IGI Global Publishers.

Ozuem, W., Thomas, T., and Lancaster, G. (2016). The influence of customer loyalty on small island economies: An empirical and exploratory study. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 24(6), pp. 447-469

Ozuem, W., Pinho, C.A., and Azemi, Y. (2016). UGC and Perceived Customer Value. In Ozuem, W and Bowen, G. (eds.) *Competitive Social Media Marketing Strategies*. IGI Global Publishers.

Ozuem, W., Patel, A., Howell, K.E., and Lancaster, G. (2017). An exploration of consumers' response to online services recovery initiatives. *International Journal of market Research*, 59(1), pp. 97-115.

Papacharissi, Z., and Mendelson, A. (2011). Toward a new(er) sociability: uses, gratifications and social capital on Facebook. In Papathanassopoulos, S. (Ed.), *Media Perspectives for the 21st Century*. New York: Routledge.

Park, D., Lee, J., and Han, I. (2007). The Effect of On-Line Consumer Reviews on Consumer Purchasing Intention: The Moderating Role of Involvement. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 11(4), pp. 125-148.

Patton, M. (2002). Two Decades of Developments in Qualitative Inquiry. *Qualitative Social Work: Research and Practice*, 1(3), pp. 261-283.

Patten, E., Ozuem, W., and Howell, K. (Fortcoming).Service quality in multichannel fashion retailing: an exploratory study. *Information Technology and People*.

Pattison, E. M. (1981). Introduction: The social network paradigm. *International Journal of Family Therapy*, 3(4), pp. 241-245.

Patterson, P.G., and Spreng, R.A. (1997). Modelling the relationship between perceived value, satisfaction and repurchase intentions in a business-to-business, services context: an empirical examination. *International Journal of Service Industry Management*, 8(5).

Park, C., and Lee. T.M. (2009). Antecedents of online reviews' usage and purchase influence: an empirical comparison of U.S. and Korean consumers. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 23, pp. 332-340.

Park, H., and Kim, Y. (2014). The role of social network websites in the consumer-brand relationship. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 21(4), pp. 460-467.

Park, M-S., Shin, J-K., and Ju, Y. (2017). Attachment styles and electronic word of mouth (e-WOM) adoption on SNSs. *Journal of Business Research*, 99, pp. 398-404.

Paschen, J., Pitt, L., Kietzmann, J., Dabirian, A., and Farshid, M. (2017). The brand personalities of brand communities: an analysis of online communication. *Online Information Review*, 41(7), pp. 1064-1075.

Perugini, M. and Bagozzi, R.P. (2001). The role of desires and anticipated emotions in goal-directed behaviours: Broadening and deepening the theory of planned behavior. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 40(1), pp. 79-98.

Perret-Clermont, A.-N., Perret, J.-F., & Bell, N. (1991). The social construction of meaning and cognitive activity in elementary school children. In L. B. Resnick, J. M. Levine, & S. D. Teasley (Eds.), *Perspectives on socially shared cognition* (pp. 41-62). Washington, DC, US: American Psychological Association.

Peng, S., Yang, A., Cao, L., Yu, S., and Xie D. (2017). Social influence modelling using information theory in mobile social networks. *Information Sciences*, 379, pp. 146-59

Phua, J., Jin, S., and Kim, J. (2017). Gratifications of using Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, or Snapchat to follow brands: The moderating effect of social comparison, trust, tie strength, and network homophily on brand identification, brand engagement, brand commitment, and membership intention. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(1), pp.412-424

Pine, J. B., and Gilmore, J. H. (2011).*The Experience Economy.2nd Edition*. Boston: Harvard Business Review Press.

- Porter, C. E., and Donthu, N. (2008). Cultivating trust and harvesting value in virtual communities. *Management Science*, 54, pp. 113-128.
- Postmes, T., Spears, R., and Cihangir (2001). Quality of decision making and group norms. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 80, pp. 918-930.
- Prendergast, G., Ko, D., and Siu Yin, V. (2010). Online word of mouth and consumer purchase intentions. *International Journal of Advertising*, 29(5), pp. 687-708.
- Pry, C.G. (2010). Social media: the less-noticed risks. *ABA Bank Marketing*, 42(7), pp. 22-7.
- Proskurnikov, A.V., Tempo, R., Cao, M., and Friedkin, N.E. (2017). Opinion evolution in time-varying social influence networks with prejudiced agents. *IFAC-Papers OnLine*
- Proenca, J., Martins Silva, M., and Fernanades, T. (2010), The impact of the internet upon bank marketing. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 15(2), pp. 160-75.
- Pulizzi, J. (2013). How to know content marketing when you see it. *E-Content*, 36(10), pp. 16-17.
- Qi, J., Monod, E., Fang, B., and Deng, S. (2018). Theories of Social Media: Philosophical Foundations. *Engineering*, 4(1), pp. 94-102.
- Quan-Haase, A., and Young, A.L. (2010). Uses and gratifications of social media: a comparison of Facebook and instant messaging. *Bulletin of Science, Technology and Society*, 30, pp. 350-361.
- Quinn, K. (2016). Why We Share: A Uses and Gratifications Approach to Privacy Regulation in Social Media Use. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 60(1), pp.61-86.
- Qualman, E. (2009). *Socialnomics: How social media transforms the way we live and do business*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.
- Raacke, J., and Bonds-Raacke, J. (2008). MySpace and Facebook: Applying the Uses and Gratifications Theory to Exploring Friend-Networking Sites. *Cyber Psychology & Behavior*, 11(2), pp. 169-174.
- Rainie, L., and Wellman, B. (2012). *Networked: the new social operating system*. MIT Press
- Rashotte, L. (2007). Social influence. In: *The Blackwell Encyclopedia of Social Psychology*, 9, pp. 562–563.
- Rajaobelina, L., Brun, I., and Toufaily, E. (2013). A relational classification of online financial institutioning consumers. *International Journal of Financial institution Marketing*, 31(3), pp. 187-205.

- Raven, B.H. (2008). The Bases of Power and the Power/Interaction Model of Interpersonal Influence. *Analyses of Social Issues and Public Policy*, 8(1), pp. 1-22.
- Richerson, P. J., and Boyd, R. (2005). *Not by Genes Alone: How Culture Transformed Human Evolution*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Rialti, R., Zollo, L., Pellegrini, M.M., and Ciappei, C. (2017). Exploring the Antecedents of Brand Loyalty and Electronic Word of Mouth in Social-Media-Based Brand Communities: Do Gender Differences Matter?. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 30(3), pp. 147-160.
- Rhodes, R. E., and Courneya, K. S. (2003). Investigating multiple components of attitude, subjective norm, and perceived control: An examination of the TPB in the exercise domain. *British Journal of Social Psychology*, 42, pp. 129–146.
- Robinson, O.C. (2014) Sampling in Interview-Based Qualitative Research: A Theoretical and Practical Guide. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 11(1), pp. 25-41.
- Rodriguez-Ardura, I., Martinez-Lopez, F. J., and Luna, P. (2010). Going with the consumer towards the social web environment: a review of extant knowledge. *International Journal of Electronic Marketing and Retailing*, 3(4), pp. 415-440.
- Rodgers, S., Wang, Y., Rettie, R. and Alpert, F. (2007). The Web Motivation Inventory: replication, extension and application to internet advertising. *International Journal of Advertising*, 26(4), pp. 447–476.
- Sandelowski, M. (1995). Sample size in qualitative research. *Research in Nursing & Health*, 18(2), pp.179-183.
- Sandelowski, M. (2000). Whatever happened to qualitative description?. *Research in Nursing & Health*, 23(4), pp. 334-340.
- Saunders, M., and Townsed, K. (2016). Reporting and justifying the number of interview participants in organization and workplace research. *British Journal of Management*, 27(4), pp. 1-17.
- Saunders, B., Sim, J., Kingstone, T., Baker, S., Waterfield, J., Bartlam, B., Burroughs, H., and Jinks, C. (2017). Saturation in qualitative research: exploring its conceptualization and operationalization. *Quality & Quantity*, 52(4), pp. 1893-1907.
- Safko, L., Brake, D., and David, K. (2009) *The Social Media Bible: Tactics, Tools, and Strategies for Business Success*. NY: Wiley
- Schrader, D. (2015). Constructivism and Learning in the Age of Social Media: Changing Minds and Learning Communities. *New Directions for Teaching and Learning*, (144), pp. 23-35.

- Schultheiss, D.E., Wallace E. (2012) An Introduction to Social Constructionism in Vocational Psychology and Career Development. In: McIlveen P., Schultheiss D.E. (eds) *Social Constructionism in Vocational Psychology and Career Development. Career Development Series (Connecting Theory and Practice), vol 4*. Rotterdam : SensePublishers.
- Sciglipaglia, D., and Ely, D. (2006). Customer account relationships and e-retail banking usage. *Journal of Financial Services Marketing*, 10(4), pp. 109-22.
- Scott, E.J., Eves, F.F., French, D.P., and Hoppe, R.P. (2007). The theory of planned behavior predicts self-reports of walking, but not step-count. *British Journal of Health and Psychology*, 12, pp. 601-620.
- Schau, H. J., Muñiz, Jr., A. M., and Arnould, E. J. (2009). How brand community practices create value. *Journal of Marketing*, 73(5), pp. 30–51.
- See-To, E.W.K., and Ho, K.K.W. (2014). Value co-creation and purchase intention in social network sites: the role of eWOM and trust – a theoretical analys. *Computer in Human Behavior*, 31, pp. 182-189.
- Sengupta, S., and Sahay, A. (2018). Social enterprises in the Indian context: conceptualizing through qualitative lens. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 8(1).
- Sheldon, P. (2016). Facebook Friend Request: Applying the Theory of Reasoned Action to Student-Teacher Relationships on Facebook. *Journal of Broadcasting & Electronic Media*, 60(2), pp. 269-285.
- Shi, Z., Rui, H., and Whinston, A. (2014). Content Sharing in a Social Broadcasting Environment: Evidence from Twitter. *MIS Quarterly*, 38(1), pp. 123-142.
- Sinha, K.S., Subramanian, S., Bhattacharya, K., Chaudhary (2012). The contemporary framework on social media analytics as an emerging tool for behavior informatics, HR analytics and business process. *Journal of Contemporary Management Issues*, 17(2), pp. 65-84.
- Siikanen, M., Baltakys, K., kannianinen, J., Mukkamala, R., and Hussain, A. (2018). Facebook drives behavior of passive households in stock markets. *Finance Research Letters*, 27, pp. 208-213
- Simonson, I., Carmon, Z., Dhar, R., Drolet, A., and Nowlis, S.M. (2001). Consumer research: in search of identity. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 52, pp. 294-275.
- Simons, H. (2009). *Case study research in practice*. Sage Publishers
- Shen, A. X. L., Cheung, C. M. K., Lee, M. K. O., and Chen, H. (2011). How Social Influence Affects We-Intention to Use Instant Messaging: The Moderating Effect of Usage Experience. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 13(2), pp. 157-169.

- Shih, K.H., Chang, C.J., and Li, B. (2010). Assessing knowledge creation and intellectual capital in the banking industry. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 11(1), pp. 74-89.
- Shih, C., Lin, T., and Luarn, P. (2014). Fan-centric social media: The Xiaomi phenomenon in China. *Business Horizons*, 57(3), pp. 349-358.
- Snelson, C. (2016). Qualitative and Mixed Methods Social Media Research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 15(1).
- Smith, J.R., and Louis, W.R. (2009). Group Norms and the Attitude–Behaviour Relationship. *Social Personality And Psychology Compass*. 3(1), pp. 19-35.
- Smith, K.T. (2012). Longitudinal study of digital marketing strategies targeting Millennials. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*. 29(2), pp. 86 – 92.
- Sohn, D. (2014). Coping with information in social media: The effects of network structure and knowledge on perception of information value . *Computers in Human Behavior*, 32, pp. 145–151
- Spillecke, D., and Perrey, J. (2012). Retail Marketing and Branding: A Definitive Guide to Maximizing ROI (2nd ed.). New Jersey: Wiley Publishers.
- Sridhar, S., and Srinivasan, R. (2012). Social influence effects in online product ratings. *Journal of Marketing*, 76(5), pp. 70-88.
- Stefanone, M., Yue, Z., and Toh, Z. (2018). A social cognitive approach to traditional media content and social media use: Selfie-related behavior as competitive strategy. *New Media & Society*, 21(2), pp. 317-335
- Steinfeld, C., Ellison, N. B., and Lampe, C. (2008). Social capital, self-esteem, and use of online social network sites: A longitudinal analysis. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 29, pp. 434–445.
- Steenhuis, H.J. (2015) Iterative-Pragmatic Case Study Method and Comparisons with Other Case Study Method Ideologies. In: Strang K.D. (eds) *The Palgrave Handbook of Research Design in Business and Management*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan
- Stokinger, E., and Ozuem, W. (2014). Social media and customer retention: Implication for luxury beauty industry. In Bowen, G. & Ozuem, W. (eds.) *Computer-mediated marketing strategies: social media and online brand communities*. Hershey: IGI Global Publishers.
- Stone, M. (2009). Staying customer-focused and trusted: Web 2.0 and Customer 2.0 in financial services. *Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, 16(2), pp. 101-31.
- Sutcliffe, A., Binder, J., and Dunbar, R. (2018). Activity in social media and intimacy in social relationships. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 85, pp. 227-235.

- Sung, Y., Kim, Y., Kwon, O., and Moon, J. (2010). An explorative study of Korean consumer participation in virtual brand communities in social network sites. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 23(5), pp. 430-445
- Tajfel, H. (1978) *Differentiation between Social Groups Studies in the Social Psychology of Intergroup Relations*. Salt Lake City: Academic Press.
- Tang, Q., Gu, B., and Whinston, A. (2011). Content contribution in social media: The case of YouTube. In *Proceedings of the Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, pp. 4476-4485.
- Tang, J., Zhang, P., and Wu, P. (2015). Categorizing consumer behavioral responses and artifact design features: The case of online advertising. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 17(3), pp. 513–532.
- Tarkiainen, A., and Sundqvist, S. (2005). Subjective norms, attitudes and intentions of Finnish consumers in buying organic food. *British Food Journal*, 107(11), pp. 808 – 822.
- Taylor, D.G., Strutton, D., and Thompson, K. (2012). Self-enhancement as a motivation for sharing online advertising. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 12, pp. 13-28.
- Teven, J.J. (2007). Effects of Supervisor Social Influence, Nonverbal Immediacy, and Biological Sex on Subordinates' Perceptions of Job Satisfaction, Liking, and Supervisor Credibility. *Communication Quarterly*, 55(2), pp. 155-177.
- Toder-Alon, A., and Brunel, F. (2018). Peer-to-peer word-of-mouth: word-of-mouth extended to group online exchange. *Online Information Review*, 42(2), pp. 176-190.
- Tong, A., Sainsbury, P., and Craig, J. (2007). Consolidated criteria for reporting qualitative research (COREQ): a 32-item checklist for interviews and focus groups. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 19(6), pp. 349-357.
- Trusov, M., Bucklin, R.E., and Koen, P. (2009). Effects of word-of-mouth versus traditional marketing: findings from an internet social networking site. *Journal of Marketing*, 73(5), pp. 90–102.
- Truong, Y., and Simmons, G. (2010). Perceived intrusiveness in digital advertising: strategic marketing implications. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 18(3), pp. 239-56.
- Tsai, W., and Men, L. (2013). Motivations and Antecedents of Consumer Engagement With Brand Pages on SNSs. *Journal of Interactive Advertising*, 13(2), pp. 76-87.
- Tsai, H-T., and Bagozzi, R. P. (2014). Contribution Behavior in Virtual Communities: Cognitive, Emotional, and Social Influences, *MIS Quarterly*, 38(1), pp. 143-163.

Tsao, W., Hsieh, M., Shih, L., and Lin, T. (2015). Compliance with eWOM: The influence of hotel reviews on booking intention from the perspective of consumer conformity. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 46, pp. 99-111.

UBL (2018). Index. Data retrieved from <http://www.ublirect.com/Corporate/index.aspx>

Vagle, M.D. (2015). *Crafting phenomenological research*. CA: Left Coast Press, Walnut Creek

Valtysson, B. (2010). Access culture: Web 2.0 and cultural participation. *International journal of culture and policy*. 16(2), pp. 200-214.

VanMeter, R., Grisaffe, D., and Chonko, L. (2015). Of “Likes” and “Pins”: The Effects of Consumers' Attachment to Social Media. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 32, pp. 70-88.

Varnali, K., and Gorgulu, V. (2014). A social influence perspective on expressive political participation in Twitter: the case of OccupyGezi. *Information, Communication & Society*, 18(1), pp. 1-16.

Vemuri, A. (2010). Getting social: bridging the gap between banking and social media. *Global Finance*, 24(5), pp. 20-1.

Vollmer, C., and Precourt, G. (2008). *Always On Advertising, Marketing, and Media in an Era of Consumer Control*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

Wang, L., Doucet, L., Northcraft, G. (2006), Culture, Affect, and Social Influence in Decision-Making Groups. In Ya-Ru Chen (eds.) *National Culture and Groups (Research on Managing Groups and Teams*, 9, pp.147 – 172. Emerald Group Publishing Limited,

Wang, X., Yu, C., and Wei, Y. (2012). Social Media Peer Communication and Impacts on Purchase Intentions: A Consumer Socialization Framework. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 26(4), pp. 198-208.

Wang, S-T. (2014). Consumer characteristics and social influence factors on green purchasing intentions. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 32(7), pp. 738-753.

Wang, N., and Sun, Y. (2016). Social influence or personal preference? Examining the determinants of usage intention across social media with different sociability. *Information Development*, 32(5), pp. 1442-1456.

Wang, J-J., Wang, L-Y., and Wang, M-M. (2018). Understanding the effects of eWOM social ties on purchase intentions A moderated mediation investigation. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 28, pp. 54-62.

Walther, J.B., Liang, Y.J., Ganster, T., Wohn, D.Y., and Emington, J. (2012). Online reviews, helpfulness ratings, and consumer attitudes: An extension of congruity theory to

multiple sources in Web 2.0. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 18 (1), pp. 97-112.

Walsh, G., Gwinner, K.P., and Swanson, S.R. (2004). What makes mavens tick? Exploring the motives of market mavens' initiation of information diffusion. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 21(2), pp. 109-122.

Walsh, S., Gilmore, A., and Carson, D. (2004). Managing and implementing simultaneous transaction and relationship marketing. *The International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 22(7), pp. 468-83.

Wang, X., and Li, Y. (2016). Users' satisfaction with social network sites: a self-determination perspective. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 56, pp. 48-54.

Wang, Y., and Yu, C. (2017). Social interaction-based consumer decision-making model in social commerce: The role of word of mouth and observational learning. *International Journal of Information Management*, 37(3), pp. 179-189.

Wang, X., Tajvidi, M., Lin, X., and Hajli, N. (2019). Towards an Ethical and Trustworthy Social Commerce Community for Brand Value Co-creation: A trust-Commitment Perspective. *Journal of Business Ethics*, pp. 1-16

Watts, D.J. (2004). The 'New' Science of Networks. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 30, pp. 243-70.

Weber, M., Fulk, J., and Monge, P. (2016). The Emergence and Evolution of SNSs as an Organizational Form. *Management Communication Quarterly*, 30(3), pp. 305-332.

Wellman, B., and Gulia, M. (1999). Net-Surfers Don't Ride Alone: Virtual Communities as Communities. In Wellman, B. (eds) *Networks in the Global Village: Life in Contemporary Communities*, pp. 331-366. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.

Wellman, B., Quan-Haase, A., Witte, J., and Hampton, K.N. (2001). Does the Internet increase, decrease, or supplement social capital? Social networks, participation, and community commitment. *American Behavioral Scientist*, 45(3), pp. 437-456.

Weinberg, B.D., and Pehlivan, E. (2011). Social Spending: Managing the Social Media Mix. *Business Horizons*, 54(1), pp. 275-282.

Whiting, A., and Williams, D. (2013). Why people use social media: a uses and gratifications approach. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 16(4), pp. 362-369.

Williams, L., and Cothrell, J. (2000). Four smart ways to run online communities. *Sloan Management Review*, 41, pp. 81-91.

Willis, J. (1995). Recursive, reflective instructional design model based on constructivist-interpretist theory. *Educational Technology*, 35 (6), pp. 5-23.

- Windels, K., Heo, J., Joeng, Y., Porter, L., and Wang, R. (2018). My friend likes this brand: Do ads with social context attract more attention on SNSs ? *Computers in Human Behavior*, 84, pp. 420-429.
- World Bank (2017). Pakistan to Record Highest Growth Rate in Nine Years: WB Report. Retrieved from <http://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2017/05/19/pakistan-to-record-highest-growth-rate-in-nine-years-wb-report>
- Wood, W. (2000). Attitude Change: Persuasion and Social Influence. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 51, pp. 539–70.
- Wood, W., and Hayes, T. (2012). Social Influence on consumer decisions: Motives, modes, and consequences. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 22(3), pp. 324-328.
- Wu, S-C., and Fang, W-C. (2010). The effect of consumer-to-consumer interactions on idea generation in virtual brand community relationships. *Technovation*, 30(4), pp. 238–248.
- Wyrwoll C. (2014) Metadata in UGC. *In Social Media*. Wiesbaden: Springer Vieweg.
- Xie, K., and Lee, Y.J. (2015). Social media and brand purchase: quantifying the effects of exposures to earned and owned social media activities in a two-stage decision making model. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 32(2), pp. 204-238.
- Xiao, Y., and Lo, H. K. (2016). Day-to-day departure time modeling under social network influence. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 92, pp. 54–72.
- Xu, X., Li, Q., Peng, L., Hsia, T.L., Huang, C.J., and Wu, J.H. (2017). The impact of informational incentives and social influence on consumer behavior during Alibaba’s online shopping carnival. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 76(12), pp. 245-254.
- Yahaya, I., Yamoah, F., and Adam, F. (2015). Consumer motivation and willingness to pay for “safer” vegetables in Ghana. *British Food Journal*, 117(3), pp. 1043-1065.
- Yamoah, F., Fearne, A., and Duffy, R. (2014). Exploring supermarket loyalty card analysis to identify who buys fairtrade. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 24(3), pp. 328-346.
- Yamoah, F., Duffy, R., Petrovici, D., and Fearne, A. (2015). Towards a Framework for Understanding Fairtrade Purchase Intention in the Mainstream Environment of Supermarkets. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 136(1), pp. 181-197.
- Yang, S., Liu, Y., and Wei, J. (2016). Social capital on mobile SNS addiction. *Internet Research*, 26(4), pp. 982-1000.

- Yankova, I., and Ozuem, W. (2014). *Social Media and its Implications for Marketing Communications*. In Bowen, G. & Ozuem, W. (eds.) *Computer-mediated marketing strategies: social media and online brand communities*. IGI Global Publishers.
- Yen, Y. (2016). Factors enhancing the posting of negative behavior in social media and its impact on venting negative emotions. *Management Decision*, 54(10), pp.2462-2484.
- Yilmaz, K. (2013). Comparison of Quantitative and Qualitative Research Traditions: epistemological, theoretical, and methodological differences. *European Journal of Education*, 48(2), pp.311-325.
- Young, S.D., and Jordan, A.H. (2013). The Influence of Social Networking Photos on Social Norms and Sexual Health Behaviors. *Cyber psychology Behavior Society Network*, 16(4), pp. 243–247.
- Yoo, K.-H., Lee, Y., Gretzel, U., and Fesenmaier, D. R., (2009). Trust in Travel-Related Consumer Generated Media. In: Höpken, W., Gretzel, U. & Law, R., (eds.) *Information and Communication Technologies in Tourism 2009*. Amsterdam: Springer.
- Yoo, K. H., and Gretzel, U. (2011). Influence of personality on travel-related consumer-generated media creation. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 27 (2), pp. 609-621.
- Yoo, Y. (2010). Computing in everyday life: A call for research on experiential computing. *MIS Quarterly*, 34(2), pp. 213-231.
- Young, R., and Collin, A. (2004). Introduction: Constructivism and social constructionism in the career field. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 64(3), pp.373-388.
- Youn, S.,and Jin, S. V. (2017). Reconnecting with the past in social media: The moderating role of social influence in nostalgia marketing on Pinterest. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 16(6), pp. 565–576. doi:10.1002/cb.1655
- Yuksel, M., and Labrecque, L. (2016). “Digital buddies”: parasocial interactions in social media. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 10(4), pp.305-320.
- Zaglia, M. E. (2013). Brand communities embedded in social networks. *Journal of Business Research*, 66(2), pp. 216–223.
- Zhang, Z (2010) Feeling the sense of community in social networking usage. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 57(2), pp. 225–239.
- Zhang, L., Tam, V. C., Wan, W. W., Wu, P., and Luk, C. L. (2015). An exploratory study on school children’s intent attributions for parental structuring behaviors. *Psychological Reports* 116(1), pp. 249–273.

Zhang, M., Guo, L., Hu.M., and Liu, W. (2017). Influence of customer engagement with company social networks on stickiness: Mediating effect of customer value creation. *International Journal of Information Management*, 37(3), pp. 229-240.

Zheng, X., Cheung, C.M.K., Lee, M.K.O., and Liang, L. (2015). Building brand loyalty through user engagement in online brand communities in SNSs. *Information Technology & People*, 28(1), pp.90-106.

Zhou, T. (2011). Understanding online community user participation: a social influence perspective. *Internet Research*, 2(1), pp.67-81.

Zhou, T., and Li, H. (2014). Understanding mobile SNS continuance usage in China from the perspectives of social influence and privacy concern. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 37, pp. 283-289.

Zhou, T. (2017). Understanding social influence on mobile SNSs. *Information Development*, pp. 1-10.

Zhu, Y., and Chen, H. (2015). Social media and human need satisfaction: Implications for social media marketing. *Business Horizons*, 58(3), pp. 335-345.

Zhu, Z., Wang, J., Wang, X., and Wan, X. (2016). Exploring factors of user's peer-influence behavior in social media on purchase intention: Evidence from QQ. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 63, pp. 980-987.

Zingale, N. (2013). The phenomenology of sharing: social media networking, asserting, and telling. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 13(3), pp. 288-297.

